

*Harmonization and Networking
in Higher Education*

*Building a Common
Credit Transfer System
for GMS and beyond*

June 2013

Bangkok, Thailand

Report prepared by Fernando Palacio

Responsibility disclaim

Views presented in this report by the author do not necessarily represent the those of either SEAMEO RIHED or ADB, while any mistakes or misconceptions that may exist in the report are full responsibility of the author.

Fernando Palacio

Executive summary

This report is the outcome from joint efforts of SEAMEO RIHED and the Asian Development Bank in looking for new strategies to facilitate harmonisation of regional higher education.

With view to the upcoming setting of the ASEAN Community and the increasing pressures brought on most societies by globalization and the rapid regional integration processes the present report represents the research outcomes from the first out of four phases designed to set a multilateral scheme for transfer of academic credits in the region. The first phase – *Explore*- provides the base for next stages: *Experiment*, *Experience* and *Expand*; it constitutes an in-depth research on existing credit transfer.

This report, and the project as a whole, is based on the premise that increasing interconnectivity among the labour markets among the countries of the region will put higher education systems and the institutions therein in a situation where they will need to make deep revisions of their traditional roles, the contents they provide as part of their curricula, the methods of teaching and the ways they interact with their environments.

These changes are putting HEIs in a situation where they cannot longer think and frame themselves within the context of clearly well defined traditional national borders. Regionalization means more integrated and complex markets and societies; which in turn mean that HEIs need to be prepared to provide their students with an education that is not only integral, updated and functional but also that is ready to prepare students to be well equipped to face these new challenges.

The report presents a review of existing research on student mobility issues with a focus on credit transfer systems as mechanisms that ease mobility. It covers experiences at the global level but with more focus on the Great Mekong Subregion region and its nearby neighbours.

Research outcomes, as the result from *Explore* phase of the project *Harmonization and Networking in Higher Education. Building a Common Credit Transfer System for GMS and beyond*, is a theoretical knowledge base from where to approach and build the next faces.

The report presents the findings of the research carried out by SEAMEO RIHED in two areas:

- 1) A comparative study on main credit transfer systems at the world level resulting from the comparison of 20 multilateral credit systems that spots practices and mechanism of transfer (recognition and accreditation of qualifications). This part of the research provides enriching insights in terms of logics and procedures of how different systems deal with the transfer of credits and the sharing of information among participants.

- 2) A second comparative analysis at the country level presents findings from a comparative research of 10 countries in the GMs and nearby region that offers an overview on credit systems being used in those countries and the opportunities they present for more harmonization and interaction among higher education systems in the region.

Finally the report puts forward strategic ideas and colligates findings from the research with a number of actions proposed for further integration based on recommendations coming from main higher education stakeholders on alternative plans to promote student mobility and harmonization of the higher education landscape.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	9
1.1. Background	9
1.2. A common credit transfer system for the region	12
1.3. Credit transfer systems: what they do.....	16
1.4. Credit systems in the region	18
1.5. Challenges of setting a credit transfer system for the region (Problem statement)	18
1.6. Goals of the project	19
1.7. Brief description of the methodology	20
1.8. Structure of the report.....	21
2. Literature review: student mobility and credit transfer	23
2.1. International student mobility.....	23
2.1.1. Strategies toward regionalization of HE.....	24
2.2. Regional student mobility	26
2.2.1. Europe and the milestone of the Bologna Process	26
2.2.2. Harmonizing HE in Asia	28
2.2.2.1. Student mobility and credit transfer in Asia	29
2.3. International instruments on mobility and recognition	31
2.4. Conclusion.....	31
3. Research methodology for the <i>Explore</i> phase.....	33
3.1. Goals of the project as a whole	33
3.2. Explanation of the first phase - <i>Explore</i> -.....	34
3.2.1. Research design and implementation.....	34
3.2.2. Goals for the first phase of the project: <i>Explore</i>	34
3.2.3. The three parts of <i>Explore</i>	35
3.3. Selection of countries and resource persons.....	36
3.4. Collection of data	36
3.5. Selection of sources (unit of analysis).....	37
3.6. Samples and analysis of the data.....	37
3.6.1. Comparison of credit transfer systems	37
3.6.1.1. The sample for credit transfer systems.....	37
3.6.1.2. Analysis of data from credit transfer systems: categories for comparison.....	38
3.6.2. Comparison of credit systems at the country level.....	39
3.6.2.1. The samples for credit systems in each country	39
3.6.2.2. The questionnaires.....	39
3.6.2.3. Making the country comparisons	40
4. Comparison of main multilateral credit transfer systems	42
4.1. Why comparing credit transfer systems	42
4.2. Summary chart comparing credit transfer systems	42
4.2.1. Types of credit transfer systems	58

4.2.2. Credit Transfer Systems Goals	62
4.2.2.1. Harmonization.....	62
4.2.2.2. Quality assurance	62
4.2.2.3. Curricula development.....	63
4.2.2.4. Mobility and international integration.....	63
4.2.2.5. Employability of graduates	64
4.2.2.6. Information share	64
4.2.2.7. Attractiveness & visibility.....	64
4.2.3. Credit transfer systems' <i>technicalities</i> in perspective.....	64
4.2.3.1.1. Commonalities	65
4.2.3.1.2. Differences	67
4.2.3.2. Intrinsic features	71
4.2.3.2.1. Transfer procedures	71
4.2.3.2.2. Information flow	77
4.2.3.2.3. Deciding courses in different HEIs	78
4.2.3.2.4. Measurement of the students' workload	79
4.2.3.2.5. Scale matching	83
4.2.3.2.6. Quality Assurance	85
4.2.3.2.7. Diploma supplements (DS).....	86
4.3. Conclusions	86
5. Credit systems at the country level	90
5.1. Findings from the country cases	90
5.2. National education systems in perspective	91
5.3. Credit systems at the national level.....	96
5.4. Transferability of students' workloads in the systems	97
5.4.1. Commonalities	97
5.4.2. Differences	98
5.6. CTS the HEIs' eyes	106
5.7. CTS the students' eyes	113
5.8. Conclusion.....	118
6. Integration of findings toward a common regional CTS	121
6.1. Basic thinking and what to expect from a CTS.....	121
6.2. Context.....	122
6.2.1. Student mobility and credit transfer	123
6.2.2. HEIs autonomy and credit recognition.....	124
6.3. Common grounds for accreditation and recognition	126
6.4. Credit transfer systems at the core	128
6.4.1. Common regional ground for a future agreement	129
6.4.2. Credit transfer systems as a complex composite.....	131
6.4.3. Rules governing the transfer of credits.....	134

6.4.4. Principles guiding recognition of credits	134
6.4.5. Credits per course and ranges of comparison	135
6.4.6. Maximum allowable transfer credits	136
6.5. Issues to consider in the near future	136
Chapter 7	139
8. Recommendations.....	143
8.1. Recommendations to all stakeholders.....	143
8.2. Recommendations to the governments	144
8.3. Recommendations to HEIs.....	145
8.4. Recommendations to the students.....	148
8.5. Other considerations: Results from group discussions during workshops 1 and 2	149
Bangkok, September and November 2012	149
8.5.1. Recognition	154
8.5.2. Quality assurance	155
8.5.3. Credit equivalence	156
8.5.4. Transferability of credits	157
8.5.5. Grade Transfer	157
8.5.6. Sources of possible conflict	158
8.5.7. Course assessment criteria	159
8.5.8. Dealing with different grading systems	159
8.5.9. Options for grade transfer	160
8.5.10. Supporting mechanisms and system context	160
9. Way forward for the project: Proposed model for phase two: <i>Experiment</i>	162
Asian Convention on Academic Credit Recognition for HEIs	162
Development and implementation of pilot project.....	162
9.1. Introduction and background	162
9.2. Rationale	162
9.3. Justification (Relevance of implementing next phases).....	163
9.4. Goals of the project in its next stages.....	164
9.5. Action plan: reaching the goals.....	164
9.6. Expected outcomes.....	165
9.8. Tentative structure of the <i>Asian Convention on Academic Credit Recognition for HEIs</i>	166
10. Glossary & Acronyms	168
10.1. Glossary.....	168
10.2. Acronyms	172
11. Resources.....	173
12. Annexes	179
13. Country reports	180

List of tables

Table # and name	Page
Table 1: Credit Transfer Systems included per table.....	36
Table 2: Transversal comparative analysis of data	38
Table 3: Summary of data comparing Credit Transfer Systems.....	41
Table 4: Credit transfer systems according to who set them	55
Table 5: Credit transfer systems according to number of stakeholders involved in the flow	56
Table 6: Credit transfer systems according to historic linkages or geographic vicinity.....	57
Table 7: Credit transfer systems according to implementation unit	58
Table 8: Groups of credit transfer systems as conventions and conversion tools.....	72
Table 9: Credit transfer system according to kind of transfer.....	73
Table 10: Country level overview of credit system	88
Table 11: Summary of findings on credit systems in the eyes of governments.....	96
Table 12: Summary of findings on credit systems in the eyes of HEIs	102
Table 13: Advantages and challenges students perceive about credit systems in use.....	110
Table 14: List of countries participating in multilateral mobility programmes.....	119
Table 15: Centralized, moderated and decentralized HE systems per country.....	121
Table 16: Outcomes from the discussions during Workshops 1 and 2.....	146

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Countries of Asia have shown increasing will to deepen their connections and interactions by looking at the rich regional diversity as a source of potentials rather than as historical threats and challenges. In so doing, governments in the region have put forward initiatives to boost integration mainly, but not only, on the economic field.

Regionalization is more evident among countries in the Southeast Asia where dialogue and efforts have been ongoing since the mid 1960's; however the phenomenon greatly exceeds projects like ASEAN as increasing number of initiatives are set to integrate Southeast Asia and East Asia under projects referred to as ASEAN+3 to include China, Japan and Korea.

ASEAN Leaders set a vision to build an ASEAN Community; which is expected to be formally launched in 2015 and consisting of three pillars: 1) ASEAN Economic Community (AEC), 2) ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community (ASCC) and 3) ASEAN Political-Security Community (APSC).

The primary goal of ASCC is contributing to realizing an ASEAN Community that is people-centred and socially responsible based on shared values; where the creation of a shared sense of identity among these nations calls for a more engaged role of higher education institutions (from here on referred to as HEIs) (Omar, Jan, Hamid, & Akhir, 2009). It is within the framework of these principles that the project (Harmonization and Networking in Higher Education Building a Common Credit Transfer System for GMS and beyond) falls into place.

At the same time countries in Greater Mekong Subregion (GMS) are implementing the GMS Human Resource Development Strategic Framework and Action Plan -under ADB's R-PATA 7275, 2009- aiming to strengthen the engagement of stakeholders in quality assurance (QA) and credit transfer systems (from here on referred to as CTS) among universities in GMS countries (Asian Development Bank, 2009).

This Strategic Framework and Action Plan includes among the opportunities for GMS the need to harmonize national regulations, standards and policies in order to facilitate the cross-border flow of investments, goods and services, workers, and students. Among the objectives of the Framework, specifically addressing High Education (from here on referred to as HE) it refers to the need to support initiatives that facilitate the process of sub regional cooperation and integration, for instance through harmonizing national regulations and standards in order to facilitate the effective regional utilization of GMS human resources, such as the portability of educational skills and training qualifications. The strategic framework also refers to high education in its programme *Promoting Regional Cooperation in Education and Skills Development* in its six objectives¹; which closely relate to the goals of the present study (Polytechnics International New Zealand Ltd, 2011).

Both schemes –*ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community* and *GMS Human Resource Development Strategic Framework and Action Plan*- are meant to contribute towards the harmonizing of HES in the region, through mechanisms like Quality Assurance and Credit Transfer.

¹(1) Developing and piloting a framework for the mutual recognition of technical and vocational skills in the GMS phase 1.
(2) Developing and piloting a framework for the mutual recognition of technical and vocational skills in the GMS phase 2.
(3) Facilitating harmonization of technical and vocational teacher training standards.
(4) Facilitating subregional cooperation in establishing quality assurance systems in technical and vocational education.
(5) Facilitating subregional cooperation in establishing quality assurance systems in higher education.
(6) Adopting secondary level exit standards and cross-border recognition.

A number of international agreements at the regional level have been signed to promote wider access to education, seeking to make it more inclusive and democratic, while encouraging ways to facilitate international recognition of qualifications and skills. In this sense, the regional conventions on the recognition of HE studies and qualifications that adopted under the auspices of UNESCO in different parts of the world deserve special mention here. These instruments seek to regulate mutual recognition of HE studies and degrees among member countries of the respective conventions. Of particular interest for SEAMEO RIHED's study on credit transfer systems is the Regional Convention on the Recognition of Studies, Diplomas and Degrees in Higher Education in Asia and the Pacific of 1983(UNESCO, 2009) that was later revised in Tokyo in 2011 as it provides the most thorough legal instrument in this regard for the region.

Regionalization of HE materialises through agreements that integrate education systems making them permeable and allowing for international mobility of students; governments and HEIs show interest in setting and participating in multilateral exchange programmes as in the cases of Erasmus among HEIs in Europe, Erasmus Mundus connecting HEIs in Europe and other continents; UMAP's exchange programme that connects HEIs in Asia and the Pacific; AIMS and AUN exchange programmes both of which link HEIs in Southeast Asia, and Campus Asia that colligates HEIs among East Asian countries².

All these programmes share the goal of promoting international mobility of students as a strategy to facilitate and support economic, political and social regional integration based on mutual understanding of cultural differences as a source for synergy and cooperation.

They encourage the generation of new options for institutions and enterprises through fostering direct contact of students and staff; which creates new business opportunities and innovation in the industrial and service worlds as mobilized students constitute a pool of well qualified and open-minded young people that can revitalize and contribute to new forms of production and service as future professionals.

These programmes are typically set on the assumption that by making students live in other cultures fosters their awareness and sensitivity towards otherness; they contribute to creating new identities like pan-European or Pan-Asian identity that bring along a sense of belonging not only to a nation but also to a region, which in turn is expected to promote a spirit of cooperation and amity among nations and HEIs.

² **Erasmus:** *EuRopean Community Action Scheme for the Mobility of University Students* -originally developed as Socrates programme of student mobility- represents a collective effort of governments and HEIs in Europe within the framework of the Bologna Process toward the creation of the European Higher Education Area.

UMAP: *University Mobility in Asia and the Pacific* consists of a voluntary association of government and non-government representatives of the HE sector in the Region to promote mutual understanding of peoples' cultural, economic and social systems through formal academic exchanges of students and staff.

AIMS: *ASEAN International Mobility for Students* programme -originally set by the governments of Malaysia, Indonesia and Thailand under the name of M-I-T- seeks to mobilize students among HEIs in the region, progressively expanding both in number of participating HEIs and countries.

AUN: *ASEAN University Network* represents an effort at the institutional level that integrates a limited number of universities in ASEAN countries.

Campus Asia: *Collective Action for the Mobility Program of University Students in Asia* is a mobility programme that accounts with the support of the governments of China, Japan and South Korea in a limited number of participating HEIs.

Mobility programmes work on the supposition that quality of educational programmes is assured, HEIs trust the excellence of services their partner HEIs offer to the students and this is what allows them to temporarily send their students to take study courses overseas; as a whole, it is also usually believed that these kind of cooperation arrangements, in turn, boost quality assurance systems at the country and the HEIs levels to further develop.

Student mobility programmes function on the same principle since exchanges take place based on the idea that HEIs are autonomous to make their own decisions and set their policies within a cooperative framework of dialogue and openness to others; and where students have the opportunity to participate in academic activities outside their HEIs that represent both a time for learning and a socializing opportunity.

The programmes are typically set to help students develop skills like professional, language and social competences, communication and problem solving, critical sense, cooperative attitudes, working experiences, developing new forms of leadership based on more internationalized careers by means of exposing them to different learning environments.

These programmes also contribute to improve the HEIs work by helping them develop their networking capabilities, increasing chances for cooperation in terms of academic programmes and research; HEIs can also create and discover ways to complement each other and offer broader study choices and programmes to the students by granting access to courses available in partner HEIs.

To achieve the goals those mobility programmes providing different forms of support to both students and HEIs. For example to students: they set schemes with scholarships and other forms of financial support, they also set mechanisms to provide information on courses available out of their HEIs of origin. While for HEIs participating they normally create easy ways of exchange and share information and to harmonize procedures.

In all cases mentioned above mobility happens as horizontal and temporary exchange programmes, although HEIs and mobility programmes can also allow for vertical progression. Typically mobility programmes promote exchanges that last for one or two semesters -or other periods as agreed by the HEIs- on the accord that home institutions will recognize the students' academic work and attainments upon return.

Students' workload and academic attainments are "swapped" differently depending on the arrangements, hence they may work based on a common framework like in Erasmus by using ECTS, or UMAP's exchanges using UCTS; others do it by recognizing credits "as they are" as in the case of AUN's ACTS and yet others like in Campus Asia, HEIs are given complete discretion to manage transfer and recognition matters.

These mobility programmes typically set a number of mutual responsibilities for HEIs participating, which usually include:

For home HEIs: 1) select students and staff to participate of the programmes; 2) assist outgoing students about courses students should take while on exchange (learning agreements); 3) assist outgoing students with travel arrangements; 4) if available, provide information and access to financial support to students; 5) provide preparatory orientations and other forms of tutorials (language and culture) to outgoing students; and 6) recognize students work completed and achievements obtained overseas toward the degrees the students aim to achieve.

For Host HEIs: 1) provide information on the courses they offer to incoming students; 2) grant tuition waivers for incoming students; 3) offer quality assured programmes; 4) assist incoming

students in arrangements for accommodation, formalities like visas and permits; and 5) support incoming students in issues of safety, welfare and healthcare.

Among the most interesting yet difficult aspects of setting mobility programmes for students are the management of academic credits granted from different systems and the recognition of those credits by HEIs granting the final degrees. The most common strategy to address this matter has been the setting of credit transfer schemes associated to those mobility programmes with the aim of systematizing the exchange of information and standardizing procedures to guaranty smooth transfers.

Specifically for the region, in 2011 SEAMEO RIHED proposed a plan to set the Southeast Asian Credit Transfer System (SEA-CTS) based on six principles: 1) the SEA-CTS programme should be developed for transfer of credits in HE; 2) the system should ease the transfer of credits for single courses or groups of courses among similar or equivalent programmes; 3) for courses at bachelor level, only grades equal or above C, or 2.00 score level, or equivalent are transferable, while for courses at graduate level grades equal or above B or 3.00 score level or equivalent, and grade S can be transferred; 4) grades from a course can be transferred when three quarters of a course content is comparable to the course to which the grade is to be transferred; 5) for bachelor degrees, transferable credits shall not exceed two equal parts of the total credits of the programme; and 6) a transferred credit shall or shall not be included in the calculation of the cumulative grade point average (Yavaprabhas, 2010), (SEAMEO RIHED, 2011a).

Within this framework and through the cooperative efforts of ADB and SEAMEO RIHED the *Harmonization and Networking in Higher Education, Building a Common Credit Transfer System for GMS and beyond* project seeks to develop a common platform that compiles best practices and lessons learned from experiences so as to develop a multilateral credit transfer model that is valid for all HEIs in the region (SEAMEO RIHED, 2011b).

1.2. A common credit transfer system for the region

The regional context is characterized by a rapid process of integration, particularly in the form of regional cooperation that is overflowing the economic spheres; increasing social, environmental and cultural aspects are overtaking the central interests of states and peoples in developing business and economic opportunities. More areas of life in modern societies have become interrelated, and not only their demands go far beyond international services and goods, but also they are demanding for more access and better institutionalized channels to transfer information, technology and knowledge.

Regionalization of HE in Asia has been promoted by organizations, like SEAMEO RIHED at the ministerial level or the Association of Southeast Asian Institutions of Higher Learning (ASAIHL), ASEAN University Network (AUN) among others, most of which are work on issues such as quality assurance, collaborative research and development, teaching and learning, student mobility, while they also promote interaction among national education systems, the region and outside Asian (Hawkins, 2012), (De Prado Yepes, 2007).

Regionalization is increasing competitiveness in all realms of life rendering economic systems more exposed and more vulnerable to the influences of external factors. For instance the role of international investments has become a crucial matter over which countries are now more than ever compelled to compete so as to attract and secure the setting of productive ventures in their territories, which closely relates to recent developments of aggressive policies at the educational field in order to produce more and better prepared graduates that can satisfy the

demands from those investments. Former SEAMEO RIHED director summarizes this idea in saying:

“Effective circulation of Human Resources requires “harmonization” of education system; especially in higher education as an engine for social and economic growth.” (Yavaprabhas, 2010)

States increasingly perceiving neighbouring countries and surrounding regions as more than simply neighbours, there is instead a growing tendency in recognizing them as conglomerate of nations, with expanding potentials for cooperation and synergy.

Southeast Asia has been integrating rapidly mainly through trade and investment. The region is also witnessing increasing mobility of people *in the region* and *between regions*. This new context places HE in a pivotal role in developing human resources capable of creating globalized and knowledge-based societies (Damme, 2000).

The setting of the ASEAN Community expected to be launched in 2015 will open the labour markets among the nations of the group to a greater scheme where mobility of human resources will greatly affect both the demand and supply sides of the work force. Asian countries need to be ready to face the challenges this scheme will bring if they expect their populations to stay competitive and integral participants of the economic game of production and consumption. And it is within this context that the international mobility of students together with the recognition of their qualifications gain particular interest.

In the last couple of decades HE has shown important changes in the ways it is conceived, imparted, in the goals it seeks to achieve and scopes it aims to cover; among these changes one very clear trend we have witnessed is the increasing levels of internationalization of its activities and stakeholders. Not only countries and HEIs have become more open to sending and receiving students but now more than ever there is marked active procurement of strategies to promote international mobility of the students.

HE is increasingly becoming a for-profit sector with progressively less ownership on the part of the states, which is leading to an increasing number of institutions and programmes many of them with international articulation, which in turn calls for a deep revision of the mechanisms for mutual recognition of qualifications.

Asia has not been an exception to the trends affecting HE in the world, the region too shows significant changes like: 1) increasing number of students; 2) a rapid growth in private and public providers; 2) a marked increase in the number of cross-border education services; 3) a widening access and use of information and communication technologies by students and institutions; 4) a progressive *massification* as accessibility to HE widens.

Institutions are also now seeing more potentials of growth by promoting new ideas such as lifelong education options; and by boosting the mutual recognition of qualifications obtained from online or long distance study programmes.

Asian countries in the 1990s were leading student exporters for education services, typically directed to The United States, France, Germany and the United Kingdom, with increasing competition from Australia and New Zealand. The major Asian countries sending students to the US were China (72,000), Japan (45,500), South Korea (36,200) and India (31,700); While Malaysia sent 12,000 students to the UK and Hong Kong another 10,000. However these figures have been shifting due to increasing international competition in the provision of education services and the growing engagement from governments investing and supporting

HE, especially as more liberalization of markets is increasingly making clear the connections between education, economic growth and employment (Reinalda, 2011).

The same figures but from the other side show an important unbalance as very few European or North American students choose Asia as a destination for their educations. For instance from the approximately 200,000 Americans that choose to study abroad every year the majority of them do it in the United Kingdom (about 16%), Italy is the second most popular destination (12%), while the remaining three most popular options are Spain, France and Australia.

A similar trend can be observed when looking at Australia, where fewer students leave the country for international experiences in HE, as some 9,000 students leave the country and about 30% of them choose the United States and about 27% opt for New Zealand and following three most popular destinations are the United Kingdom, Canada and Japan. While Australia's proactive policy to attract more students is now spending about US\$1 billion/year to recruit academic talents from within the Asia-Pacific region (Junor & Usher, 2008). All figures that show how Asia as a whole lags behind in terms of incoming students from outside the region.

Two presentations describe mobility and internationalization in Southeast Asia. These are Hirosato's *International/Regional Cooperation among Universities in Asia – Current Status and Future Prospects* and Kamogawa's *Student Mobility Programs towards Asian Regional Networks in Higher Education*. Both of them greatly confirm previous findings and provide convincing information regarding the directions and amounts of students moving around different regions over time, among the aspects presented are the changes in the direction of those moves as a result to the setting of new multilateral mobility programmes in Asia such as UMAP, M-I-T/AIMS, Doctoral Degree Sandwich Program AUN/SEEDNet, S3 Asia MBA and Campus Asia (Hirosato, 2012), (Kamogawa, 2012).

This means that the number of mobile students and researchers has grown at exponential rates, while at the same time the direction of those flows and the rationales behind them have changed as well. Rumbley, Albatch and Reiserg for example; in *Internationalization Within The Higher Education Context* cited the OECD (2009) in recalling that the organization had estimated that in 2008 there were some 3.3 million internationally mobile students around the world; while the organization speculated that this number could grow to at least 5.8 million by 2020." (Rumbley, Altbach, & Reisberg, 2012).

In a related article Bhandari and Blumenthal cited a 2009 UNESCO report asserting that parallel to the growing number of mobile students there is a global tendency in the growing levels of enrolment; according to these authors students enrolment grew from 68 million students in 1991 to 125 million students in 2007; with countries in Asia and the Pacific showing the greatest rates of growth; and where many of those students seek to obtain degrees out of their home counties implying important flows of people and resources, for example they estimate that while China is becoming number one students' exporter and a major destination for foreign students; some 450,000 Indian students migrate overseas and spend US\$13 billion each year to get some form of HE (Bhandari & Blumenthal, 2011).

However and contrasting those figures the World Bank's report *Putting Higher Education to work Skills and Research for Growth in East Asia* argues that although Asia is developing rapidly, regional standards of HE in the region still lag behind the rest of the world mainly due to five *disconnects* that relate to: 1) the gap between HE and the skill needs of employers; 2) a weak research and technology linkage between HEIs and private companies; 3) a separation

between teaching and researching institutions; 4) a disconnect among institutions themselves and between these institutions and other training providers; and lastly 5) a separation between and earlier education institutions (The World Bank, 2009).

Specifically in internationalization of HE and student mobility, although some multilateral credit transfer systems are in place in the East and Southeast region the amount of students moving *within* the region remains comparatively small to those choosing destinations in other continents or moving within the framework of bilateral agreements. This relates to factors like:

1. Attractiveness of other destinations and programmes
2. Prestige of the institutions and HE systems outside the region
3. Most mobility of students is canalized through bilateral agreements or Memorandums of Understanding between institutions rather than on multilateral arrangements; which constitutes an enormous duplication of work (in terms of setting those agreements) that however function *better* as mutual trust is possible through direct contact among partners.
4. Existing multilateral systems in the region maybe *too general and all too inclusive*, while others appear to be too narrow as they include limited number of universities leaving the bulk of students and institutions out of opportunities within those systems to allow for transfer of students' workload.
5. There has been a rapid expansion in the number of HEIs in the region, both public and private ones, with different names, goals, degrees and programmes, which renders the HE landscape more complex and fluid.
6. Although there is an increasing demand from the students for more international programmes, and in parallel an increasing offer in the region of programmes in foreign languages, especially in English, there seems to remain an important gap in terms of access to those programmes and the language skills required.

In order to address some of these challenges main stakeholders in the sector are promoting the mobility of students at the university level as they believe this strategy will increase mutual understanding among cultures, cooperation among nations, business opportunities, and friendship among the peoples of the region.

In the long run the exchange of students can bring the above mentioned *disconnects* together and greatly contribute to the deepening of historical linkages, the development of new areas of common interests, the enhancement of intraregional commerce of goods and services, the implementation of joint policies to address common challenges such as the protection of human rights and the environment, the fight against trafficking in goods and people and organized transnational crime and so forth.

In order to facilitate student mobility, the region's diverse HE systems need more harmonized standards and mechanisms for permeable and transparent quality assurance and credit transfer among institutions. Encouraging and supporting students to study abroad is a major strategy to develop a well-trained international workforce, which can improve the quality and quantity of human resources in the economy as well as the national education sector.

More specifically within this context it is worth considering that at the HE level, student mobility and multilateral credit transfer systems promote advancements in curricula developments, updating of programmes, comparability of syllabi and learning outcomes. Well institutionalized credit transfer systems promote student-centred study programmes and in

so doing they can enhance effectiveness in the learning process and in creating bridges between those gaps.

Multilateral credit transfer systems are known to promote the mobility of the students (Junor & Usher, 2008), but they also increase the exposure of universities and other HEIs to currents of change in terms of contents, teaching methods and technologies. As a whole this exchange process, understood as the search for more academic transparency, favours the institutional learning process through the exchange and access to more and newer information.

Multilateral credit systems are generally recognized mechanisms that help democratize HE as they create rules where students become the centre of their educational choices and the drivers of their own careers, while at the same time credit transfer systems contribute to the expansion in the access to HE of more people (*massification*) and in alternative forms of education (beyond the traditional formal settings).

1.3. Credit transfer systems: what they do

Credit transfer systems are constructed on a central assumption related to the concepts of *accreditation* and *recognition*. Both terms have a dual nature as they are understood as a *status* (i.e. HEIs *being accredited* and *being recognized*) and as a *function* (i.e. *HEIs grant academic credits* and *HEIs recognize those credits when granted by others*).

In the first case –status-, *accreditation* of the HEI is an official procedure that requires formal steps; for HEIs to be *accredited* they undergo a process of quality assurance through which normally public agencies set and evaluate minimum quality standards HEIs must meet so as to be able to grant degrees to the students. While *recognition* relates to a less formal process based on how HEIs perceive each other and how much credibility they offer each other regarding the quality of the education they provide in their programmes.

In the second case –function-; *accreditation* relates to HEIs capacities to award academic qualifications (in the form of credits) to students that successfully complete a given study course toward a degree; while *recognition* here relates to the will or capacity of a HEI in relation to another to accept the credits/qualifications granted to a student by a different HEI as valid and relevant toward a degree it will eventually award to the student.

From here it follows (and this is the underlying assumption) that for credits to be transferred and recognized (in the functional sense of the word) HEIs –especially the ones *accepting* the credits- must at least implicitly recognize the HEIs granting those credits (in the status sense of the word) in terms of quality of education provided and relevance of those qualifications toward the degree expected by the student.

Consequently, it is logic to expect that if a HEI does not recognize another (in the status sense of the word) it is unlikely to either send its own students as participants of temporary exchange programmes to the second HEI, or to accept the credits students may have acquired there as transfer toward a degree it will eventually grant. In other words, recognition of credits is more likely to happen when HEIs recognize other HEIs as quality assured (which typically implies the idea that both HEIs will be officially accredited).

With this framework in mind, we can now approach topic of credit transfer systems starting from the rationale behind them; which consists of attaching a given value to the efforts the students are required to do in order to achieve certain amount of knowledge, skills or other forms of learning outcomes from a course or study programme.

Basically credit systems quantify the students' workload into scales or set of points that help making the content and the learning process and outcomes more transparent in terms of contents and work required, more understandable for people in different contexts and easier to compare to other courses within or outside the institution providing the courses.

By attaching credits or points to the subjects and courses HEIs are saying "this student that passed this subject studied/worked this many hours and obtained these many points for that effort, all of which should help describe and judge the knowledge and skills s/he has acquired through the process".

Another way to see it is as if credits were "a form of knowledge currency" where the recognition of the value of those credits can be understood as in the "exchange rate" different institutions give to them in order to decide whether they are acceptable or not (Junor & Usher, 2008).

Traditional credit systems focus on HEIs in an *inward looking* attitude (these many credits represent what the student did and what s/he knows according to the standards set by *this* institution); however credit systems gain more functional value when they are applied in the context of two or more institutions exchanging information and working together in terms of imparting programmes (that may be similar or not) and by recognizing each other's work and value.

Credit systems are meant to facilitate the attainment of four main purposes: 1) promoting life-long learning; 2) widening participation and allowing access to education to more people; 3) reduce failure and non-completion rates; and 4) allow for more mobility of people within and outside the academic realm (Bekhradnia, 2004).

HE systems based on credits are meant to bring flexibility to academic structures according to the interrelated notions of *credit* and *modularity*, because together they expand access to education and make more rational use of resources. The introduction of these systems is usually related to clearer understandings of the learning processes and structures themselves; while they are also expected to promote academic partnerships. However these systems may also bring new risks that deserve serious consideration, for instance among the dangers these systems bring is the fact that students may simply accumulate credits rather than integrating the learning experiences they have across modules (Allen & Geoff, 1995), (Morrison, Cowan, & Harte, 1997).

Credit systems acquire their full potential when they are used as *transfer systems*, meaning that they help HEIs mutually understand and interpret their work by allowing and facilitating the transfer process and the recognition of qualifications those institutions have granted to students that successfully passed one or multiple courses.

Bergan, Divis and Rauhvargers compare accreditation and recognition to a bridge, whose goal is "to allow persons to cross the divide between various education systems without losing their 'luggage' (i.e. the value of their qualifications) on the way through unreasonable 'customs tariffs' (i.e. recognition requirements)." (Bergan, Divis, & Rauhvargers, 2000).

From this it follows that credit transfer systems work differently depending the institutions participating in the scheme and the direction in which the flows of information move – meaning that credit transfer systems can be unilateral, bilateral or multilateral-.

It is within the context of increasing mobility of goods, services and people set by globalization and regional integration that multilateral credit transfer systems become a key element not

only for the advancement and transfer of knowledge but also for the increasing need to create bridges that connect those peoples and the productive systems in the economies they will work by means of better connecting HE systems.

1.4. Credit systems in the region

The reason behind the variety of credit systems in the world relates to the fact that each system is set to address the needs and expectations of those who create them. National HE systems and HEIs have different goals, function in different ways and move at different paces; hence when they seek to create mechanisms that facilitate the communication among them they set credit transfer systems that *adjust* to their needs and possibilities.

Creating credit transfer systems relates to many factors that include for example the members of the scheme; geographical vicinity, cultural and traditional closeness, institutional prestige, access to educational resources and wealth, etc.

It is practically impossible to assert at once how many systems exist. This is because they change over time in the goals they seek to achieve, the scopes and procedures; new systems are created while others fall out of use and simply die off as mere formal letters that never actually make it to transfer credits since institutions never actually *own* them and *use* them.

In the last few decades credit transfer systems have been set in all five continents however they present significant differences in terms of goals, levels of implementation, scopes, members and commitments. As such they represent a complex research universe.

There are credit transfer systems that deserve more attention, like those that hold together and that are being used; if we focus on *multilateral* systems only, the number of case drops drastically since the great majority of credit transfers actually take place within the framework of bilateral agreements between individual HEIs.

Among multilateral systems the most recognized example is ECTS (European Credit Transfer System) that was set through the Bologna Process to facilitate transfer of credits of students among HEIs in Europe; and that has become –regardless of its actual effectiveness- a clear (dominant?) paradigm at the world level in terms of design and procedures.

In East and Southeast Asia most prominent examples of multilateral credit systems are UCTS (UMAP’s Credit Transfer System), ACTS (ASEAN’s Credit Transfer System) and the credit system used in the Campus Asia programme. These three systems represent perhaps the complexity of the topic in the region as they illustrate particularly clear differences in their goals, scopes, members, and above all in the way they function. (Nguyen, 2009)

Although asking “how many credit transfer systems exist?” is a tempting research idea, the efforts required to answer to that question may be vain for they constantly change, instead a more fruitful interrogation would be “what do we need to know about the credit transfer systems to make them more effective?”. And *that* is what this report aims to respond to.

1.5. Challenges of setting a credit transfer system for the region (Problem statement)

Regardless of how desirable the idea of setting a common transfer system that is comprehensive and inclusive for all countries of the region might be as it is happening in Europe in the context of the Bologna Process, especially given the rapid integration process Southeast and East Asia are going through; the recognition of academic qualifications remains

a thorny issue that will require important efforts from all interested parties for it to actually happen.

It is clear that difficulties about recognition and transfer of academic credits for mobile students is a major obstacle to mobility; however even if transferability may not be the biggest hurdle, the issue remains complex due to the large number of stakeholders whose engagement is needed to reach an affective and fair solution (Junor & Usher, 2008).

The above does not mean that creating a regional credit transfer system is a futile endeavour but instead that there are important challenges to overcome in relation to the facilitation of the transfer of academic credits among HEIs in the region. Both objective and subjective obstacles need to be addressed and progressively removed for the effort to flourish; and this will require an awareness rising effort to create more open minded and flexible attitudes towards diversity and otherness.

Among the main factors that still hinder the creation of mechanisms that facilitate the mobility of students; the transferability of their workload of and the recognition of their qualifications we can observe for example:

a. There are deep differences in HE systems within and among the countries of the region. Some of which are legal or structural distinctions, while others relate to cultural and political factors –understood, for instance, in the sense of institutional values, history, prestige, etc.-.

b. There continue to exist attitudes that reject openness and change in the HE realm mainly based on “traditional comfort” (institutions and the people therein do not appreciate working with the unknown) that sets major obstacles in the way to facilitate the mobility of students across institutions and national borders.

c. Lack of trust among institutions and countries represents an important obstacle in the construction of mechanisms to that can help facilitate student mobility and recognition of qualifications.

d. Issues of quality assurance remain a major challenge to the increase of mobility of students among HEIs in the region. The lack of effective and internationally comparable mechanisms in this regard greatly undermines mutual trust.

f. Negative attitudes towards mobility can also be seen among students that prefer to stay in their home universities; a factor that mostly relates to the lack of awareness on the learning process typically resulting from going to exchanges and also very importantly due to the fact that in many cases students perceive exchange programmes (at least for the case of temporary exchanges) as a waste of time and money because they think their home universities will not recognize the work they do while on abroad. (Junor & Usher, 2008)

g. Financial constraints, specially but not only, among less developed countries and less endowed HEIs hinder mobility of students and the chances of setting frameworks that can allow for new and more efficient channels of communication among major stakeholders.

h. Many stakeholders perceive the process of regional integration and globalization as a major threat to their traditions and values, for example as many of them fear *homonisation* of education and cultures.

1.6. Goals of the project

The project *Harmonization and Networking in Higher Education. Building a Common Credit Transfer System for GMS and beyond* seeks lay foundations upon which HE systems in the region can better coordinate their efforts towards the production of human resources that can respond to the new demands set by increasingly fluid labour markets.

The project promotes the creation of scenarios for dialogue and understanding based on the assumption that increased exchanges and interactions help develop new and stronger personal and institutional linkages that in turn create fertile soils for more synergies.

By focusing its thematic scope on the transfer of academic credit systems at the multilateral level, the project seeks to build bridges among educational systems and HEIs in order to make programmes and courses more transparent and understandable so as to facilitate student mobility particularly at the international level.

Although initially focusing more on promoting horizontal mobility of students (as temporary exchanges among HEIs and countries); in the longer run it is expected that the creation of a multilateral credit transfer scheme for the region will increase vertical mobility (lifelong learning) as accumulation of credits facilitates recognition of previous qualifications and the advancement to higher levels of specialization.

By increasing interaction throughout the exchange of students the project seeks to generate a more democratic scenario where students become the centre of their academic choices and the direction of their careers hence increasing the chances for better matching their skills with the demands of the employers.

The objectives set for the initial phase of the project –*Explore*– in this report is to *condense* lessons learned from existing multilateral credit transfer systems to better understand how credit transfer can be used more effective and extensively so as to reach more students; and how to better articulate already existing credit transfer systems in the region.

One of the goals of the study is to analyse multilateral credit transfer systems to depict the logics upon which they work to address the needs of the HEIs using them, to capitalize lessons learnt and to better articulate them.

This is done through two parallel comparisons: one considering major credit transfer systems in the world (with focus in Asia) to see how they function; and the other analyzing the situation of academic credit management in the countries included at this point of the project; and from the conjunction of both will lay the foundation from where to propose a model valid for the region as a whole.

This report seeks to respond to the need of thinking of a common platform for credit transfer based on the consensus of all major stakeholders, namely governments, HEIs and students at a “graspable geographical area” like the Great Mekong Subregion; that can be expanded progressively to include all of East and Southeast Asia.

1.7. Brief description of the methodology

The whole project composes four phases: *Explore*, *Experiment*, *Experience* and *Expand*, it has been conceived as *an action research project* that first describes and compares multilateral credit systems at the global level but with focus in Asia and then at the country level among ten countries including the six countries in the Great Mekong Subregion (Cambodia, China, Lao PDR, Myanmar, Thailand and Vietnam), plus Indonesia and Malaysia among other Southeast Asian countries, together with Japan and Republic of Korea in East Asia.

The first phase of the project –*Explore*– consists of basically a double comparison: one portraying multilateral credit transfer systems being used worldwide, and two contrasting the particular situation of the ten countries regarding credit transfer systems being used in each of them and the position of the main stakeholders concerning both effectiveness of those systems and opportunities for more international integration. The outcomes from these comparisons constitute the theoretical platform from where the project will move into the next phases in order to propose strategies to further develop mechanisms for the mobility of students by using multilateral credit transfer systems.

Explore consisted of three parts that took place simultaneously. Research was carried out as *Part one: Credit transfer systems in perspective* compared major multilateral credit transfer systems to spot main features of those models. *Part two: Credit transfer systems in and for Great Mekong Subregion* and *Part three: Credit transfer systems in non-Great Mekong Subregion* analysed models on a country base and included government-to-government and university-to-university agreements. The only difference between these two parts was the way in which data was gathered (fieldwork to GMS countries and data gathered locally by national resource persons and shared in an International workshop for non-GMS countries).

Findings were presented in an international workshop in Bangkok in November 2012, which included presentations from all resource persons for the country descriptions and from SEAMEO RIHED for comparisons of systems, a regional overview and the way forward.

Details and further explanation on the methodology used for the collection of data, the selection of sources (units of analysis), the construction of the sample, research instruments, and the explanation of the analysis of data are included in chapter 3 of the report: *SEAMEO RIHED ADB CTS Report 3. Methodology of the project*.

1.8. Structure of the report

Chapter 2: *Literature review* presents a general scrutiny of existing research regarding student mobility and focusing on credit transfer systems as facilitators of that mobility. The review analyzes global trends but with focus on the experiences taking place in East and Southeast Asia.

Chapter 3: *Methodology* presents the research design for phase 1 –*Explore*– within the context of the project as a whole. It describes how the comparisons of multilateral credit transfer systems and of academic credit situations at the country level were done.

Chapter 4: *Review and comparison of main credit transfer systems* presents the findings from the comparison of 20 multilateral credit systems. This provides insights in terms of logics and procedures of how different systems deal with the transfer of credits and the sharing of information among participants. The chapter provides a qualitative assessment in terms of how those systems are responding to the needs of HEIs and students in facilitating international mobility of students.

Chapter 5: *Findings from comparative country level research [based on country reports]* provides an analysis of the situation of credit systems and the opportunities for credits transfer at the national level in the ten countries included in this phase. The chapter is structured to: 1) describe commonalities and differences among the countries and basically contain the synthesis of the country reports presented by the resource persons on credit systems for each country; 2) portray the perspectives main stakeholders have regarding use

of credit systems at the national level; 3) present credit transfer situations as perceived by governments, HEIs and students.

Chapter 6: *Integration of findings toward a common regional CTS* combines findings from the previous chapters focusing on the common areas that serve as a platform from where to construct a regional scheme for credit transfer and recognition.

Chapter 8: *The model proposed* presents the technical aspects upon which the regional credit transfer system should work based on the agreement and acceptance of HEIs in the region.

Chapter 8: *Recommendations* includes a number of suggestions and proposals for future actions to continue promoting the development of mechanisms to further promote student mobility and harmonization of the HE landscape to main stakeholders (government, HEIs and students). The chapter captures and condenses the conclusions from discussions carried out by the participants to the two international workshops on credit transfer organized by SEAMEO RIHED during 2012, where not only resource persons but also general audience put forward their ideas and suggestions on how credit transfer schemes should be like.

Chapter 9: *The way forward to the project* briefly explains how SEAMEO RIHED envisions the next phases to the project, meaning concrete actions to further facilitate the setting of a framework that allows for practical and fair transfer of academic credits among HEIs in the region.

Chapter 10: *Glossary and acronyms* presents a list of terms and acronyms used throughout the report.

Lastly chapter 11: *Annexes* contains the original data used for the research, namely: Multilateral CTS individual charts; Multilateral CTS comparative chart; and Country reports.

2. Literature review: student mobility and credit transfer

Rationalization of HE follows regional integration and the setting up of cooperative agreements with similar geographic and cultural connections. The phenomenon has brought economic political and social systems more into line and educational systems contained therein, as well as their structures, goals and methods are not exception to this.

Integration of HE in Europe represents the starting point of this research for the Bologna Process constitutes the first *rational, systematic, multilateral and international initiative* ever taken to create an integrated educational area with agreed goals and procedures where HE and international labour market meet. According to Knight, for example, the rationalization of students' mobility became more evident since the beginning of the 80's when internationalization in HE started to boom as a result of the interaction of global forces; with Europe as the leading integration effort (Knight, 2012).

To approach student mobility and the use of credit transfer the review focused on thematic areas that give a consistent direction to the whole project; where the unifying thread is the use of academic credits as a unit for measurement of students' workload and as mechanism to facilitate comparability and dialogue among educational systems and institutions.

2.1. International student mobility

To put in context the matter of international mobility of students a number of articles and books were revised to frame trends and challenges arising in the sector due to the impacts of globalization and regional integration. Topics that evidence changes in the HE relate to: 1) increasing numbers of mobile students and destinations; 2) growth of cross-border educational provision, 3) institutions' push for world class status; 4) interest of governments in producing globally competent graduates; 5) prevalence of English as language of instruction; 6) level and kind of networking among institutions; 7) competition in attractiveness and prestige; and 8) commercialization and privatization.

Part of the literature is devoted to the concepts of *brain-drain* and *brain-train*, which closely relate to the goals of the project; for example Knight devotes a good part of her report to analyse the competition of developed countries to attract talents, while students seek to develop careers across institutions and countries (Knight, 2012). In this sense for instance Salmi analyzes how competition among universities and groups of universities materialize in a much more complex yet intertwined landscape of "corporate universities" (Salmi, 2001).

Banks and Bhandari provide an overview of mobility as they describe causes of mobility in terms of economic opportunities, political security, cross border trade, migration, tourism, study and research. These authors identify delivery of international education as: 1) direct exchange programmes; 2) distance education or online education; 3) supported distance education or programme articulation; 4) franchising; and 5) offshore campus or foreign branch campuses. They offer concrete data comparing sending and receiving countries and the reasons behind those flows (Banks & Bhandari, 2012).

In her book *Higher Education in Turmoil*, Knight looks at the strategies that bring about effective responses to make educational systems more inclusive, democratic and effective. She analyses *motives behind internationalization* in four areas: 1) *socio/cultural motives* - development of identities, cultural understanding and citizenship-; 2) *political motives* -states' foreign policies, national security, technical assistance, promotion of peace and regional integration-; 3) *economic motives* -economic growth, integration of markets and

competitiveness-; and 4) *academic motives* -extension of academic horizons, institution building, visibility of HE, quality in education at international standards and connections between teaching, learning and researching- (Knight, 2008).

An observation from the review is the confirmation of Gaston's hypothesis on the fact that the *language utilized in the world of higher education is evolving and is coming to closer understanding of concepts*. Although important gaps remain there is growing agreement among academicians and practitioners in calling things by increasingly similar names; which implies at least two things: 1) a rapid increase in the interactions among institutions and people; and 2) a growing will to further deepen and strengthen those connexions through the "*use of language that is more similar, more understandable*" (Gaston, 2010).

An important conclusion to be made from this is that interactions among HE systems and institutions have increased rapid and widely as the result from rational plans seeking to internationalize HE, which lead us to our next topic in the review.

2.1.1. Strategies toward regionalization of HE

Multilateral credit systems facilitate student mobility and a number of research pieces provided enriching insights on how this happens. Among the most outstanding pieces it is worth recalling Woodfield's work that identifies *kinds* of student mobility as 1) physical mobility or education-only mobility; 2) short or long term mobility; and 3) permanent or temporary mobility. Typically associated to *horizontal* moves as opposed to *vertical* mobility that relates to accumulation of qualifications of different levels. Other forms of mobility are associated to diploma mobility or credit mobility. Other forms of transnational education happen as virtual mobility, typically done on offshore kind of cross-border supply and commercial presence of foreign providers in satellite campuses (Woodfield, 2012).

In the same line Knight provides a typology that rationalizes the complexity of mobility in four groups: 1) The first category of *mobile students* are people moving for different spans of time for full or partial degrees, research, internships, consulting; etc. 2) The second category is for *programmes* (courses, programmes and degrees) that materialize as twinning, franchised services, articulated qualifications, joint or double degrees and online or distance programmes, etc; 3) next group *providers* (HEIs) extend their international reach by setting branch campuses, virtual universities, through merging and acquisition processes and the development of independent institutions; 4) at project level (academic or service kind) materialize through research, development of curricula, capacity building and the provision / expansion of educational services (Knight 2008).

The increasing correlation of systems and institutions responds to cooperative and competitive relations among them. Vincent-Lancrin describes the strategies HEIs use to attract students into their campuses and to internationalize their programmes; then he classifies those policies into: 1) strategies based on mutual understanding of the institutions; 2) strategies based on excellence and the competition for talents; 3) strategies based on revenue generation; and 4) strategies based on capacity development. (Vincent-Lancrin, 2009). In the same line Sakamoto and Chapman analyse the schemes through which institutions collaborate *in* and *outside* their countries, the strategies used to build *bridges and trust* among them by setting cross-border programmes at faculty level, to carry joint research and other initiatives to develop quality assurance, improve technology and information sharing, as well as widening the provision of non-academic services. They analysed cross-border partnerships at four levels: organizational; financial, individual (faculty) and context

for collaborative ventures; and it is within the organization and individual (faculty) levels that they provide the most enriching insights for the study of multilateral credit transfer systems (Sakamoto & Chapman, 2011).

These authors agree in that cross-border education is a multi-billion dollar industry due to privatization and now mass-oriented; which calls for systematic harmonization of education; and that regional integration impinges internationalization due to linkages in the productive systems and national economies. All of which, leads us to the justifications of this research, i.e. the need to better colligate HE to increasingly internationalized labour markets.

Tillman put forward the need to integrate student mobility programmes to the global workforce markets by portraying changes in traditional paradigms on how institutions prepare graduates through the accreditation of domestic and international internships. His findings show that increasing number of schools demand internship periods as compulsory for their careers to better articulate academic learning and work experience. However this brings along difficulties on how to gauge learning outcomes and certify the quality of learning (Tillman, 2012).

In a related piece, Spöttl and Becker argue the idea of academic accreditation of vocational education and training by analyzing procedures for transfer of occupational qualifications. They describe how institutions deal with the recognition of learning processes of the students, and how to build inter-institutional trust by focusing on 1) similarities of programmes; 2) overlapping areas leading to transferability; and 3) areas with significant differences to be negotiated. They propose a model and categorization of activities towards a solution based on a “set of zones of mutual trust” (Spöttl & Becker, 2005). While Rauhvargers makes an enriching contribution to the argument above by defining the concepts of academic and professional recognitions and accreditations, and their legal and practical implications (Rauhvargers, 2004).

Central to the understanding and applicability of these concepts and strategies are the ideas presented by Betts and Smith in *Developing the Credit-based Modular Curriculum in Higher Education*. These authors provide a guide for curricular reform that was of particular interest for our research as they set outlines on the process and the nature of the reforms needed in HEIs at the time of setting a modular curriculum, which relates to multilateral mechanisms to transfer students’ workload; as modularization facilitates the breaking into pieces of study programmes They argue that *knowledge* and *learning* are not be necessarily connected, which represents a challenge to institutions and governments as they now need to make the two concepts *compatible* and *feasible*. Institutions have become providers of *learning* rather than providers of *subjects or disciplines*, which sets far reaching tests to those managing the HE institutions. (Betts & Smith, 1998).

They present the fragmentation and further integration of HE through modularization as the main strategy to address more complex scenarios as well as the increasing demands from students and societies. This model presents opportunities for more flexibility while challenges will remain in terms of accountability in terms of quality of education and assurance mechanisms.

The differences between *knowledge* and *learning* represent a central aspect of the research carried out by SEAMEO RIHED, as it relates to the goals of ASEAN Social Cultural Community (ASCC) on building a human centred community, and to the goals of the Great Mekong Subregion Human Resources Development Framework and Action Plan to promote quality assurance and credit transfer schemes for the region.

It is before this complex scenario that the role of credit systems and mechanisms to transfer those credits become central as tools to *lubricate* the moves by creating standard study programmes, learning outcomes and grading values. However before focusing in the analysis of our geographic area of interest (East and Southeast Asia) let us first briefly see recent developments in the European context as the main antecedent in this regard.

2.2. Regional student mobility

2.2.1. Europe and the milestone of the Bologna Process

Harmonization of HE at the multilateral level and the use of academic credits as a tool is approached by looking at the process of integration in Europe as it represents the first systematic effort to bring into line a diverse number of high education systems.

The setting of credit systems bring far-reaching changes by moving from teaching-centred to learning-centred process –a process related to the democratization of education-. The Bologna Declaration and the process that followed have much to do with this change of paradigm especially as its mentors have focused on learning outcomes rather than teaching inputs. Another important change in the paradigm has been the idea of a diploma supplement to help people understand what students did during their learning experiences.

Among the goals of the Bologna process is the promotion of wide recognition of qualifications through policy reforms and the promotion of students' mobility, within this context the Lisbon Convention of 1997 set a landmark as it calls for the recognition of entry requirements, study periods, and degrees. A central mechanism for the implementation of the process has been the ERASMUS programme to ensure that achievements abroad are recognized by home institutions. Among many others, and only as example of the broad existing literature Huisman and others analyse the progressive course of voluntary integration happening as a parallel phenomenon: where harmonization and mobility have been systematically promoted particularly through the use of ECTS; while there has been an evident growth in the similarities of practises in other regions so as to increase and support harmonization (Huisman, Adelman, Hiseh, Shams, & Wilkins, 2012).

In this sense, for instance Junor and Usher argue that the Erasmus project accounts each year with a budget of €190 million that are used to support approximately 140,000 mobile students within European institutions; which is supported by a proactive promotion of the procedures set in the Lisbon Convention, particularly in regards to use of credits and a common method of measurement and transfer (Junor & Usher, 2008).

Concretely speaking, these refers to the promotion of reforms to set common three cycle degree structure (bachelor, master, and doctorate), national qualification frameworks, mechanisms for quality assurance, agreements of recognition of qualifications, credits and prior learning, the advancement in the idea of mobility of students, researchers, teachers and staff. In most cases this has also been related to the goals of giving regional integration a social dimension based on overlapping interest in education.

Witte, Huisman and Purser describe the Process and its connections to inner political interests of the European Union and the progressive implementation of the system based on governmental and institutional agreements. They describe the mechanisms used to share information through the use of *diploma supplements* and *institutional communications* to implement the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS) as an agreed process for multilateral

recognition of qualifications (Witte, Huisman, & Purser, 2009), (European Commission, Council of Europe, & UNESCO/CEPES, n.d.).

Related to the above and central for SEAMEO RIHED's research has been Gaston's work on how credit systems ease the creation of knowledge by making students the owners of their learning and by allowing them to link societies' needs and what they learn. Another aspect put forward is that the use of credits fosters innovation and creativity among teachers and students as they see what is useful for their societies within their own contexts. This author explains and compares how Bologna boosted integration and mobility of students in Europe as opposed to the United States, he concludes that the setting of common goals based on dialogue, the use of ECTS and the diploma supplement have over passed transfer systems in the American scheme as the European system has become more consistent in its goals and processes, in the mechanisms used by focusing more on learning outcomes rather than focusing on the time students spend on learning content or developing skills. (Gaston, 2010)

Among those critical to the process and outcomes from Bologna and especially its ECTS a number of researchers discuss the relevance, pertinence and the limitations the current statistical distribution of the ECTS grades have. Some authors have analyzed the historical path of the process, connected to the federalization of Europe and to its agendas (political, economic and cultural) where some even see it as a sociologically naïve and intellectually irresponsible endeavour (Tomusk, 2004). Also from the side of the critiques other authors assert that an European credit system brings in an *Americanization of European education*, implying disturbances for traditions and cultural customs in the region (Steiner, 1996).

With more optimistic views other authors propose strategies to overcome technical disparities for example through optional ways to calculate the ECTS grades attribution (Grosgees & Barchiesi, 2007), (Sullivan, 2002). While others are proposing creative ways to measure and share information on credits awarded to students taking part in long distance and virtual education (Kargidis, Kefalas, Stamat, & Tsadiras, 2003), (ECA, European Consortium for Accreditation in higher Education, 2007). And lastly an interesting area of interest relates to improvements in communications towards better informed and more transparent decisions on recognition of qualifications (Adam, 2001).

Harmonization in Europe has laid down the foundations to new efforts in the same way in different areas of the world basically because of the fact that the mechanisms used there have been embraced by the stakeholders involved. It is the combination of elements within the scheme such as the democratic and voluntary elements of the process that allow the system to accommodate to the needs of the stakeholders and not the other way around.

Transferability of academic credits in Latin America presents an interesting example of *alignment* with the integration process in Europe, as opposed to creating a newly integrated HE system of its own; countries in the region have opted to work among themselves and with European partners through a more direct-dialogue based strategy aiming to set a common space with Europe. (Yavaprabhas, 2009)

Related to regionalization in Europe countries in other areas of the world have too working on setting their own systems to integrate HE, African countries for example are working on to harmonize their systems following developments of the Bologna Process, which relates to the historical linkages that colligate the study systems there. Initiatives like The Southern Africa Development Community (SADC) aiming to create the African Higher Education Area (AHEA) through curricular to address national and regional priorities of the labour markets through more balanced academic mobility and with harmonization of legal frameworks serve as

example of this; even if the notion of transfer of academic credits appears still too premature and directly aligned to the European system. (Nguyen, 2009), (Chien, Kot, & Mpinganjira, 2011), (African Union, 2007), (Woldetensae, 2011)

Another example is the East African Community (EAC) in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania, that set an arrangement for credit transfer and accumulation at the government level in 2006, which is promoted by the Inter-University Council for East Africa (IUCEA) with the direct support from the East African Legislative Assembly (EALA). The initiative is also promoting the creation of a quality assurance mechanism related to accreditation and transfer systems at national level, as well as the setting of a regional qualification framework to facilitate mutual recognition of qualifications among EAC countries to ease the movement of human capital in the region. (The Inter-University Council for East Africa, n.d.), (Oyewole, n.d.)

2.2.2. Harmonizing HE in Asia

Efforts towards regionalization of education in Asia became more active with the setting of The International Network of Quality Assurance Agencies in Higher Education, established in 1991. Another important landmark was 1995 when ASEAN member states set the ASEAN University Network (AUN) to reinforce cooperation among universities in the region. Like these, other efforts by institutions like the South East Asian Ministers of Education Organization (SEAMEO) in different fields, the APEC Education Centres of the Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) and University Mobility in Asia and the Pacific (UMAP) have made important contributions through mechanisms like quality assurance, trans-border cooperation, student exchanges and the setting of different credit transfer schemes (Reinalda, 2011), (Umemiya, 2008).

The starting point for the review for Asia was the report produced by Waseda University after the first international Symposium *Formulating and International Higher Education Framework for Regional Cooperation and Integration in Asia*; where in its presentation on *Experiences of Asian Higher Education Frameworks and their Implications for the Future*, the then Director of SEAMEO RIHED presented an overview of the challenges HE faces in the region, which includes the setting of quality assurances mechanisms, the need to create a scheme for the transfer of credits among countries and institutions and a system of comparable and readable degrees in the region (Yavaprabhas, 2009).

In a related article named *"Shared Space" in Global Higher Education*, Sirat analyses the prospects of a Common Area of Education for the Southeast Asia region as proposed by SEAMEO RIHED, which tends to bring together educational systems within a broad geopolitical context built upon the construction and consolidation of networks based on the analyses of circuits of exchange and their impact (Sirat, 2012).

Most representative research pieces and books on strategies and challenges towards regionalization include Kell and Vogl in *International Students in the Asia Pacific* that provides an overview of future prospects in the region by analysing current trends and strategies leading to HEIs to be efficiently managed, with an eye into capturing larger amounts of students and researchers and seeking to boost the quality of learning and teaching. They offer data on amounts and directions of flows of students in the world and conclude that Asia is the region developing the fastest (at least quantitatively) which closely relates to the increasing private wealth and the search for international education of newer generations. They argue that there are different *ethoses* motivating the flows, among richer countries like Japan, China, Hong Kong, and Singapore, where the moves are typically self-financed by the

students' families and typically to destinations outside the region; while on the other side less developed countries tend to send students outside the region but with a larger amount of intraregional percentage and higher percentages of those flows financed by development agencies or bilateral cooperation schemes (Kell & Volg, 2012).

These facts put forward two aspects about HE in the region: 1) most students and families show more interest in studying in HEIs and in countries outside Asia; and 2) important amounts of financial and human resources -from both developed and less developed countries- continue to contribute more to richer countries and more prestigious universities, which means that an important drift of wealth in terms of financial and human resources.

In the same context they analyze the setting of education Hubs in the Asia (Hong Kong, Singapore and Malaysia) as tactic approaches to making their systems more attractive. Lastly they analyze a recent trend they call "*Asianisation of Mobility*" where they synthesize the initiatives countries in Asia implement to boost intra-regional mobility.

In a related area Neubauer in *Giving Dimension and Direction to Mobility and Migration in Asian Pacific Higher Education* analyses how markets have affected the mobility and equity in HE in the region leading to new national and regional transformations that bring both matches and mismatches for students and the labour market (Neubauer, 2012).

In a more focused approach Altbach describes how China and India are becoming the *new heavy weights* of HE; for the time being as the main exporters of students but both increasingly becoming aware for the potentials and needs to foster quality in education and research within their own countries in order to retain more students at home and to promote incoming flows of fresh foreign students and educational investments into their domestic institutions and countries (Altbach, 2009).

It is worth then considering how governments and institutions are preparing themselves to address the issue of mobility and more specifically how they are adjusting and reforming their credit systems in the search for more compatibility.

2.2.2.1. Student mobility and credit transfer in Asia

In the context of Southeast Asia one of the most representative research pieces on the development of credit systems belongs to Hotta; whose research greatly contributed to the present study, and represents a major milestone on credit transfer in Asia.

Of particular interest is his study comparing credit systems, grading policies and level of implementation in 13 countries of the region. The piece compares standards and regulations set by governments and quality assurance agencies, while looking at the trends in the implementation of those systems by the institutions. Through the chapters of the report a detailed description of HE systems is offered for each country with data on structures and functioning of each educational system.(Asahara & Hotta, 2010)

In a related article the same author offers an overview of: 1) Standards and regulations at the national level on credit systems, and 2) general status of implementation (Hotta, 2010a).

As a whole, Hotta's research puts forward important aspects that give a solid theoretical base to the present project, these aspects refer to the fact that:

- The amount of contact hours and students' workload, for typical lectures average time of study is 13-17 hours; self-study hours including practice and experiments range from 32.5 - 51 hours. This is in average 15 hours of lectures with 45 hours of self-study per credit.

- Similar allocation of years for study programmes: bachelor degree tends to last 4 years, with variations on amount of credits needed for graduation (where the typical range of credits goes from 120-150 credit units for social sciences and humanities). While engineering and medicine tend to be 1 or 2 years longer.
- Masters tend to last two years with credits in the range of 24-45 units. However there are shorter and longer programmes, whereby allocation of credits is also diverse.
- Doctorates tend to last two to three years and the use of credits is diverse. Among countries using credits the trend is a range of 30-50 credits for graduation; however distribution of credit to workload varies depending on courses and dissertation.
- Grading regulations show that most countries have rules to guide evaluation of students, some countries do not have unified systems.
- On regulation of transfer of credits with institutions abroad, only a small group of countries account with national rules that determine how those transfers are to be done.
- Regarding amounts of credits per course, in most cases courses yield two to four credits. To finish a bachelor degree students need to complete an average of 120 to 170 credits; however Medicine and Engineering typically request up to 200 credits and longer periods. For masters rules vary in amount of credits needed in a range of 20 to 60 credits. And for doctorate programmes tendencies are more disperse.
- There is a tendency of considering a passing mark at 60% or more, some countries and institutions require 50% or more and others even 40% or more.
- On the use of GPAs (Grade Point Average), the comparison shows that most countries have implemented this system however usage varies greatly.

Another important contribution Hotta makes on the transferability of credits in Asia relates to ensuring objective grading standards, and the need of explaining grading methods and distribution of points on the syllabi of subjects. After acknowledging the difficulty here due to the great range of differences among teachers and institutions that render mutual understandings thorny and complicated, he suggests a strategy to approach the problem:

“In this situation [difficulties institutions and teachers face due to differences in the systems], credit transfer systems, such as ACTS and ECTS, have proposed the use of relative estimation. In this research, we investigated the use of absolute estimation and relative estimation as well, and found out that many HEIs use both estimation systems according to the program and school year. Therefore, we should not discuss the rights or wrongs of the use of either estimation. Rather, we should set up certain rules for the distribution of grades and investigate the possibility of constructing a system to maintain fairness in grading [...].” (Hotta, 2010b)

A similar study was done by the ASEM Asia-Europe Meeting Group resulting in a research piece called *Credit Systems and Learning Outcomes in ASEM Member Countries* seeking to enhance cooperation at the interregional level based on the compatibility of programmes and educational systems. Similar to Hotta’s work it compares HE systems in the countries of the grouping by regions. Interestingly the comparison goes from a country to country based approach for Asia, to a *system* level when analysing the European case -focused on the *Bologna process*- putting in evidence the gap in the level of integration between the two regions. The study was based on the premise that common points are starting points for more cooperation between the regions, especially in the areas of quality assurance, curricular

transparency and development of mechanisms to boost recognition based on learning outcomes (The ASEM education secretariat, n.d.).

To deepen inter-regional relations and to boost cooperation between Asia and Europe, Mongkhonvanit and Emery analyze the roles *bilingualism* (English as the medium for instruction and communication) and *quality education* play to ease international recognition. These authors argue that a credits transfer scheme for Asia and Europe is plausible, considering similarities between ERASMUS and ECTS as compared to UMAP's UCTS (Mongkhonvanit & Emery, 2003).

The review credit transferability in Asia suggests a complex scenario with deep differences both within and among the countries and institutions. Non-the-less it should be noted that the region shows potentials for integration especially given the atmosphere of increasing interaction and growing number of international programmes.

2.3. International instruments on mobility and recognition

Key international legal instruments have been considered for reference as they delineate mechanisms for cooperation and harmonisation of educational systems at the multilateral level. There exist today various international conventions on the recognition of HE studies and qualifications typically adopted under the auspices of UNESCO.

The first of these agreements is a convention signed among countries in Latin America and Caribbean called *International Convention on the Recognition of Studies, Diplomas and Degrees in Higher Education* (1974). Which was followed by five similar conventions covering other regions: in the Arab and European States bordering the Mediterranean Sea - Mediterranean Convention- (1976), the Arab States (1978), Europe (1979), Africa (1981), and Asia and the Pacific (1983).

The Regional Convention on the Recognition of Studies, Diplomas and Degrees in Higher Education in Asia and the Pacific was adopted in the International Conference of States in Bangkok to facilitate recognition of studies, diplomas, and degrees among signatory states (UNESCO, 1983). In 2011, 35 countries, including 25 Asia-Pacific member states during the International Conference of States celebrated in Tokyo endorsed a renewed Regional Convention on the Recognition of Studies, Diplomas and Degrees in Higher Education in Asia and the Pacific to reinforce the harmonization efforts; the convention was renamed as *Revised Asia-Pacific Regional Convention on the Recognition of Qualifications in Higher Education 2011*, or simply Tokyo Convention on recognition. (UNESCO, 2011). This offers a framework and guidelines to ease regional co-operation on recognition of qualifications through already existing national, bilateral, sub-regional and regional mechanisms.

Finally, the Lisbon Convention or *Convention on the Recognition of Qualifications concerning Higher Education in Europe* agreed in the Council of Europe elaborated with UNESCO (1997) was included as a key reference for it provides measures to deepen harmonization (Council of Europe, 2011). Similar to what is happening in other regions of the world, and especially regarding the developments within the Bologna Process, this Convention deserves deep consideration as it may well lay the foundations for further integration of HE in Asia.

2.4. Conclusion

The review offers an overview of research and documentation on student mobility and mechanisms to foster it with a focus on multilateral transfer of credits. Although many of the

research pieces here present case studies, the review has given more relevance to those with more interest in *multilateral level*.

Among the most relevant findings was the fact that very little is available comparing credit transfer schemes at the system level. Instead most of literature focuses on cases (typically countries) in a somewhat encapsulated fashion, rendering the transversal analysis difficult.

There is great amount of interest in analysing political, social, economic and cultural aspects of the credit systems; however there is little discussion on the *technical* aspects of the credit systems and transferability of credits. Although some insightful papers describe the “*hows*” of credit transfer, in terms of amount they appear as a minority, which further justifies the need for this research at the context of SEAMEO-RIHED.

Notably in Asia very little seems to be available beyond country level comparisons. Although various arrangements for multilateral credit transfer have been put in place academic research on their implementation and effectiveness is clearly still lacking.

Among the challenges foreseen through the review, we should mention difficulties associated to the increasing enrolment rates, which will continue to put more pressure on governments and education institutions in order to accept and canalize more students. Likewise, more mobility means new risks in terms of accreditation and recognition related to quality of services; the increase in the number of providers and their integrity. More students on the move and institutions canalizing that flow mean more diversity; which will necessarily bring more difficulties to control fake or fraudulent credentials and to recognize qualifications from newly accredited institutions. Challenges will likely remain regarding the understanding of academic qualifications, their contents and graduations; and related to this, the absence of credit recognition, the fairness in evaluation and recognition and so on.

Although there is high motivation among countries regarding regionalization of HE, areas of possible conflict will continue to call for decisive actions in terms of 1) reforms regarding the cycle of degree system and years associated to them; 2) development and refinement of joint degree programmes; 3) overcoming economic and financial constrains that put obstacles to mobility; 4) overcoming other restrictions like visas, work permits and the like; 5) need for further improvements in quality assurance; and 6) need to further understand how HE strengthen national and regional economies.

A last reflection to be drawn from the revision of the literature is that there is need to consider and understand that credit transfer systems -be them unilateral or bilateral, but especially for multilateral arrangements- serve as *bridges* that connect *knowledge* and *learning*. Not only these schemes facilitate the mobility of students around HE systems and institutions, but they also promote the increasing mutual understanding of those systems, institutions and the programmes provided by them.

Credit transfer systems greatly contribute to the process of making curricula more transparent and understandable; while they also have important potentials to democratize the access to education and the direction of the careers, while allowing more learners to enter different forms of HE (*massification*).

Credit transfer systems utilized at the regional level have the potential to contribute in the consolidation of knowledge based societies in Asia, as the most appropriate strategy countries and institutions have in a world where globalization does not forgive or wait.

3. Research methodology for the *Explore* phase

3.1. Goals of the project as a whole

As explained in the Introduction the project *Harmonization and Networking in Higher Education. Building a Common Credit Transfer System for GMS and beyond* seeks to lay foundations for HE systems in the region to better coordinate efforts and create synergies toward the production of human resources for the increasingly fluid labour markets.

With this broad goal in mind the project seeks to set a regional scheme for credit transfer that is suitable for all HEIs conceived in a process of four phases: *Explore*, *Experiment*, *Experience* and *Expand*.

Due to funding reasons the project has been designed to begin its implementation in a limited scope focusing on GMS countries (Cambodia, China, Lao PDR, Myanmar, Thailand and Vietnam) plus two other members of ASEAN (Indonesia and Malaysia), plus two East Asia countries (Japan and The Republic of Korea) to gradually grow and include all countries in Southeast and East Asia.

Each of these phases works as a block upon which the next is built, hence *Explore* seeks to present an overview of the credit transfer systems worldwide with a focus in the situation of credit systems at the national level to serve as the base from where to create a scheme that is valid and flexible enough to be applicable to all HEIs in the region.

From the outcomes of *Explore*, the second phase of the project, *Experiment*, is designed to launch a pilot project where pioneer HEIs are invited to use the credit transfer scheme proposed for the exchange of students in the region at a limited scope both in terms of HEIs participating and disciplines.

The third phase of the project, *Experience*, will evaluate the outcomes from phase two, to consolidate good practices, revise directions as necessary and prepare for the further growth of the projects to a full regional and multidisciplinary scope in the fourth phase of the project –*Expand*–.

Goals at the higher education system level

- Contribute toward the consolidation of a harmonic Asian Higher Education Area
- Re-direct the flows of student mobility towards an intra-regional level
- Promote attractiveness and visibility of HE in the region
- Set a regional strategy endorsed by HEIs and supported by governments
- Promote the realization of regional potentials and deepening mutual understanding
- Reduce duplication of work resulting from bilateralism
- Democratize access and progression of HE → Deepen and boost the process of *massification* by offering flexible learning opportunities to people in the region
- Promote participation based on ownership of stakeholders
- Create a HE Area where profiles of graduates relate to their professional goals
- Better colligate profiles and competences of graduates to global labour markets
- Promote recognition of prior learning (accumulation) towards life-long learning
- Promote regional brain-train while reducing extra-regional brain-drain
- Promote multiculturalism and respect for diversity for economic growth and peace

Goals at the HEIs level

- Set a common mechanism toward practical and rational comparability of programmes
- Promote multilateralism among HEIs to enhance networking potentials
- Encourage competitiveness and quality of HEIs and programmes
- Increase interconnectivity within the region and the world
- Facilitate inter-institutional comparison of academic credits and grades
- Set rules that make education systems more compatible
- Promote networking among HEIs to facilitate interpretation of qualifications and grades
- Account with an agreed framework that allows for systematic procedures for mobility:
 - o Within the same HEIs and among different HEIs
 - o Horizontal mobility:
 - HEIs to HEIs (in the same level: Ba, Ma and PhD)
 - o Vertical mobility
 - Include / add to traditional recognition of degree the recognition of credits (accumulation → life-long learning)
 - o Temporary: in exchange programmes → relating home and host HEIs
 - o Permanent: students moving definitely for completion of degrees in other HEI → relating sending/original and receiving/accepting HEIs
- Emphasize equal partnerships based on comparative advantages of each HEI

Goals at the student level

- Increase educational pathways and choices for learning and progression
- Improve the relation value for the money of HE
- Promote the recognition of non-academic learning experiences (E.g. work experience)
- Promote ownership and responsibility toward future professional goals
- Promote fairness in the transfer and recognition processes
- Allow space for consideration of students as free movers, for those who wish to study outside the frameworks set by the agreements of their HEIs, or that are left outside the placement quotas for exchange programmes → If HEIs agree to the framework proposed, students are free to choose destinations and courses of their own interest.

3.2. Explanation of the first phase -*Explore*-

3.2.1. Research design and implementation

The following pages explain the research action plan guiding this study for the project's first phase: *Explore*. This stage was conceived as a descriptive and comparative research that constitutes the starting step upon which the next phases of the whole action research project build on toward the setting of a common credit transfer scheme for the region.

Phase one, or *Explore*, was structured as two research areas:

- 1) Describe and compare multilateral credit transfers systems globally;
- 2) Describe and compare HE systems and credit systems at the national level in the ten countries included at this stage.

3.2.2. Goals for the first phase of the project: *Explore*

For the initial phase of the project –*Explore*- this study seeks to:

1. *Condense* lessons learned from existing multilateral credit transfer systems to better

understand how different mechanisms deal with the transfer of academic credits.

2. *Capitalize* those experiences to contribute to the betterment of student mobility through a renewed strategy for credit transfer that can better articulate already existing systems.

3. *Describe* and *find common points* among the credit systems in use in the countries included in the research at this point.

4. From the findings from 1, 2 and 3, *propose* a model for credit transfer that is valid for the region as a whole.

By accomplishing these goals the report resulting from the *Explore* phase of the project responds to the need of thinking of a common platform for credit transfer based on consensus from major stakeholders -governments, education institutions and students- in a relatively small geographical area -the Great Mekong Subregion and a other neighbouring countries in East and Southeast Asia-.

3.2.3. The three parts of *Explore*

Due to the nature of the funding used for the research, *Explore* was conceived and structured in three parts that took place simultaneously:

Part one: CTS in perspective. It is a comparative screening of major multilateral credit transfer systems at a global scope and the goal of this phase is to describe and spot main features of existing models. This was done through an internet based a review of main existing schemes by the coordinator of the programme at SEAMEO-RIHED. Outcomes from part one serve as a base for further discussion among regional stakeholders.

Part two: CTS in and for GMS. This part of the study focused on existing trends and credit transfer models in the countries in the Great Mekong Subregion (Cambodia, China, Laos PDR, Myanmar, Thailand and Vietnam) GMS. Part two described and assessed on-going credit transfer systems (or other forms of transfer of students' workload and achievements) at the national, bilateral, multilateral levels. This included government-to-government and university-to-university agreements. Data was collected with the collaboration of a national resource person and consists of a desk review (literature and policies) for each country, followed by interviews with key stakeholders carried out jointly by the resource persons and SEAMEO RIHED's personnel during fieldtrips. (July-October 2012)

Part three: CTS in non-GMS (Indonesia, Japan, Republic of Korea and Malaysia). This part of the research explored trends and models beyond but relatively close the Great Mekong Subregion. The goal of part three was to describe and assess ongoing credit transfer systems (or other forms of transfer of students' workload and achievements) at the national, bilateral, multilateral levels. This included government to government and university to university arrangements. Data was gathered locally by national resource persons and consists of a desk review (literature and policies) for each country, followed by interviews with key stakeholders. (July-September 2012)

In this case, different from part 2, the research instead of having fieldtrips to the respective countries by SEAMEO RIHED's personnel, local resource persons were requested to carry the interviews by themselves and then they were invited to present their findings in an international workshop organized by SEAMEO RIHED in Bangkok on 28 September 2012.

The reason why parts two and three were developed in a sly

Findings from the three parts of the study were shared in an international workshop in Bangkok on 5 and 6 November 2012 including all participants of the project. The workshop served as a platform to 1) present country reports -findings-; 2) share experiences and lessons learnt; 3) integrate good practices and 4) gather participants ideas for a future action plan towards the implementation of a pilot regional credit transfer model based on agreed goals and procedures.

3.3. Selection of countries and resource persons

The *Explore* phase focused the research on ten countries in Southeast and East Asia, the selection of the countries included in this stage of the project was based on two reasons:

1. Nature of the funding for the research

The explore phase of the project has been financed with the contribution from the Asian Development Bank using funds allocated for the GMS Human Resource Development Strategic Framework and Action Plan -under ADB's R-PATA 7275. Hence the initial focus of the research on the six countries in the Mekong sub region: Cambodia, China, Lao PDR, Myanmar, Thailand and Vietnam.

2. Existence of multilateral student mobility programmes

The second reason is practical and is based on the fact that multilateral credit systems closely relate to student mobility programmes. At the moment of launching the research two programmes were deemed essential as they were ongoing and account with strong governmental and institutional support. These are the AIMS programme (former M-I-T) that already connects HEIs in Malaysia, Indonesia and Thailand through the temporary exchange of students; and the Campus Asia programme that in a similar fashion connects HEIs in China, Japan and The Republic of Korea; hence the inclusion of the countries therein.

The selection of the resource persons for each country was made on nominations done by the respective Ministries of Educations and by SEAMEO RIHED's network at the HEIs level. The criterion in the selection was seeking to balance and include both researchers working at the country policy making level and academicians working at the implementation level in the universities.

3.4. Collection of data

Information for *Explore* has been gathered in the following ways:

For part one: a review on multilateral credit systems worldwide (Internet based) was done. The collection of data was guided by the categories contained in a *Comparative Individual Credit Transfer System Chart* (attached in Annex 1: Research Instruments). The chart contains areas of interest regarding multilateral credit systems on nature of the systems, scopes, procedures and advantages. The categories in the chart facilitated the organization of data from individual credit transfer systems into a transversal comparison chart.

For parts two and three: a desk review at national level was carried out in the countries included to describe national HE systems and the nature of individual credit systems being implemented there. In order to make the comparison of credit systems at the national level, resource persons were requested to use the above mentioned Comparative Individual Credit Transfer System Chart to describe systems in each country.

In depth interviews were carried out with main stakeholders from governments, universities and students at national levels of all countries included in this phase of the project.

Two international workshops were organized in Bangkok aiming to share partial findings and continue deepening the data collection process.

- *Workshop 1*, on 28 September 2012: for non-GMS+2 (Indonesia, Malaysia, Japan, and the Republic of Korea, Thailand participated as well as the host country) served as a platform for resource persons from each country to share their preliminary findings.
 - *Workshop 2*, on 5 and 6 November 2012 included all ten countries in this phase (GMS+ASEAN+Japan+R.Korea). In this occasion, resource persons from each country shared their findings and discussed with participants through open discussions on future steps and strategies for implementation of an open regional scheme.
- Follow up was carried out after country reports were submitted in order to finalize details for comparison.

Lastly during workshop 3, which took place in Siem Reap, Cambodia in April 2013, findings from the explore phase together with a model for regional credit transfer were presented by SEAMEO RIHED and discussed with major stakeholders.

3.5. Selection of sources (unit of analysis)

The project includes three main stakeholders in HE:

1. **Government officers.** Because credit transfer is a mechanism for mobility in the *Explore* phase, with the help of resource persons SEAMEO RIHED identified officials that are knowledgeable of credit system in each country and carried out interviews to understand each government's position; typically these were people working for the Ministry of Education, in positions related to HE, international cooperation or exchange programmes.

2. **High education institutions such as universities, tertiary schools or research institutes** that allow students to move (temporary or permanently) *to* and *from* other institutions; and that recognize (totally or partially) the work students do while in the other institutions (be it in the form of academic credits or in any other form). Interviews with this group and those in charge of internationalization policies at the HEI level included mostly administrative personnel dealing with exchange students and procedures.

3. **Students and researchers** that have, are in the mist of, or wish to participate in exchange programmes or transfer from a university or institution to another, were interviewed in order to include their voices as main beneficiaries of the credit transfer schemes.

3.6. Samples and analysis of the data

Because the study consists of two comparisons (one of credit transfer systems and another of HE systems and the credit systems in the countries) two different samples were used to approach each of them and two different forms of data analysis were used accordingly.

3.6.1. Comparison of credit transfer systems

3.6.1.1. The sample for credit transfer systems

A purposive sample was used for the comparative analysis of credit transfer systems and focused *more* on systems being implemented in Asia but considering the global context.

The sample considered more extensively on multilateral credit transfer systems including various countries and HEIs. However in order to make the sample more representative it also contains systems that function at the multiregional level and examples of country and institutions based unilateral systems were included only as reference.

On order to make the handling of the sample easier, it was organized in four comparative tables including 5 credit transfer systems each and consisted of the following credit transfer arrangements.

Table 1: Credit Transfer Systems included per table

Comparative tables	Credit Transfer Systems included per table
Group 1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ECTS: European Credit Transfer System 2. UCTS: UMAP Credit Transfer System 3. AeU ACTS: Asia e University contemplated in Asia Cooperation Dialogue (ACD) scheme 4. ACTS: ASEAN Credit Transfer System (AUN network) 5. CAMPUS Asia (Collective Action for the Mobility Program of University Students)
Group 2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. ASEM CTS: Asia Europe Meeting 7. AE CTS: Asia Exchange 8. Credit Accumulation and Transfer System in East Africa 9. Association of African Universities 10. Arab Space for Higher Education
Group 3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Latin-American Reference Credit (CLAR) Tuning project 12. Carnegie Unit and Student Hour - American typical CS 13. EAUI. East Asian University Institute for Asian Region 14. Go8: Credit Transfer Agreement by 8 Universities in Australia 15. SADC South African Development Community
Group 4	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 16. CTS at University of Melbourne Australia 17. EACTS: EU-ASEAN. Student mobility and joint Award Degree in Engineering Education 18. The Open University (UK) CTS-ECTS 19. QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK 20. CQFW. Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales

3.6.1.2. Analysis of data from credit transfer systems: categories for comparison

For this part of the research, SEAMEO RIHED created a *Comparative Individual Credit Transfer System Chart* (attached in Annex 3: Research Kit) that served as the base of categories for contrast and assessment of the different systems.

The categories used to compare credit transfer systems include four areas of analysis: 1) Nature; 2) Procedures; 3) External assistance to CTS; and 4) Evaluation of CTS.

The area of *Nature* describes features of each credit transfer system and includes the following subcategories/descriptors: 1) Regional scope; 2) Members; 3) Main stakeholders; 4)

Goals; 5) Legal involvement (governmental participation vs. HEIs' autonomy); 6) Applicable students; and 7) Others.

The area of *Procedures* depicts how different systems manage the movements of information among high educational institutions. This section includes the subcategories / descriptors of: 1) Procedures. 2) Who and where does the system originate? 3) How is the information shared among students and universities? 4) While students are overseas, how are subjects decided? 5) Students' workload measurement (at home and host HEI). 6) Scale "matching" system. 7) How is information circulated between HEIs? 8) Who verifies documents? 9) Time for procedure. 10) Appeal system. 11) Outcomes. 12) Others.

The area of *External assistance to CTS* explores factors outside the credit transfer systems themselves that help to facilitate the mobility of students and hence foster the use of credit transfers among HEIs. This section includes the following categories/ descriptors: 1) Scholarships; 2) quality assurance; 3) diploma supplement; and 4) other forms of recognition of workload.

The last area of comparison was *Evaluation of CTS*. In this section the comparison focuses on assessments of those systems in order to spot good practices, avoid mistakes and learn from previous lessons. The section includes the following categories: 1) main advantages of the CTS; 2) main disadvantages of the CTS; 3) perceived level of effectiveness; and 4) others.

3.6.2. Comparison of credit systems at the country level

3.6.2.1. The samples for credit systems in each country

For this part of the research again a *purposive sample* was used to target knowledgeable individuals on credit systems in the countries included at this stage and it consisted of:

- Three or more government officials in key positions (typically, but not only, working in ministries of education)
- One or more international officer from each selected university or high education institution. The amount of institutions included per country depended on the complexity of each country. Recourse persons were requested to build balanced samples that include: 1) representative institutions, not only "major/famous universities" but also one or two middle range institutions and two or three newer and less famous institutions; 2) Public *and* private institutions; 3) Institutions from different regions of the country (located not only main or capital cities); 4) *All levels* of high education: bachelor, diploma, master and doctorate; 5) the sample should include careers like accounting, architecture, business, economics, engineering, international studies, language courses, medical, nursing, technology and tourism & hospitality.
- Three or more students or researchers participating of exchange programmes

3.6.2.2. The questionnaires

Resource persons were requested to use standard questionnaires (attached in Annex 3: Research Kit) with each of the target groups (government officials, personnel in universities and HEIs and students & researchers participating in exchange programmes) focusing on:

1. Nature of existing credit systems in the country
2. Credit transfer procedures

3. Perceptions on effectiveness of credit systems in the country
4. Stakeholder critical inputs for future action to facilitate mobility and harmonize HE.

3.6.2.3. Making the country comparisons

In order to compare the situation of credit systems and the transferability of academic achievements among countries resource persons were requested to adjust the content of their country reports to a standardize format categories so as ease the transversal comparison of same categories. Country reports consist of the following sections:

1. Introduction
2. CTS Desk Review in [country name]
3. CTS in the eyes of the government
4. CTS in the eyes of the universities or other HEIs
5. CTS in the eyes of students
6. Conclusions
7. Recommendations
8. Bibliography

Introductions include a description of the high education system in each country, trends on students' mobility (domestic/international) and transfer of students' workload horizontally (university to university) or vertically (E.g. from undergraduate to masters or doctorate programmes).

CTS Desk Review in [country name] synthesizes data found on general HE trends in each country.

CTS in the eyes of the government provides information on the position of each government regarding transfer of students workload (domestic and internationally). Data for this section was obtained from interviews with government officers and agencies in key positions of HE. Resource persons were requested to analyse the data in a transversal fashion, as in the graph to the right.

Table 2: Transversal comparative analysis of data

CTS in the eyes of universities or other HEIs provides information on the position of main HEIs regarding the mobility of students *from* and *to* other universities (domestic and international). Data for this section was obtained from the interviews with personnel in universities in key positions related to student mobility; typically officers working at international students affairs departments or international student exchange programmes. The analysis of data was done in the same way as in the graph above.

CTS in the eyes of students provides information on the position of students participating in exchange programmes to universities or HEIs other than their home universities (domestic and international). Data for this section was obtained from interviews with students. Analysis of data was done in the same way as in the two previous sections.

Conclusions and recommendations were considered a central part of the data collected as they include observations on the countries and their trends, but most importantly this section suggests actions to be taken by major stakeholders in order to encourage changes and reforms in attitudes and policies aiming to further facilitate student mobility through the use of credit transfer models.

4. Comparison of main multilateral credit transfer systems

4.1. Why comparing credit transfer systems

This section provides a comparative analysis of 20 credit systems to describe how they work, their advantages and disadvantages as tools to facilitate student mobility. The comparison of credit systems is based on the need to understand the logics behind their principles and procedures, as well as learn from previous and on-going experiences; understanding differences and commonalities and why some systems work smoothly while others remain dead letter; identifying good practices; and understanding the factors that make systems more or less sensitive, rendering them more likely to be used.

Credit transfer systems support students as they pass through educational pathways. They simplify and promote moves among programmes and institutions creating opportunities for successful completion and promote graduation rates. Transferability of credits encourages lifelong learning and widens access and participation rates of learners. They reduce and even eliminate unnecessary tuition fees and other educational costs; which help students reduce borrowing money for education promote further enrolment and completion because they allow for more flexibility in terms of time and financial costs (Junor & Usher, 2008).

Recent decades show increasing systematization of procedures, especially at the multilateral level, which responds to a growing interest of governments and HEIs for strategies to further harmonize systems and procedures; which at the same time has promoted increasing volumes and kinds of student mobility.

Although the bulk of student movements among HEIs still happen on *bilateral agreements* between HEIs, the focus here is on *multilateral systems* because these agreements are more efficient and reduce duplication of work, for those negotiating the terms of the agreements and for international relations officers dealing with transfer and recognition procedures.

As compared to bilateral agreements, multilateral ones work slower when negotiated and implemented but they remain more *stable* over time, they usually show rapid institutional learning and maintenance of records on progress and offer standardized procedures and communication channels that ease procedures as compared to bilaterally based transfers, where information and procedures are more disperse.

Within this context two *paradigms* have emerged on *how students' workload is measured*, which has important implication regarding procedures and transferability. On the one hand the American system gauges students' workload based on *time* as *the* unit to measure efforts required to achieve knowledge or skills (Shedd, 2003) that are accumulated in blocks towards graduation. Harris explains that “[the American] *credit system makes the university a banking system (...), [by] likening the pursuit of the American baccalaureate to buying it on the installment plan*” (Harris, 2002). While on the other hand, European systems focus on *learning outcomes* as knowledge or skills acquired from a learning process that includes the notion of time but as *one more element* in the assessment, not as the main one.

4.2. Summary chart comparing credit transfer systems

The following table presents a compact transversal comparison of 20 credit systems analyzed for this research. The complete (extended) version of the table can be found at the Appendix 1: Comparison of Credit Transfer Systems.

Table 3: Summary of data comparing Credit Transfer Systems (N/A : data not available)

(Group 1)

ECTS	UMAP / UCTS	AeU / ACTS	AUN / ACTS	CAMPUS Asia
NATURE OF SYSTEM				
Regional scope				
European countries	Countries in Asia and the Pacific	Asia Cooperation Dialogue, 30 Asian countries	ASEAN countries	China, Japan, South Korea
Goals				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Common Education Area - Smooth recognition - HE compatible & attractive - 3 cycles (Ba, Ma, PhD) - QA → trust - Credit based programmes - use of learning outcomes - Student-centred system - Common language - Lifelong learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Credit transfer for exchange - Academic mobility - Multilateral approach - Cooperation as <i>consortia</i> - Smoothen mutual recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate mobility and recognition - Curricular development and comparability - Cooperation amongst HEIs in Asia - Recognition of prior learning - Promote attractiveness of Asian HE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Student mobility among AUN HEIs - Cooperation for ASEAN integration - Promote ASEAN spirit - Increase choices of courses - Re-direct student mobility flows (intra region) - Cultural enrichment of students - Create an ASEAN Brand 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop exchange among universities - Develop Human resource - Cultural diversity - Mutual understanding - Harmonized university evaluation
PROCEDURE				
Procedure				
<p>Learning outcomes → credits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 60 credits=full time year - 30 credits = semester - Workload: 1500 - 1800 hours a year → 1 credit = learning outcomes from 25-30 work hours - Degree awarding HEI decides recognition - <i>Modularisation</i> of courses 	<p>Principles for HEIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UCTS follows ECTS with differences) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equivalence based on credit value, learning level and outcomes - Accreditation of prior learning and experimental learning - Subjects from host HEIs accepted by home University (mandatory) - Subjects must be similar or close - Transferred credits not calculated in GPA but account for graduation - Maximum transferable: 30% 	<p>An extended flow chart of process is available in the Appendix 2: Comparative Table of Credit Transfer Systems Worldwide. <i>As Reference 1</i></p>	<p>Campus Asia follows procedures set for ECTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Universities as consortia - applicable to short, mid and long-term exchange and 'double degree programs' - that enable credit transfer

ECTS	UMAP / UCTS	AeU / ACTS	AUN / ACTS	CAMPUS Asia
How is information shared				
Home HEIs select students and inform host HEI - Approve programmes - Decide financial support - Recognize overseas work Host HEIs accept student, evaluate student's work and report to home HEIs	Home HEIs select students, approve programmes, financial support, and recognize overseas work. Host HEIs provide agreed programmes, evaluate student, report to home HEIs. Support to participants (accommodation, health care arrangements)	Information circulated among HEIs directly and informing the ACTS coordinator	Same as above	HEIs allow student exchange with partner HEIs based on direct communication. QA agencies support and set shared standards
How is the information shared among students and universities?				
Compare foreign/domestic qualifications on: education systems, QA, and learning outcomes. Standard information packs and online access. - ENIC/NARIC centres	- Online <i>Student Connection</i> links home, host HEIs and students - HEIs share data on courses openly to students and other HEIs - Students select host HEIs for Programme A, B or C, country, academic fields, subjects, etc.	- ACTS Coordinator receives and forwards applications from students to Dean, who nominates an academic to assess for recognition of credits based on: similarity of subjects: 70%; based on passing mark. Recognition up to home HEI	Students apply at home HEI, choose host HEIs/courses based on learning agreement. Home HEIs: assist on travel and learning agreement. Host universities: waive tuition fee, arrange accommodation, visas, etc. Online Application process	N/A
While students are overseas, how are subjects decided?				
- ENIC centres advice - Selection of subjects on <i>Learning Agreement</i> (IROs, teachers and students)	- Students choose subjects with agreement of home and host HEIs - Amendments are possible	N/A	Learning agreement prior to leaving the home university: includes students, home and host HEIs	N/A
How is student workload measured (home or host university)				

ECTS	UMAP / UCTS	AeU / ACTS	AUN / ACTS	CAMPUS Asia
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 60 credit=workload fulltime student in 1 year =1500–1800 hours - Allocation of credits based on length of programmes - Fulltime programme=36/40 weeks a year→1 credit=25-30 hours - Total workload for Ba (3-4 years)=180 or 240 credits - Level (Ba,Ma,PhD) doesn't affect credit value - Contact hours/self study do not affect credit value - Programmes award more or less credits when exceptionally long or short. 	<p>60 points (= ECTS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Workload: lectures, practices, tutorials, self-study, fieldwork,etc - Extra credits for extra activities - Value of credits agreed by student and IROs at host and home HEIs (for transfer) - Credits upon completion - 60 points = fulltime year - 30 points = one semester <p>Host HEIs: 1. Identify credits per course; 2. Convert host HEIs course units to 60 points UCTS scale and then to its own system</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If HEIs do not use credits, conversion is done on fractions of total fulltime work per term. 	<p>Full-time programmes are based on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACTS: last 36 to 40 weeks per year - 2 semesters: last 14-16 weeks - 3 trimesters: last 12 to 14 weeks <p>Workload→60 credits for full-time student; → 30 credits per semester; or → 20 credits per trimester.</p> <p>Credits measure amount of learning. ACTS follows ECTS: 1 credit=25–30 hours→ a course of 3 credits=75–90 hours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACTS covers work placement, practicum or internship <p>ACTS recognizes learning in academic, vocational/technical and skills development.</p> <p>Accreditation of prior learning</p>	<p>Workload not converted into credits for transfer (1 to 1) →automatic recognition</p> <p>ACTS distributed over time: 1 full year = 60 credits 1 semester = 30 credits 1 term/trimester = 20 credits</p>	<p>Workload described and shared by HEIs case by case</p>

Scale “matching” system (Complete grading tables available in Appendix 1)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECTS does not replace local system. Interpretation based on statistical distribution - Assessment done by host and interpreted by home HEIs with its own system - ECTS divides 2 groups: <i>pass</i> and <i>fail</i>. Passing students fall into 5 groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - top 10% = A - next 25% = B - following 30% = C - following 25% = D - final 10% = E 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Norm-referenced scale with percentage of candidates in each cohort with a pass, or better <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>grade</th> <th>Success grade (%)</th> <th>Definition</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>A</td> <td>10</td> <td>Excellent: outstanding with minor errors</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B</td> <td>25</td> <td>Very good: above average with errors</td> </tr> <tr> <td>C</td> <td>30</td> <td>Good: sound work with errors</td> </tr> <tr> <td>D</td> <td>25</td> <td>Satisfactory: fair with shortcomings</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	grade	Success grade (%)	Definition	A	10	Excellent: outstanding with minor errors	B	25	Very good: above average with errors	C	30	Good: sound work with errors	D	25	Satisfactory: fair with shortcomings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HEIs use own system - Use of percentile as reference - ACTS defines grading in relation to ECTS. Table below: <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>ECTS Scale</th> <th>US Grade 4.0 scale</th> <th>British Grade</th> <th>BERN Swiss</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>A</td> <td>A to A+ (4.0)</td> <td>70 or over</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B</td> <td>B+ to A-</td> <td>60 – 69</td> <td>5.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>C</td> <td>B (3.0)</td> <td>55 – 59</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>D</td> <td>C+ to B-</td> <td>50 – 54</td> <td>4.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>E</td> <td>C (2.0)</td> <td>40 – 49</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>FX</td> <td>F</td> <td>30 – 39</td> <td>3.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>F</td> <td>F</td> <td>< 30</td> <td>3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	ECTS Scale	US Grade 4.0 scale	British Grade	BERN Swiss	A	A to A+ (4.0)	70 or over	6	B	B+ to A-	60 – 69	5.5	C	B (3.0)	55 – 59	5	D	C+ to B-	50 – 54	4.5	E	C (2.0)	40 – 49	4	FX	F	30 – 39	3.5	F	F	< 30	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grade system is reference only - Proposed automatic recognition but HEIs decide. - Grading depends on home HEIs <p>Grading scale based on students' achievements</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>ACTS / ECTS</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Normal distribution</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>A</td> <td>Excellent</td> <td>10%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B</td> <td>Very Good</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>C</td> <td>Good</td> <td>30%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>D</td> <td>Satisfactory</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>E/F</td> <td>Fail</td> <td>10%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	ACTS / ECTS	Description	Normal distribution	A	Excellent	10%	B	Very Good	25%	C	Good	30%	D	Satisfactory	25%	E/F	Fail	10%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HEIs transfer grades attached to evaluations at their own discretion.
grade	Success grade (%)	Definition																																																																			
A	10	Excellent: outstanding with minor errors																																																																			
B	25	Very good: above average with errors																																																																			
C	30	Good: sound work with errors																																																																			
D	25	Satisfactory: fair with shortcomings																																																																			
ECTS Scale	US Grade 4.0 scale	British Grade	BERN Swiss																																																																		
A	A to A+ (4.0)	70 or over	6																																																																		
B	B+ to A-	60 – 69	5.5																																																																		
C	B (3.0)	55 – 59	5																																																																		
D	C+ to B-	50 – 54	4.5																																																																		
E	C (2.0)	40 – 49	4																																																																		
FX	F	30 – 39	3.5																																																																		
F	F	< 30	3																																																																		
ACTS / ECTS	Description	Normal distribution																																																																			
A	Excellent	10%																																																																			
B	Very Good	25%																																																																			
C	Good	30%																																																																			
D	Satisfactory	25%																																																																			
E/F	Fail	10%																																																																			

ECTS	UMAP / UCTS	AeU / ACTS	AUN / ACTS	CAMPUS Asia
How is information circulated between universities?				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Course Catalogue, package - Student Application Form - Learning Agreement - Transcript of Records - Diploma Supplement 	Online access: <i>Student connection</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Course Catalogue - Student application form - Learning agreement - Transcript of records 	ACTS proposes the use of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information Packages - Course Catalogues - Learning agreements - Transcript of records 	Direct connections between IRO's and links with the central system related to its website	N/A
EXTERNAL "ASSISTANCE" TO CTS				
Quality assurance				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use ECTS is central for QA - Accreditation based on agreement of curricula - ECTS use learning outcome 	N/A	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - QA key for mobility - Regional QA system being considered - Relevant role of National QA 	N/A
Diploma supplement				
Describes nature, level, context, content of studies, graduates and HEIs	N/A	DS under consideration but not yet implemented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No advancements - Perceived as "political issue" to be addressed at the ministerial level 	N/A
EVALUATION OF CTS				
Main advantage				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HEIs autonomy - Easy interpretation, transfer and recognition → more mobility - Flexible study paths and progression: student-centred - Curricula development - Use of learning outcomes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fair value of credits - Practical information share - Open to HEIs/countries - Easy comparison - Curricula development - Students undertake formal studies on exchange 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Student-centred - Flexibility and transparency - Aids mobility - Preserves autonomy of HEIs - Helps curricula development - Eases mutual recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "online shopping" courses in English in HEIs of network - Online system allows for rapid evaluation and monitoring, up to date information - Student-centred - ACTS does not need modifications 	N/A
Main disadvantage				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not all countries use ECTS-compatible systems - ECTS is still under debate - Implementation lagoons 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operation is not satisfactory - Little authority - QA issues - Lack of ownership by HEIs 	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited to member universities - Academic compatibility - poor attention to accumulation - Undergraduate students only 	N/A

COMPARISON OF CREDIT TRANSFER SYSTEMS (Group 2, continued)

ASEM. Asia Europe Meeting	AE – ECTS. Asia Exchange	Credit Accumulation and Transfer System East African Countries	Association of African Universities	Arab Space for Higher Education
NATURE OF SYSTEM				
Regional scope				
Asia, Europe, Australia and New Zealand	Inter-region (Asia-Europe) + New Zealand America, Australian and	Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania	Southern Africa, Eastern Africa, Western Africa and Northern Africa.	Maghreb countries
Goals				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve information on academic developments - Use of learning outcomes - Promote joint studies- Interregional cooperation (QA among HEIs & networks) - Transparent programmes, - Asia/European Network of experts (information share) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Boost international mobility - Foster language proficiency and professional skills - Broaden awareness on cultural diversity and lifelong friendships - Access to international programmes - Easy and smooth transfer of educational experiences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Curricular transparency - Promote student mobility - Use common CS with workload based on credit hours - Guarantee value for money in HE - Link credits and diplomas with HEIs in East Africa - Recognition of previous work - Integration of HES in East Africa 	Continental HE strategy to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harmonise regional HE - Standardised information exchange - Develop a continental qualification framework - Set minimum academic standards - Set a joint curriculum development and student mobility schemes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish Arab QA network - Easy exchange of information - QA agencies support for standards in HE - Cooperation between existing agencies in the region - Set a regional CTS
PROCEDURE				
Procedure				
N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study plans agreed - Students complete requirement and receive grades to transfer credits - Host HEIs issue transcript upon completion but recognition of credits lies on home HEI. - Home HEIs request students to complete courses at host HEI to be added as core or selective. 	Experts decide minimum requisites Course description include hours needed to cover their content and suggested credits Support from QA agencies at national level toward recognition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decisions made in Conferences of Rectors, Vice Chancellors and Presidents of African Universities aiming to: - Create an African HE Space (Arusha Convention) - Establish African QA framework - Establish a credit transfer system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CT follows ECTS - QA promoted among countries associated with to Tempus programme
How is information shared				
N/A	- Online information of HEIS	N/A	N/A	N/A

ASEM. Asia Europe Meeting	AE – ECTS. Asia Exchange	Credit Accumulation and Transfer System East African Countries	Association of African Universities	Arab Space for Higher Education																		
How is the information shared among students and universities?																						
N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Online diffusion and application - Agreed study plan - AE students are <i>freemovers</i> 	N/A	N/A	N/A																		
While students are overseas, how are subjects decided?																						
N/A	- Study plan prior to departure	N/A	N/A	N/A																		
How is student workload measured (home or host university)																						
N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Credits based on workload & learning outcome. Larger work yield more credits Converting Thai Credits Courses at AE's partner HEIs are worth 3-4 credits, where 1 credit = 15-12 lecture hours. 1 course in Thailand= 5 ECTS or 3 US credits Converting Chinese Credits In china partner HEI 1 credit=18 lecture hours→1 credit = 1.5 ECTS or 1 US credit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 Credit Unit (CU)=15 lecture hours - 1 CU = 30 tutorial hours - 1 CU = 45 practical hours - 1 CU = 60 industrial/ training hours - Total transferable credits: up to 49% of total required for graduation 	N/A	N/A																		
Scale “matching” system (Complete grading tables available in Appendix 1)																						
N/A	N/A	Proposed grade system: <table border="1" data-bbox="902 1038 1341 1347" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Mark - %</th> <th>Class/letter grade</th> <th>Grade value</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>75 to 100</td> <td>1st Class/A</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>60 to 74</td> <td>2nd Class upper/B</td> <td>3 to 4.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>40 to 59</td> <td>2nd Class lower/C</td> <td>2.0 to 2.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>45 to 49</td> <td>Pass or D</td> <td>1.0 to 1.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>35 to 44</td> <td>Pass or D</td> <td>0.5 to 1.0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Mark - %	Class/letter grade	Grade value	75 to 100	1 st Class/A	5	60 to 74	2 nd Class upper/B	3 to 4.5	40 to 59	2 nd Class lower/C	2.0 to 2.5	45 to 49	Pass or D	1.0 to 1.5	35 to 44	Pass or D	0.5 to 1.0	N/A	N/A
Mark - %	Class/letter grade	Grade value																				
75 to 100	1 st Class/A	5																				
60 to 74	2 nd Class upper/B	3 to 4.5																				
40 to 59	2 nd Class lower/C	2.0 to 2.5																				
45 to 49	Pass or D	1.0 to 1.5																				
35 to 44	Pass or D	0.5 to 1.0																				
How is information circulated between universities?																						

ASEM. Asia Europe Meeting	AE – ECTS. Asia Exchange	Credit Accumulation and Transfer System East African Countries	Association of African Universities	Arab Space for Higher Education
N/A	Credit transfer is based on the students' own plan and account of workload, HEIs' assessments and decisions. Home HEIs decide on transfer of credits	Government and university cooperation	N/A	N/A
EXTERNAL "ASSISTANCE" TO CTS				
Quality assurance				
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Diploma supplement				
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
EVALUATION OF CTS				
Main advantage				
- Informality - Multi-dimensionality - Emphasis on equal partnership - Focus: <i>people-to-people</i>	- Students have <i>freemover</i> status - No HEIs placement quotas - Simplified application & approval procedures - Centralized information access	N/A	N/A	N/A
Main disadvantage				
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

COMPARISON OF CREDIT TRANSFER SYSTEMS (Group 3, continued)

Latin-American Reference Credit (CLAR) TUNING	Carnegie Unit and Student Hour	EAUI. East Asian University Institute for Asian Region	The Go8 Credit Transfer Agreement Group of 8 universities (Australia)	CTS SADC. South African Development Community
NATURE OF SYSTEM				
Regional scope				
Latin America and Europe	American Universities	HEIs in East & Southeast Asia	8 Universities of Australia	South Africa Development Community (SADC)
Goals				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Set Latin-American HE Space - Curricular reform based on competences - Harmonization of degrees - Evaluation of achievements to improve quality - Design a CS to transfer to ease recognition 	Measurement of students workload for comparison and transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set a political, economic, social hub on Asia-Pacific Studies - Boost Asian integration - Produce experts to contribute to the realization of regional interests - Establish an inter-University QA framework - Develop joint research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote student mobility - Enhance HEIs contribution to the nation's prosperity - Strengthen Australia's capacity to engage in and benefit from global developments - Expand opportunities for Australian students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regionalisation and intra-region student mobility - Standardization of entrance requirements, harmonization of HE, ease credit transfers, provision of in-state tuition and fee rates to students from other SADC countries - Improve quality in HE
PROCEDURE				
Procedure				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Academic activities assessed based on hours required to achieve capacities needed by degree. - Correlation of profile of degrees, learning outcomes. - General and specific competencies are weighed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HEIs give credit for sessions in standard semesters - Credits granted adjust to length of terms - When transferring credit, students' credit hours are adjusted based on the systems used between the two HEIs. 	Faculty personnel to be employed to take classes on subjects relevant to Asian regional integration and adopt core roles in joint research projects. Inter-university exchange and employment expected to be in place.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transfer of credits based on the agreement that recognition at all Go8 HEIs are comparable - No formal transfer process needed between Australian universities. -No guarantee that students receive credit for all courses completed at the original institution. 	African Credit Transfer Systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reach common understanding of what a "credit" is - Agree on minimum content for courses - Enter into regional agreement on credit transfer
How is information shared				
Among universities	Directly between HEIs	N/A	N/A	N/A
How is the information shared among students and universities?				
N/A	N/A	Information on project's website	Directly between universities	N/A

Latin-American Reference Credit (CLAR) TUNING	Carnegie Unit and Student Hour	EAUI. East Asian University Institute for Asian Region	The Go8 Credit Transfer Agreement Group of 8 universities (Australia)	CTS SADC. South African Development Community									
While students are overseas, how are subjects decided?													
Universities communicate directly	Learning agreement	Students agree with HEIs depending on type of programme.	Students meet requirements of programme. Agreed study plan.	N/A									
How is student workload measured (home or host university)													
<p>- 1 credit hour=15 or 16 weeks in a semester. 1 hour of class implies 2 hours of independent work</p> <p>- Countries measure credits qualitatively, relative importance of subjects to careers.</p> <p>- Annual workload of fulltime students=60 credits, a semester=30 credits</p> <p>- 36 weeks of academic work a year → range of hours per week (40 to 55), hours range of student work is 1440 to 1980 hours</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="91 1002 432 1321"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="91 1002 181 1161">Week /year</th> <th data-bbox="181 1002 300 1161">Work hours / week</th> <th data-bbox="300 1002 432 1161">Work hour/ year</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="91 1161 181 1241">36 week</td> <td data-bbox="181 1161 300 1241">40 hours</td> <td data-bbox="300 1161 432 1241">1440 hours</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="91 1241 181 1321">36 week</td> <td data-bbox="181 1241 300 1321">55 hours</td> <td data-bbox="300 1241 432 1321">1980 hours</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Week /year	Work hours / week	Work hour/ year	36 week	40 hours	1440 hours	36 week	55 hours	1980 hours	<p>- State/HEI set minimum credits to graduate</p> <p>- Various systems exist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 credit = 1 course - 1 credit = 1 hour/week in class - 1 credit = hour/week to course (including homework), etc. <p>- In the <i>Carnegie unit system</i> all courses contain the same amount of hours per semester. After a four-year run, the student needs 24 - 28 credits to graduate</p> <p>- In HEIs students receive credit hours based on number of <i>contact hours</i> per week in class</p> <p>- HEIs with emphasis on research receive reduced course loads in lieu of research</p>	N/A	Credit unites granted by a HEI in the group are considered <i>appropriate</i> units of study, and if successfully completed by the student at another HEI in Group of Eight university, automatically recognized.	N/A
Week /year	Work hours / week	Work hour/ year											
36 week	40 hours	1440 hours											
36 week	55 hours	1980 hours											
Scale “matching” system													

Latin-American Reference Credit (CLAR) TUNING	Carnegie Unit and Student Hour	EAUI. East Asian University Institute for Asian Region	The Go8 Credit Transfer Agreement Group of 8 universities (Australia)	CTS SADC. South African Development Community
Transfer/recognition of grades is authority of home/receiving institution	- To figure a grade-point average (GPA), grade received in each course is weighed, by multiplying it by the number of credit hours.	N/A	Credits that are transferred will not necessarily be granted a mark or grade and may not be included in the calculation of a GPA, unless it forms part of a formal agreement	N/A
How is information circulated between universities?				
- Exchange of transcripts and other forms of descriptors of courses and modules	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
EXTERNAL "ASSISTANCE" TO CTS				
Quality assurance				
N/A	N/A	N/A	Australian Qualification Framework	N/A
Diploma supplement				
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
EVALUATION OF CTS				
Main advantage				
- Weighing of outcomes in different contexts - Credits recognize <i>learning</i> - Improvements in HE as it puts students at the centre of their learning processes. - Liable on competences and achievements of student - Comparability of contents	- HE more accessible to more people and eases comparison of students and HEIs - These units help to evaluate students' entry into HE, and to determine completion of work and degrees	N/A	N/A	N/A
Main disadvantage				
Slow implementation	- Arbitrary use of time to measure educational attainment	N/A	N/A	N/A

Latin-American Reference Credit (CLAR) TUNING	Carnegie Unit and Student Hour	EAUI. East Asian University Institute for Asian Region	The Go8 Credit Transfer Agreement Group of 8 universities (Australia)	CTS SADC. South African Development Community
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No consideration for learning variations among individuals - Concern over distance learning 			

COMPARISON OF CREDIT TRANSFER SYSTEMS (Group 4, continued)

Credit Transfer system The University of Melbourne (UM)	EACTS. EU-ASEAN Credit Transfer System EU-ASEAN (Engineering education)	The Open University (UK)	QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK	CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales
NATURE OF SYSTEM				
Regional scope				
University of Melbourne, Australia (Unilateral system used for reference only)	Universität Duisburg-Essen, Germany; Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia; Universiti, Kebangsaan Malaysia; Università degli Studi di Parma, Italy	University to university (using ECTS as frame)	England based extensible to Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland and countries linked to Bologna Process	Wales in the context of the UK and the Bologna Process
Goals				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Student mobility from and to the university - Allow the transfer of credits to better meet the long term goals of students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU-ASEAN CTS in engineering - Enhance student mobility - Promote Joint Programmes across EU and ASEAN - Enhance mutual understanding - Extended network of HEIs in the field of engineering - Improve curriculum structure - Boost partnership of HEIs 	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality guide (teaching/learning) - safeguard quality standards - drive improvements in UK HE - Reinforce autonomy of awarding HEIs and ensure comparability- Support HEIs to meet and shape students' expectations, ensuring students are involved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allow access to HE - Encourage lifelong learning - Support development of skills achieved through: - Removing barriers to progression - Promoting recognition of skills
PROCEDURE				
Procedure				
- Credit for tertiary studies are granted if studies are comparable in content, in	Credits are transferred in the same level (Ba, Ma, PhD) N/A	Previous studies acceptable but expire over time.	- Through MOUs HEIs determine credit transfer and value of credits as general or specific to a programme	Common principles: - Use of learning outcomes

Credit Transfer system The University of Melbourne (UM)	EACTS. EU-ASEAN Credit Transfer System EU- ASEAN (Engineering education)	The Open University (UK)	QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK	CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales
standard to be included as part of a course - Faculties specify maximum CT allowable		OU regulations require that any studies in OU take place in level 3 or after (post secondary) for the qualification to be completed by studying OU modules. Students responsible of evidence of previous studies Courses may be condoned and compensated	- CT for accumulation depends on relevance to programme - Accumulation allowed for credits from modules, at appropriate levels	- Volume of learning seen as achievements and measured in credits. - Model to underpin all types and styles of learning - Standardized procedures set by CQFW on its website to register qualifications.
How is the information shared among students and universities?				
Applicants find courses and meet requirements. Apply to courses by Central Victorian Tertiary Admissions Centre. If application succeeds students get offer from University to enrol.	HEIs produce their information package - Information circulated to partner HEIs for students and professors to consult and use in planning study agreement.	Previous studies are referred to academic experts in the area of OU qualification to assess matches (case by case) Students who completed studies recorded in ECTS contact the Credit Transfer Centre for advice at OU.	N/A	CQFW sets a minimum unit specification to show learners' learning records and provides tailored careers advice. Standards and protocols for inter-operability with national information systems.
While students are overseas, how are subjects decided?				
Students are eligible for advanced standing with credit from overseas HEIs. - Exchange students have advanced standing arrangements approved by Student Centre	Information package 1) Student's personal data 2) Learning Agreement 3) Transcripts of EACT 4) Official Certification of completed EACTS 5) Study Programme	Learning agreement and analysis of learning experiences	N/A	N/A
How is student workload measured (home or host university)				
Advanced standing granted at discretion of faculty Dean on advice of teachers.	1 EACTS credit is a work hour, not a fraction of the yearly workload (1500-1800h) like the ECTS credit.	OU credit system and ECTS do not compare like with like. ECTS does not consider academic level, hence comparisons are difficult. Yet, at any	- Credits awarded on learning outcome, as students demonstrate achievements by completing work to a minimum standard.	- Credit level shows complexity of learning and autonomy - CQFW has 9 levels to describe post secondary formal and

Credit Transfer system The University of Melbourne (UM)	EACTS. EU-ASEAN Credit Transfer System EU-ASEAN (Engineering education)	The Open University (UK)	QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK	CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales																																																																			
<p>Advanced standing can be awarded for prior studies as complete or incomplete university course. Students are eligible to advanced standing based on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High level additional work at secondary level. - Studies taken in non-award programmes at UM. - Professional experience in graduate programmes. - TAFE (<i>Technical & Further Education</i>) study in an advanced diploma with credit points for Ba degree. HEIs specify pre-approved arrangements for advanced standing with credit points. 	<p>Workload is broken into study plans that specify amount of credit hours per activity. Learning outcomes, competences set for programmes and courses</p> <p>Learning outcomes of EU and ASEAN courses differ in skills gained and in balance theory/application → recognition is negotiated. Comparison of courses for accreditation based on how credits contribute to development of skills</p> <p>Levels EACTS requires consideration of the level (Ba, Ma, PhD) attached to courses. As a rule, credits are transferred among same programme level The comparison must consider learning outcomes and their depth</p>	<p>given level, 60 OU credits are worth 30 ECTS points. Students that complete studies at HE level elsewhere, may transfer accreditation to their OU degree Tables show credits required at each level to achieve an OU qualification</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="907 555 1332 1347"> <thead> <tr> <th>Qualificatio</th> <th>Credit s Level 1</th> <th>Credit s Level 2</th> <th>Credit it vel 3</th> <th>Tota l</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>OU Certificate</td> <td>60</td> <td>-</td> <td>-</td> <td>60</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Certificate of HE</td> <td>120</td> <td>-</td> <td>-</td> <td>120</td> </tr> <tr> <td>OU Diploma</td> <td>120</td> <td>-</td> <td>-</td> <td>120</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Foundation / HE diploma</td> <td>120</td> <td>120</td> <td>-</td> <td>240</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ba degree without honours</td> <td>120</td> <td>120</td> <td>60</td> <td>300</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ba degree with honours</td> <td>120</td> <td>120</td> <td>120</td> <td>360</td> </tr> <tr> <th>Qualification</th> <th colspan="2">Credits post grade</th> <th>Total</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Postgraduate certificate</td> <td colspan="2">60</td> <td>60</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Postgraduate diploma</td> <td colspan="2">120</td> <td>120</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Masters</td> <td colspan="2">180</td> <td>180</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Qualificatio	Credit s Level 1	Credit s Level 2	Credit it vel 3	Tota l	OU Certificate	60	-	-	60	Certificate of HE	120	-	-	120	OU Diploma	120	-	-	120	Foundation / HE diploma	120	120	-	240	Ba degree without honours	120	120	60	300	Ba degree with honours	120	120	120	360	Qualification	Credits post grade		Total	Postgraduate certificate	60		60	Postgraduate diploma	120		120	Masters	180		180	<p>- Exceeding minimum standard does not result in more credits - Credit value = amount of learning (number of credits) and intellectual demand (credit level) - Modules have levels for credits and amounts of learning relate to notional learning hours to estimate amount of learning → credits relate to levels of learning - Eight credit levels are used; of which: levels 4-8 are HE. - Amount of learning shown by credits value is based on notional learning hours. Hours show length needed to achieve learning outcomes of a module. Notional hours of learning include classes, independent study and completion of course-work. In UK, 1 credit = 10 learning hours. - Credit levels reflect depth of learning and the intellectual demand</p>	<p>informal learning (available in progressive frame. See <i>Fan Diagram</i> in Appendix 1) - Learning time measures learning substance of a module relative to time needed to achieve learning outcomes. - Credit Value=learning time/10 hours @ credit level. Modules are delivered joint or independently to combine programmes or qualifications - Credit Common Accord does not prescribe a method to assign credit to qualification units → HEIs use own systems to processes qualifications. - Credits required for degrees:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1836 957 2228 1228"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">Undergraduate</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Certificate</td> <td>120 credits</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Diploma</td> <td>240 credits</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Honourous Degree</td> <td>360 credits</td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2">Postgraduate</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Certificate</td> <td>60 credits</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Diploma</td> <td>120 credits</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Honourous Degree</td> <td>180 credits</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Undergraduate		Certificate	120 credits	Diploma	240 credits	Honourous Degree	360 credits	Postgraduate		Certificate	60 credits	Diploma	120 credits	Honourous Degree	180 credits
Qualificatio	Credit s Level 1	Credit s Level 2	Credit it vel 3	Tota l																																																																			
OU Certificate	60	-	-	60																																																																			
Certificate of HE	120	-	-	120																																																																			
OU Diploma	120	-	-	120																																																																			
Foundation / HE diploma	120	120	-	240																																																																			
Ba degree without honours	120	120	60	300																																																																			
Ba degree with honours	120	120	120	360																																																																			
Qualification	Credits post grade		Total																																																																				
Postgraduate certificate	60		60																																																																				
Postgraduate diploma	120		120																																																																				
Masters	180		180																																																																				
Undergraduate																																																																							
Certificate	120 credits																																																																						
Diploma	240 credits																																																																						
Honourous Degree	360 credits																																																																						
Postgraduate																																																																							
Certificate	60 credits																																																																						
Diploma	120 credits																																																																						
Honourous Degree	180 credits																																																																						
Scale “matching” system																																																																							

Credit Transfer system The University of Melbourne (UM)	EACTS. EU-ASEAN Credit Transfer System EU- ASEAN (Engineering education)	The Open University (UK)	QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK	CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales
Grades transfer for advanced standing based on credit points for student exchange or study abroad programme.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conversion of grades is linear - Statistical grading not used - Within EACTS network, HEIs translate all its passing grades into centesimal EACTS grades. - Workload is qualified upon learning outcomes (competences) - Comparison of grades with other course in UE and ASEAN, is based on how credits contribute to development of key skills. 	Acceptance and recognition of grades from other HEIs is a right of the HEI awarding the degree.	Assessments use schemes that grade performance. Performance above the minimum standard is recognised by higher marks awarded on a scale reflecting levels of achievement in classes: First Class, Upper Second Class, Lower Second Class, Third Class. Rules on assessment are determined by individual HEIs.	Arrangements regarding transfer and recognition of grades are assessed and determined by each HEI
How is information circulated between universities?				
Directly among universities	N/A	N/A	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Unique Learner Number</i> - <i>Regulated General & Vocational Education</i> - <i>Training & Quality Assured Lifelong Learning</i>
EXTERNAL "ASSISTANCE" TO CTS				
Quality assurance				
N/A	- EACTS is itself a QA policy. Further work is needed to develop mutual academic trust.	N/A	Nationally-agreed approach; HEIs use own QA procedures, checked by QAA through audit and review.	HEIs are autonomous but adapt to the <i>Framework for Higher Education Qualifications QA</i>
Diploma supplement				
N/A	N/A	N/A	Accumulated credits in transcript	N/A
EVALUATION OF CTS				
Main advantage				

Credit Transfer system The University of Melbourne (UM)	EACTS. EU-ASEAN Credit Transfer System EU- ASEAN (Engineering education)	The Open University (UK)	QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK	CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales
N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EACTS provides information and services among ECTS & UCTS. - Covers double-degrees - Network open to new members - Flexible and context-sensitive. - Pragmatic <i>step-by-step</i> 	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consistent comparison of learning (independent from context or time) - promotes life-long learning and horizontal mobility among HEIs. - Allows accreditation of prior, informal and non-formal learning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Student-centred and flexible structure to allow tailor-made learning opportunities. - Effective matching of learning, training and employment. - Articulation with HE in Europe
Main disadvantage				
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

4.2.1. Types of credit transfer systems

The comparative chart in the previous section provides insights about common and different features credit systems have and how they work. According to data there credit transfer systems can be classified following different criteria depending on; A. Who sets the system; B. The number of stake holders involved in the transfer flows; C. The historical or geographical linkages that bound the members in the systems; D. The units in charge of making the transfers; and E. The ways in which those transfers are done. The following pages present the classification of the systems included in the sample.

A. Systems classified by *who set the systems*, refer to actors involved at the time of setting and implementing principles and rules contained therein. Systems may be set by:

1. Governments: typically within national frameworks that are applied domestically.
2. HEIs: universities and other institutions set networks and apply transfer rules both domestic and internationally.
3. Governments and HEIs jointly: these are integrative efforts that bring together different stakeholders toward a common set of rules applied domestic and internationally.
4. Autonomous HEI that connect themselves to networks and other HEIs. Systems here work similar to bilateral agreements but with standard procedures, typically for incoming transfers.
5. Independent/private organizations that connect students to HEIs as *free movers*, usually working as for profit organizations facilitating academic exchange experiences.

Table 4: Credit transfer systems according to who set them

CTS type by who sets system	Credit transfer system in the sample
1. Set by/among governments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AeU / ACTS - ASEM. Asia Europe Meeting - Credit Accumulation and Transfer System East African Countries - Arab Space for Higher Education - Carnegie Unit and Student Hour - CTS SADC. South African Development Community - QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK - CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales
2. Set by/among HEIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AUN / ACTS - Association of African Universities - Latin-American Reference Credit (CLAR) TUNING - EAUI. East Asian University Institute for Asian Region - The Go8 Credit Transfer Agreement - EACTS. EU-ASEAN CTS (Engineering education)
3. Set jointly by governments and HEIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECTS - UMAP / UCTS - CAMPUS Asia
4. Autonomous HEI open to networks and other HEIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Open University (UK) - The University of Melbourne (UM)

5. Independent/ private organization	- AE – ECTS. Asia Exchange
--------------------------------------	----------------------------

B. Systems classified according to *number of stakeholders involved in the transfer flow* consider *poles* participating in flows and *directions* of those flows (from where / to where) of information for recognition. Flows of transfers can happen at government or HEIs levels and they can be *unidirectional*, *bidirectional* and *multidirectional*.

1. Unilateral CTS set by a country: typically set in national frameworks and applied domestically as a country unilaterally opens to accept accreditations from others.
2. Unilateral CTS set by HEIs: a HEI sets rules for inward or outward transfers of credits with other institutions, applied domestic and internationally.
3. Bilateral CTS by countries: Two countries agree to mutually recognize the qualifications HEIs in their territories grant.
4. Bilateral CTS by HEIs: Two HEIs agree to mutually recognize their qualifications. This is the most usual form of cooperation and exchange.
5. Multilateral CTS by countries: Three or more countries agree to mutually recognize the qualifications granted by HEIs in their territories, E.g. as set in Regional Conventions on Recognition of Academic Qualifications within the umbrella of UNESCO.
6. Multilateral CTS by HEIs. Three or more HEIs agree to mutually recognize their qualifications.

Table 5: Credit transfer systems according to number of stakeholders involved in the flow

CTS Type by number of stakeholders involved in the transfer flows	Credit transfer system in the sample
1. Unilateral CTS set by a country	- QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK - CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales
2. Unilateral CTS set by HEIs	- The University of Melbourne (UM) - The Open University (UK)
3. Bilateral CTS by countries	- No systems of this kind were found in the sample, however representative examples may include cases like China, who has signed agreements on mutual recognition of studies, diplomas and degrees with 34 countries (The ASEM education secretariat, n.d.)
4. Bilateral CTS by HEIs	- AE – ECTS. Asia Exchange - Carnegie Unit and Student Hour
5. Multilateral CTS by countries	- AeU / ACTS - ASEM. Asia Europe Meeting - Credit Accumulation and Transfer System East Africa - Arab Space for Higher Education - CTS SADC. South African Development Community CTS
6. Multilateral CTS by HEIs	- ECTS - UMAP / UCTS

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AUN / ACTS - CAMPUS Asia - Association of African Universities - Latin-American Reference Credit (CLAR) TUNING - EAUI. East Asian University Institute for Asian Region - The Go8 Credit Transfer Agreement - EACTS. EU-ASEAN CTS (Engineering education)
--	---

C. Credit transfer systems can be classified by *historic linkages* or *geographic vicinity* as *agglutinating* factors. These groupings can fall into the categories of:

1. Common history and similar educational traditions, typically including countries with common colonial systems that inherit similar educational systems.
2. Language based systems, similar to the one above; these systems are set based on shared history or common colonial pasts but language plays a major role as the agglutinating factor.
3. Geographical vicinity, where countries create credit transfer schemes and other forms of mutual recognition based physical proximity.
4. A rather new category emerging here relates to newer forms of agreements that aim to connect inter-continental or inter-regional partners through credit transfer schemes.

Table 6: Credit transfer systems according to historic linkages or geographic vicinity

CTS Type by historical linkages or geographical vicinity	Credit transfer system in the sample
1. Common history and similar educational traditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Credit Accumulation and Transfer System East Africa - Latin-American Reference Credit (CLAR) TUNING - Carnegie Unit and Student Hour - The Go8 Credit Transfer Agreement - QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK - CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales
2. Language based systems	- Association of African Universities organized as Francophone and Anglophone groupings
3. Geographical vicinity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECTS - UMAP / UCTS - AUN / ACTS - AeU / ACTS - CAMPUS Asia - Arab Space for Higher Education - EAUI. East Asian University Institute for Asian Region - CTS SADC. South African Development Community CTS
4. Intercontinental approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ASEM, Asia Europe Meeting - AE – ECTS. Asia Exchange - EACTS. EU-ASEAN CTS (Engineering education) - The Open University (UK)

D. According to *who is the unit in charge of implementing the systems* and making most relevant decisions, credit transfer systems can be classified in the following categories:

1. HEIs directly in charge of implementing the rules for transfer contained in the systems. HEIs account with enough autonomy to decide on application and recognition of credits and grades.
2. Implemented by public agencies; where decisions on recognition are treated as official matters relevant to respective agencies and of mandatory acceptance for HEIs.
3. Mix implementation by HEIs with support from public officers, typically seen in cases where quality assurance agencies have a say (may not be final) regarding the evaluation of the worth of credits requested for recognition by the students.
4. Implemented by other forms of organizations such as charities, NGOs or private companies. Here, independent organizations agree with HEIs for them to recognize the credits (and sometimes grades) students obtained from participating in a privately organized exchange programmes.

Table 7: Credit transfer systems according to implementation unit

CTS Type by implementation unit	Credit transfer system in the sample
1. HEIs are directly in charge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UMAP / UCTS - AeU / ACTS - AUN / ACTS - CAMPUS Asia - ASEM. Asia Europe Meeting - Association of African Universities - Latin-American Reference Credit (CLAR) TUNING - Carnegie Unit and Student Hour - EAUI. East Asian University Institute for Asian Region - The Go8 Credit Transfer Agreement - The University of Melbourne (UM) - EACTS. EU-ASEAN CTS (Engineering education) - The Open University (UK)
2. Implemented by public agencies	- No systems in the sample fall in this categories, however examples can be found in the national credit systems of countries like Vietnam or Myanmar, where government agencies have the final say in recognition or not of credits and grades (From country reports in Chapter 5 of this research)
3. Implemented by HEIs with support from QA agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECTS (with possible support from ENIC centres) - QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK - CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales
4. Implemented by other forms of organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AE – ECTS. - Asia Exchange
5. Not yet operational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AeU / ACTS - Credit Accumulation and Transfer System East African Countries

- | | |
|--|--|
| | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Arab Space for Higher Education - CTS SADC. South African Development Community CTS |
|--|--|

Here concludes the overview of *kinds of credit transfer systems*; the following sections present the transversal analysis of features in the systems of the sample to spot practical commonalities and differences among them.

4.2.2. Credit Transfer Systems Goals

The transversal comparison of systems regarding the goals they seek attain shows that although with small differences they all are set towards: 1) Harmonization of HE; 2) promotion of quality in education and trustable assuring mechanisms; 3) curricular development; 4) mobility and international integration; 5) employability of graduates; 6) share of information; and 7) promoting attractiveness of HEIs. The following paragraphs provide more details about each point.

4.2.2.1. Harmonization

All credit transfer systems analyzed seek to create channels to facilitate understanding on academic issues and easing the flow of information about students' workloads and achievements. In so doing credit transfer systems attempt to:

- Make HEIs more permeable by developing closer ties among HEIs and countries and boosting smoother procedures for recognition of qualifications from other institutions.
- Bridge local, regional and global education systems by creating a shared language that is understandable for all.
- Make HE systems more transparent in terms of curricula, academic periods and teaching/learning methodologies aiming to facilitate integration at the three levels (bachelor, master and doctorate) and to better articulate them, both horizontal and vertically.
- Improve curricular structure, admission and assessment criteria by increasing exposure to different systems and by practicing openness.
- Create more inclusive societies where more people can have access to HE by means of 1) facilitating wider access to traditional and alternative forms of education; 2) removing barriers to progression; and 3) easing access to different ways to develop or maintain skills.
- Reinforce autonomy of HEIs to boost responsibility and ownership.
- Promote *recognition of skills* required to support economic growth looking at wider regional pictures, by overcoming traditional nation-wide scopes of education and the value attached to qualifications by offering to learners of different ages and backgrounds parity in recognition of learning achievements.
- Promote joint developments in study programmes and research by enhance temporary mobility and double and joint programmes and degrees.

4.2.2.2. Quality assurance

All systems in the sample show that, although indirectly, by promoting exposure to other systems and programmes they facilitate comparison and call for improvement and the creation of agreed standards; thus the implementation of credit transfer systems tends to:

- Foster mutual trust among HEIs that wish to ease mutual recognition of the qualifications they issue. To do it these institutions tend to apply quality assurance systems by making study programmes more comparable as a result from increased exposure and confrontation to different curricula.
- Boost international and interregional cooperation in quality assurance as HEIs seek to deepen the relations with other educational systems and institutions.

4.2.2.3. Curricula development

All systems analyzed claim to promote exposure of HEIs and educational systems, which promotes more diverse learning opportunities to individuals and institutional development of the HEIs, which leads to:

- Students having new and more learning options based on increased availability of study programmes/courses.
- Lifelong learning by developing mechanisms that facilitate the recognition of previously obtained qualifications (prior learning).
- More fluid transfer and share of information among HEIs, which stimulate curricular reforms, advancement and updating of study programmes.
- Changes in curricular paradigms that welcome multidisciplinary frameworks and overcome traditionally narrower institutional or national approaches.
- Improving specific skills among students such as language proficiency, professional skills or boost joint research interests.
- Promote curricular reform based on the development of competences and skills rather than simply based on the transfer of academic contents.

4.2.2.4. Mobility and international integration

Credit transfer systems facilitate cooperation in academic fields firstly; however they are conceived within wider contexts of cooperation to further support social, economic and political integration; as such credit transfer systems trigger further cooperation in a domino effect that materializes in ways that go beyond education itself; which happens because:

- Academic credit transferability generates changes in the attitudes of learners and administrators by making them aware of broader pictures beyond traditional national scopes of knowledge and skills into more globally integrated labour markets.
- International academic transferability develops human resources that are culturally sensitive and that see differences as a source of potentials; which in turn prepares learners to face global challenges and expand working opportunities regardless of their backgrounds and locations of origin.
- Develop know-how and skills to contribute to the realization of national, regional and global interests based on *glocal education* that better colligates the contribution HE systems to their communities and productive systems.
- Multilateral systems re-direct traditional trends of the directions of academic flows; they tend to modify usual flows directed to either more developed countries or main international language speaking countries such as English or French toward alternative destinations and countries. This is evident among the systems in the sample in the Asian context that actively promote a change from typically directed flows to Western Europe, North America, Japan, Singapore and Australia toward destinations *within* the region. The

credit transfer systems in AUN' ACTS, Campus Asia, EAUI East Asian University Institute stand as the most clear examples of this for the region; while the Latin American and African experiences do the same in their respective areas.

- Improve channels for networking and to develop friendship across borders among students, HEIs and governments.
- Boost innovation and deepen a sense of socially responsible citizens nurtured in systems functioning as incubators of economic, political and cultural understanding.

4.2.2.5. Employability of graduates

Transferability of credits relates to current migration trends in a mutually reinforcing loop, labour related mobility boosts educational mobility, which in turn facilitates dynamism in the labour market. Within this context, the *systematization of transferability* seeks to develop more accurate and easily applicable ways to link study programmes and employability of graduates in relation to social and economic needs and personal expectations. In other words, creating sound bridges between provision of education (in whatever its form) and access to productive and fulfilling employment.

4.2.2.6. Information share

All credit transfer systems in the sample share the goal of smoothening the flow and interpretation of information related to study programmes and achievements of learners, as such these systems aim to:

- Improve the quality and amount of information exchanged to democratize access to it.
- Enhance public awareness and access to educational options and quality of programmes.
- Advance knowledge in the management of HE as a whole by means of comparison and exposure.
- Provide evidence based advice and guidance to HEIs for them to award degrees that meet national, social and labour needs and expectations.

4.2.2.7. Attractiveness & visibility

All credit transfer systems analyzed seek to boost the attractiveness of the services provided by participating institutions in order to direct (or re-direct) the flows of students towards them. In so doing systems seek to:

- Increase visibility of HEIs, within and outside their geographical and thematic areas.
- Render regions more attractive in terms of educational hubs in specific fields.
- Create regional or thematic brands.
- Improve the relation of value for the money of study programmes.

This concludes the comparative analysis of *goals sought by credit transfer systems*; the following pages present the analysis of technical features of the different systems.

4.2.3. Credit transfer systems' technicalities in perspective

The comparison of technical features of credit transfer systems resulted in a number of commonalities and differences that were classified as generic and intrinsic aspects.

4.2.3.1. Generic technical features

4.2.3.1.1. Commonalities

All systems in the sample share technical aspects that refer to:

1. The use of *credits units* to describe workload and learning achievements
2. Credits are used to facilitate the recognition of courses or programmes
3. Mechanisms to promote mobility and harmonization
4. Mechanisms to increase awareness on diversity
5. Mechanisms to increase curricula transparency
6. Mechanisms to promote quality assurance
7. Strategies to move from bilateral to multilateral

1. The use *credits units* to describe workload and learning achievements

In all cases analysed the use of credits as units to measure students' workload appears as an *undisputable rule*, based on the agreement that attaching a number of credits to the students' workload facilitates comparison. Similar to other measuring systems such as the Metric System or the use of Imperial Customary Units the growing acceptance of credits to measure academic efforts and outcomes appears to be a consolidating trend. Important differences appear here however.

There are systems that present exact definitions and strict rules for measurement of credits (usually linked to the notion of workload time) like in ECTS, UCTS (for programmes A and B), AUN's ACTS and the Carnegie System.

However and interestingly not all multilateral systems require credit units to transfer workloads and learning achievements; these systems use "softer" definitions of what credits are. Examples of this relate to recognition of:

- 1) *Subjects for subjects* (regardless of number of credits) as in the systems in Latin American Reference Credit (CLAR-Tuning), EAUI East Asian University Institute and Open University.
- 2) *Internships for subjects*, like in the systems of AeU/ACTS, Credit Accumulation and Transfer in Eastern Africa, the Carnegie system and in the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales.
- 3) *Subjects in specific fields*, like language or cultural studies, as in the case of UMAP's programme C (UMAP, 2011) and in system proposed by AE-ECTS Asia Exchange.

2. Credits are used to facilitate the recognition of courses or programmes

All credit transfer systems analysed seek to facilitate recognition of workloads and learning achievements of students in HEIs within their networks. In all cases this applies to both temporary exchange programmes and permanent moves of students to a new HEI.

Likewise all systems promote recognition of credits in horizontal mobility of students (in the same cycle: undergraduate-to-undergraduate and postgraduate-to-postgraduate programmes). An important difference noted here is that only a few systems promote the use of credits for vertical mobility (from bachelor to master, and from masters to doctorate programmes). In our sample this happens -in principle- in ECTS, AeU/ACTS, Go8 Credit transfer Agreement, Credit transfer system at the University of Melbourne, Open University, Quality Assurance Agency UK and Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales. (The rest of the systems in the sample either explicitly assert they are meant for horizontal mobility or do not mention the idea of vertical mobility).

3. Mechanisms to promote mobility and harmonization

All systems analyzed work associated with the promotion of student mobility, related to cultural exchange as a strategy for regional integration and development; where all involved stakeholders progressively work to create more common grounds for HE by making educational systems come closer in structure, format and content.

However important differences were found among the systems related to the kind of stakeholder participating and the sort of support provided to each of them by the governments and HEIs. The issue relates to the observations presented above in point 4.2.1 regarding who sets the systems and the number of stakeholders involved; and due to the amount of specific nuances found for each case the topic is further developed in the next section: 4.2.3.1.2. Differences.

4. Mechanisms to increase awareness on diversity

A common aspect all systems in the sample share is the fact that although academic purposes of student mobility is a major goal, in all cases cultural appreciation and building of new “regional identities” appears among the driving motivations behind the systems.

In all cases elements like internationalization, regional integration, development of global human resources and international competitiveness appear among the reason used to promote the systems.

5. Mechanisms to increase curricula transparency

A side effect of increased student mobility is that HEIs participating in credit transfer schemes show more open attitudes in sharing and making information available on their programmes to students and partner HEIs. In all cases in the sample this responds to HEIs’ need to understand what students do while they study in different HEIs or programmes, be them temporary or permanent, while at the same time keeping themselves up-to-date in the services they offer.

By definition, all multilateral credit systems require teachers and personnel at HEIs to understand what other institutions teach and how they do it; which is bringing along a growing level of awareness on the need to make institutional information more widely and easily accessible.

6. Mechanisms to promote quality assurance

Although quality assurance responds to different principles and works on different rules to facilitate comparability of programmes, the analysis of the credit transfer systems in the sample show that they all overlap in their aim of promoting academic correlations.

This research demonstrates that credit transfer systems tend to develop hand-in-hand with quality assurance frameworks. Showing that even if they are different schemes they share some goals and as such they tend to mutually support and boost each other.

7. Strategies to move from bilateral to multilateral

Although a purposive sample was used for this research focusing on multilateral systems and only two unilateral credit transfer systems were included as reference (The Open University in the UK and the Credit transfer system at the University of Melbourne in Australia). Data in the sample evidences a growing tendency towards the implementation of multilateral agreements, including wider number of both countries and HEIs.

The trend can even be seen as complete regions are being connected by these models, in our sample cases like ASEM Asia Europe Meeting, AE-ECTS Asia Exchange, the Latin American Reference Credit (CLAR), and the EACTS EU-ASEAN student mobility and joint-Award degree in Engineering Education clearly demonstrate this.

The analysis of members participating in each of the multilateral systems included here reveal that multilateral approach to credit transfer reduces duplication of efforts in the process of recognition; while it increases networking potentials and it expands the frontiers of mutual understanding among HEIs and governments.

4.2.3.1.2. Differences

Multilateral credit transfer systems present general variations in their natures and functions, which respond to the different needs they are aimed to address and the will of those creating them. They differ from each other in at least the following aspects:

1. Scope and regional extension
2. Levels of involvement from different stakeholders
3. National definitions of HE cycles (bachelor, master, doctorate)
4. Ways to measure workload (time, outcomes)
5. Rules regarding recognition of other forms of workload
6. level of integration and involvement of partners in the system

1. Scope and regional extension

Multilateral systems in the sample reflect the fact that they normally have a geographical connection to the areas where they are set and that they are normally related to other forms of integration (trade, financial, economic, political, cultural, etc).

Regional integration and harmonization of education systems reinforce each other because regionalization offers more fertile soil for student mobility which in turn calls for the development of effective mechanisms to transfer and recognize academic qualifications.

Clear geographical connections of the credit systems in the sample are observed in advanced process of integration in the cases of ECTS that relates but overflows the context of the European Union; AUN' ACTS connects universities within the context of ASEAN; while Credit Accumulation and Transfer System in East Africa and The CTS SADC (South African Development Community) do it for their respective regional blocks.

Other systems are set on a geographical link by they are more independent from political or economic processes of integration, for instance Campus Asia and EAUI East Asia University Institute, both of which connect HEIs in East Asia; UMAP' UCTS that connects HEIs in Asia and the Pacific; AeU /ACTS that connects 30 countries in Asia; the Latin American Credit of Reference (CLAR) that linkages universities in among countries in the region; the Association of African Universities that connects HEIs in that continent and the Arab Space for HE that plans to eventually connect HEIs in the Maghreb region.

2. Levels of involvement of different stakeholders

A mayor difference observed among systems in the sample is the type of stakeholders participating and their level of involvement regarding recognition decisions.

For instance, there are differences in the level of autonomy that governments grant to HEIs on recognition and accreditation of qualifications when those HEIS are members of

international networks. (This relates to the fact that multilateral credit transfer systems overlap with national credit systems and they may work on different principles).

In all the cases analyzed in the sample, systems are functioning in countries where governments allow HEIs enough autonomy to decide whether they recognize or not qualifications from other HEIs, however cases like Vietnam and Myanmar present some obstacles to the logic of the multilateral systems, e.g. the participation of both countries in the credit transfer initiatives within UMAP or the AIMS programme.

Matters of this sort are political in nature and will require political decisions to be solved as they relate to the level of openness and commitment to harmonization of the governments where the multilateral systems function.

Thus, some countries show more proactive attitudes by making reforms in their systems so as to bring those system more in line with international standards; while other countries are more open to accept international agreements as their own law, making those regulations valid in their territories sometimes working even hierarchically as superior to their own national laws. E.g. the implementation of the Lisbon Recognition Convention among European countries; where countries ratifying the convention accept the norms contained there as their own national law.

In general lines the analysis of the systems in the sample show different levels of commitment from the stakeholders involved. In the case of the governments, for instance, and depending on their interests, they provide different volumes and types of support to the credit transfer systems; which can be observed through:

- a) *Political support*, for example by promoting one system or another.
- b) *Legal support* by promoting necessary legal reforms in their educational systems to allow for the systems to work more smoothly and by allowing larger autonomy to HEIs regarding mobility issues;
- b) *Operational support*, for instance by providing facilities, infrastructure and personnel for the administration and implementation of the systems;
- c) *Financial support*, by making scholarships for mobility available.

On the other side of the same coin HEIs feel more attracted to use one or other system according to how they respond to their needs and how they perceive the partner HEIs with who they interact in the context of each system.

3. National definitions of HE cycles (bachelor, master, doctorate)

Among the challenges multilateral credit transfer systems face are the differences in terms of how countries delineate educational cycles (what degrees like bachelors, diplomas, masters or doctorate mean and include therein). This is a common problem to all systems that relates to what should the connection be in terms of transferability in interlocking levels of the degrees.

Credit transfer systems face challenges when dealing with horizontal and vertical mobility of students, as the personnel utilizing the systems may feel “forced” to understand and use information in ways that are decoded differently in different settings.

The issue remains an obstacle to credit transfer systems specially in regards to vertical mobility because while some education systems at the country and HEI level recognize and promote accumulation of credits as a facilitator towards higher levels of formal education

(lifelong learning); other systems are constrained because governments and HEIs perceive accumulation as foreign or even dysfunctional to their systems, for example in some countries vertical mobility heavily relies on entrance exams (which are used as a strategy to limit access) rather than on recognizing previous learning.

None of the credit transfer systems analysed for Asia explicitly touches on the accumulation issue, while typically reinforcing the idea of *recognition of degrees* rather than recognitions of credits when students advance from bachelor to masters or from masters to doctorates.

The way multilateral credit transfer systems deal with this reflects the logics and interests of countries and HEIs using them, as some see lifelong learning a natural course of life where what a person learns can be expanded and applied in a *continuous* manner. Systems that allow for accumulation tend to be more student-centred; as they consider and legitimize prior learning toward acquisition of higher levels of formal education.

The systems in the sample showed that systems (and countries) that refute accumulation of credits tend to be more *institutionally-centred*, meaning that learning experiences are more constrained by rules set by HEIs and governments rather than the learners' own interests.

Among the systems analyzed in the sample, a few of them explicitly promote and regulate accumulation of credits toward progression of formal studies into higher cycles; these are ECTS where the issue of accreditation of PhD programmes is still under debate, AeU/ACTS, Credit Accumulation & Transfer System East Africa, Credit Transfer System in Melbourne University, Quality Assurance Agency UK and Credit & Qualifications Framework for Wales.

4. Measurements of workload (time, learning outcomes)

Another area that poses challenges to multilateral credit transfer systems is how HEIs deal with the measurement of students' workloads and what their credits mean.

As explained, two traditions exist in this regard; one associated with measuring students' workload based on the *time required to achieve learning goals* set by a course or programme, and the other based on the *learning outcomes* obtained upon completion of a course, where time is considered as *one among various* indicators for measurement, not as the main one. How credit transfer systems resolve and manage the issue of workload measurement greatly determines how they work and are implemented at the grass-root level among HEIs.

These traditions of thought relate to teaching methods used and the relative role given to the students in the learning process; where *the more student-centred the programmes are the more credit transfer systems are associated with measuring workload by learning outcomes*; while conversely *where the role of teachers is more central to the learning process, the more credit transfer systems use contact hours to determine workload*.

Whether one approach or the other is more efficient and fairer is a judgement based on values that needs to be agreed among those HEIs applying one or other measurement and transfer system. This is a rather political issue that, even if crucial, for the future of credit transfer systems at this point it falls out of the scope of this study.

Systems in the sample fall into one or another tradition and can be classified as more *time-based workload oriented* like in the cases of UMAP's UCTS, AUN's ACTS and Carnegie System that greatly rely on the concept of contact hours to determine the value of the credits; as opposed to systems that even if including the notion of time and contact hours, focus more on achievements and outcomes from the learning process as it happens in the credit transfer system of ECTS, AeU/ACTS, Campus Asia, ASEM Asia Europe Meeting, AE-ECTS Asia Exchange,

The Latin American Reference Credit (CLAR), EAUI East Asia University Institute, Go8, EU-ASEAN Student mobility and joint Award Degree on Engineering Education, Open University, the University of Melbourne, the Quality Assurance Agency of the UK and the Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales.

5. Recognition of other forms of workload

A few systems in the sample accept and even promote the recognition of alternative forms of students' workloads as academically worth accreditation. These systems recognize that different forms of learning experiences can be measured in credits; however other systems do not consider the issue at all.

A typical case is that of students who take temporary leaves from regular academic study programmes to participate in internships, voluntary activities or other forms of learning or practical experiences (as opposed to theoretic classes).

Among the systems analyzed, only a few explicitly set forward that all learning outcomes can be "translated" into credits if they account with a clear learning process and description of learning strategies and outcomes. More "conservative" systems remain closer to the idea that academic credits should be granted *solely* to learning processes from formal and institutionalized learning experiences.

Similarly, there exist contrasting views regarding credit transferability of research work and other forms of workload should research be measurable and transferable.

Although to a great extent the decision to recognize or not these experiences belongs to the HEIs credit transfer systems like ECTS; UMAP's UCTS; AeU/ACTS, Credit Accumulation and Transfer System in Eastern Africa, Carnegie System, the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales actively promote the idea of recognizing those experiences towards more institutionalized forms of accreditation.

6. Level of integration and involvement of partners in the system

The use of multilateral credit systems in countries and HEIs correlates with the profiles they aim to provide to their graduates, which in all cases means looking at *internationalization of HE* as an intermediate goal towards greater regional integration.

The analysis of systems in the sample shows clear differences in regards to the level of integration or depth of the mutual commitments of the partners in the arrangements. Some systems provide good examples of how political and institutional will drive harmonization into more integrated areas; the best example is the Bologna Process that progressively has involved both governments and HEIs in a process of building a more transparent, permeable and mutually understandable regional system.

Although ECTS still has a way to go towards more integration of HE systems in Europe, as a referral it has set a practical example of how *differences within* can be managed and how a common will can be constructed through a democratic and inclusive process.

Multilateral credit systems Asia show variations as some have clearly moved into more integrated goals and procedures, while others still remain in the stage of defining features, goals and procedures. Some are already being used by HEIs and continue to consolidate while others remain theoretical frameworks with low level of applicability given factors like lack of support from governments or poor awareness from HE officials, professors and students.

Systems in the sample that show the highest level of integration with involvement and support from governments and actual use by HEIs include ECTS, UMAP' ECTS, Campus Asia,

the Latin American Reference Credit (CLAR), the Go8, the Quality Assurance Agency in the UN and the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales.

Systems that account with strong support from the HEIs that use them, but with somewhat less support from governments (because they are set as university networks) include cases like AUN' ACTS, AE-ECTS Asia Exchange, Association of African Universities, the Carnegie System, the EAUI East Asia University Institute, the Credit transfer system at the University of Melbourne, the EACTS EU-ASEAN credit transfer system for mobility of students in Engineering Education and the Open University.

Other systems account with support from the governments promoting the groupings, mainly as political associations showing intention to deepen regional cooperation, but that have yet to be accepted and use by the HEIs at the grass-root level. Systems in this category include the cases of AeU/ACTS, ASEM Asia Europe Meeting, Credit Accumulation and Transfer System in East Africa, the Arab Space for HE and the credit transfer system in the South African Development Community.

4.2.3.2. Intrinsic features

The following pages present core aspects of the study as they portray the “hearts” of multilateral credit transfer systems by analysing the technical aspects upon which they function; basically on three areas: 1) Recognition of qualifications; 2) measurement of students' workloads; and 3) treatment of students' grades.

The comparison is based on the contrast of the features of each system in the sample following the categories of analysis set in the individual credit transfer system chart. (For more details each charter see annex 1 Individual Credit Transfer System Chart).

The categories used refer to: procedures; ways in which information is shared among members of the systems, ways in which students and high education institutions decide on the subjects students take while on exchange, how HEIs participating in each system measure students' workload, how they match scales in terms of workload and grades, how credit transfer systems relate to other mechanisms such as quality assurance and the share of information packages or diploma supplements and finally making a description of advantages and disadvantages of each system.

4.2.3.2.1. Transfer procedures

This section focuses on the ways credit transfer systems function, how the information is circulated among institutions and what minimum requirements for validation of are when students transfer from a HEI to another.

The analysis of the systems in the sample showed both similarities and difference on how their rules and practices affect the mobility of students.

Among the **SIMILARITIES** observed in all the systems worth noting are the following:

1. Extra credits for extra academic workload
2. Agreed and standardized procedures
3. The use of time as a parameter
4. Modularization of study courses
5. Standardization of communication

1. Extra credits for extra academic workload

Although typical standards in the number of courses a student can realistically take in an academic period, all systems in the sample suggest that students may obtain larger amounts of credits when they engage in more academic activities that yield credits; which allows students to move faster towards graduation by inputting extra working load in a typically shorter period of time. Likewise all systems acknowledge that extraordinary lengthy study courses and programmes typically grant larger amounts of credits.

All multilateral systems analyzed assert aiming to be student-centred mechanisms that systematically address the needs and expectations of the students. Credit transfer systems by definition seek to facilitate the students' progression in their careers as they move around HEIs, as such systems' *raison d'être* is seeking for ways to facilitate the accomplishment of learning goals of the students when they are faced to mobility issues.

While all systems acknowledge that they do not, by nature of their use, guaranty the recognition of qualifications (in all cases final decisions rely on the receiving institution).

2. Agreed and standardized procedures

Multilateral systems work based on the assumption that they facilitate procedures by advancing and encouraging the use of standard procedures for mobility; where the role of HEIs includes *evaluating* and *interpreting* the work of other institutions. I.e., when students return to home universities international relations officers and academic personnel are the ones in charge of interpreting the assessments other HEIs did of the students.

In all cases analyzed the notion of *equivalence between subjects* to be recognized (similarities in content) is among the most frequently mentioned principles for recognition. However subjects or courses may also be taken as *alternative* or *complementary* and hence be accepted as optional subjects, when allowed.

Transferability of credits relies on mutual trust and comparability of study programmes among HEIs; hence the importance attached to curricular transparency HEIs expect from other HEIs. All transfer systems seek to create flexible procedures so as to *smoothen* differences when curricula and content are compared so as to ease their understanding by professors and international relations officers.

In all systems analyzed the acceptance of transfer of credits is based in previous agreements that normally determine whether the recognition will be in full or partial and give the HEIs the right to request students for further works in case gaps exist.

Transferability of credits is by rule is applied to qualifications that have obtained passing marks or above.

3. The use of time as a parameter

All systems in the sample relay on the use of time as a unit for measurement of students' workload and from there to the amount of credits attached to a study course. However systems give different relevance to it, where for example UMAP's UCTS and the Carnegie System work on the notion of time almost entirely in the valuation of courses in terms of credits attached. (In the following section a detailed explanation of differences is provided).

4. Modularization of study courses

Although not explicitly put as a mandatory issue by the credit transfer systems to the HEIs using them, through the analysis of the data it could be noticed that the implementation of multilateral credit systems fosters modularization of study programmes since it facilitates

comparability and allows flexibility *within* programmes in their contents, structures and passage through; and promote interconnectivity among different programmes and HEIs.

5. Standardization of communication

All credit transfer systems analyzed rely on the use of academic transcripts as information exchange tools because these documents ease the transfer of information and mutual understanding of students' workloads and attainments.

In the case of credit transfer systems used for student exchange programmes, they all advocate for the use of *learning agreements* prior to departure of the student to exchange programmes; which works as practical "contracts" where students, teachers and HEIs agree on what subjects the student should take while on exchange.

All systems in the sample request HEIs to produce and use information packages or programme catalogues to share of information and to disclose academic details, contents and methods to students and partner HEIs.

Among the **DIFFERENCES** in procedures used by the systems it should be noted that:

1. Definitions of workload
2. Transferability of credits
3. Use of external units to assist in accreditation like QA agencies
4. Management of documentary information
5. Systems: *conventions* or *conversion tools*
6. Multilateral credit transfer systems as currency exchange markets
7. Maximum transferable credits

1. Definitions of workload

Transfer and recognition procedures are greatly determined by the way each system defines *workload* and how they attach *ideal* amounts of credits to study courses and programmes and other forms of learning experiences.

The diversity of procedures observed among the systems in the sample greatly confirms this and can be seen for example in how different systems give different relative values to the credits according to levels/cycles where they are granted (bachelor, master, doctorate); and they used different lengths of academic periods as base for measurement of the value of the courses; all of which affects the worth or weight of the credits making comparisons and transfer more difficult. (An extended analysis of the problem of definition of workload is presented in the following section)

2. Transferability of credits

Transferability of academic credits among HEIs varies when considering *moves within same* HEIs to different study programmes. And when moves happen *among* different institutions to same, similar or completely different study programmes. Thus, while HEIs may choose to use their own credit systems for moves within their own structures, they may as well choose to use mechanisms set by multilateral systems, as it happens in the cases of ECTS, UMAP's UCTS, AUN's ACTS, AE ECTS Asia Exchange, the Latin American Credit Reference (CLAR), the Carnegie system and the Go8.

Alternative systems set different levels or amounts of transferable credits, for example by establishing quotas, maximums or minimums. Although the decision of how many credits a HEI will accept to recognize remains a right of the HEI issuing the degree in all systems analyzed, some of them set maximums standards of transferable credits for the case of

movements based on temporary exchanges. Cases showing this particularity are AeU/ACTS that allows a maximum of up to 30% of the total credits needed for graduation; AUN's ACTS that allows for exchanges based on one or two semesters only, and Go8 that sets a minimum of a year of study or 50% of relevant study at the HEI granting the degree.

Some systems specify periods of time and expire periods for transferability. E.g. credits are only transferable within six months from the moment they were granted, credits are valid during 5 years and then expire, credits may be accounted for and validated only if obtained after *year such and such*, etc. In our sample, this is explicitly stated in the cases of the AeU/ACTS, Open University, Quality Assurance Agency of the UK and the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales.

1. **3. Use of external units to assist in accreditation like QA agencies**

Some systems recommend setting external units (like quality assurance agents) to analyse and encourage shared curricular developments to make education systems come closer, by setting agreed basic standards as it happens in ECTS in relation to ENIC-NARIC centres, the Go8 and the Australian Qualification Framework, the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales. While in the Asian context UMAP's UCETS and AUN's ACTS refer to the need to further consolidate a regional quality assurance system based on a network of national quality assurance frameworks.

4. Management of documentary information

Systems show discrepancies about management of documentary evidence, e.g., kinds and amounts of details in the information required so as to be shared; who should issue that information, through what channels, in what formats, etc. In this sense, systems like UMAP's UCTS, AUN's ACTS, the Go8, the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales offer good examples of centralized mechanisms for the management of information both at the HEIs and students levels.

5. Systems: *conventions* or *conversion tools*

Credit transfer systems are meant to make individual credit systems (at the HEIs or at the countries) compatible by comparing students' workloads and attainments, to do it some systems work as *conventions* and others as tools for *conversion*.

Convention meaning that HEIs participating in the scheme agree to measure workloads under the same rules; while *Conversion* implies that HEIs continue to use their own accreditation systems and utilize an "external" mechanism to *translate* the workload and the credits attached to it from a HEI into another.

In the sample systems using *conventions* include: ECTS, AUN'S ACTS, the Carnegie system, the Go8, the Credit Transfer System at University of Melbourne, the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales as each of them sets ways to measure workloads upon which credits are granted to the students who successfully finish a given course.

In ECTS, for instance, HEIs and governments agree that 60 credits represent a typical full-time academic year; therefore HEIs produce study courses structured in programmes that accommodate to this based on a modular configuration of courses to allow direct transfer and recognition. In quite the same way HEIs using the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales, agree in the definition of learning time as related to the hours students need to achieve a given learning outcome, including all academic activities, hence transferability is automatic.

Similar examples are set by AUN’s ACTS or the Go8, where HEIs agree to accept credits from partner HEIs “as they are”. Different from ECTS, here HEIs accepting credits acknowledge both the workload required and the amount of credits attached as presented by the host HEI after completion of courses even if they may be different to their own credit system.

In the Carnegie System HEIs agree that one course per semesters yields 3 credits based on a range of weeks in the length of an academic period, hence periods can be shortened or extended in the amount of weeks and the number of learning hours is adjusted accordingly.

Among the systems in the sample using *conversions* the sample includes: UMAP’s ECTS, AeU/ACTS, ASEM Asia Europe Dialogue, AE-ECTS Asia Exchange, the Arab Space for Higher Education, the Latin American Reference Credit (CLAR), the EACTS EU-ASEAN credit transfer system for Engineering Education, the Open University (all of which relate to ECTS as a norm reference) and Campus Asia that uses its own framework.

In the cases of UMAP’s UCTS, AeU/ACTS, ASEM Asia Europe Dialogue and AE – ECTS Asia Exchange, the systems use the framework of ECTS (convention of 60 credits for full-time per year) as a norm reference. In each system HEIs agree in that credits granted by another HEI are converted into an agreed standard of credits (like UCTS credits or ECTS credits) and then, converted again into the system of the HEI receiving the credits. The conversions credits yield by courses of different lengths allow for extra amount of credits granted based on extra volume of academic activities.

In the Latin American Credit Reference (CLAR) credits are granted based on the workload required to achieve a given amount of learning. When making transfers HEIs in the system apply ECTS (convention of 60 credits per year); however an important feature of this system is the wide use of qualitative indicators. It is worth mentioning at this point the importance given to the *tuning approach*, which seeks to make comparison in a rather qualitative fashion where recognition is done as “*course by course*” (Nguyen, 2009), (Regel, 1992)

Within the group of systems working as conversions mechanisms the last example is the case of Campus Asia, where HEIs cooperate in the form of Consortium, whereby universities convert the credits granted to the students based on direct negotiation, allowing flexibility in the measurement of workloads based on very different academic periods and lengths of courses. The system works on case-by-case basis rather than using a single reference norm.

The remaining systems in the sample have yet to determine how they will implement the transfer of credits.

Table 8: Groups of credit transfer systems as conventions and conversion tools

CTS that use <i>conventions</i>	CTS that use <i>conversion</i>	CTS that are not yet clear
ECTS, AUN’S ACTS, the Carnegie system, the Go8, the Credit Transfer System at University of Melbourne, the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales	UMAP’s ECTS, AeU/ACTS, ASEM Asia Europe Dialogue, AE-ECTS Asia Exchange, the Arab Space for Higher Education, the Latin American Reference Credit (CLAR), the EACTS EU-ASEAN credit transfer system for Engineering Education, the Open University (all of which relate to ECTS as a norm reference) and Campus Asia	Credit Accumulation and Transfer System for East Africa, the credit system in the Association of African Universities, the EAUI East Asia University Institute and the credit system in the South African Development community

6. Multilateral credit transfer systems as currency exchange markets

Related to the topic above is the fact that systems work differently regarding *how credits are transferred among HEIs*. An analysis model has been proposed by Junor and Usher that compare credit transfer systems to currency exchange systems in different geographic jurisdictions (mostly countries; however in our case the model is applied instead to the systems in the sample). In this *metaphor*, every HEI works as a central bank issuing credits that function as currency; which in turn can be transferred as in the currency exchange market, where three systems channel interactions (Junor & Usher, 2008).

1. Systems with **floating exchange rate**, where every HEI sets a value for its own credits and weighs credits issued by other HEIs case-by-case; there is no intermediate body to transfer the credits, and students negotiate directly with the HEI to which they wish to transfer credits. Due to the nature of the systems in the sample, this category presents two subcategories: 1) Pure free floating; and 2) Free floating attenuated by partial use of ECTS.
2. Systems with **fixed exchange rate** set an *exchange rate rule* to determine how the value of a credit issued by a HEI is weighed against the credit of another. Systems may account with an agency to facilitate inter-institutional communications, promote common policies; and provide guidance.
3. Systems working as a **pure currency union** have a unique system to which all members conform. The example being the Bologna Process -where, similar to a common currency, the Euro- the region seeks to create a "*common knowledge currency*"; meaning that all forms of credits are integrated and recognized automatically.

As the sample includes systems that are still in the process of being set; they are included in the category of **yet to be implemented**; and due to the different nature of each system the category presents three subcategories of systems: 1) tending to free floating; 2) tending to fix rate; and 3) tending to pure union.

Table 9: Credit transfer system according to kind of transfer

CTS Type by kind of transfer used	Credit transfer system in the sample
1. Systems with floating exchange rate	1) Pure free floating - CAMPUS Asia - The University of Melbourne (UM) - EAUI. East Asian University Institute for Asian Region 2) Free floating attenuated by partial use of ECTS - ASEM. Asia Europe Meeting - AE – ECTS. Asia Exchange - EACTS. EU-ASEAN Credit Transfer System (Engineering education) - Latin-American Reference Credit (CLAR) TUNING
2. Systems with fixed exchange rate	- UMAP / UCTS - AeU / ACTS - The Open University (UK)
3. Systems working as a	- ECTS - AUN / ACTS - QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK

pure currency union	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales - The Go8 Credit Transfer Agreement - Carnegie Unit and Student Hour
4. Yet to be implemented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) tending to free floating <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Credit Accumulation and Transfer System East African Countries 2) tending to fix rate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Arab Space for Higher Education (follows ECTS) 3) tending to pure union <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Association of African Universities - CTS SADC. South African Development Community Credit Transfer system

7. Maximum transferable credits

Other differences noted among systems relate to amounts or percentages of transferable credits. Some systems leave that decision to HEIs others stipulate specific amounts as maximum transferable credits. The difference between both groups is clearer depending on whether students transfer permanent or temporarily. In the first case, HEIs are granted more autonomy as they will grant the degrees, and hence they are recognized wider rights to accept or reject credits from previous learning experiences. In the case of permanent transfers, examples in the sample setting a specific rule are the Credit Accumulation and Transfer System for East African Countries that stipulates the 51% of the credits must have been obtained at the HEI awarding the degree. And the Go8 that specifies that transferring students must complete at least one year of equivalent full-time study, or a minimum of 50% of relevant studies at the HEI where students expect to graduate. In Open University credits can be transferred only if they are less than 16 years since they were granted.

In the case of temporary moves and exchange programmes credit transfer systems tend to set clearer rules regarding total amounts of transferable credits, for example in AeU/ACTS the maximum transferable of credits is 30% of the total amount needed for graduation, in the case of AUN's ACTS the limit is instead set by the number of semesters students are allowed to stay in host universities as exchange students, hence one or two semesters; while in the cases of the credit systems in Open University in the UK the Credit Transfer System at University of Melbourne establish maximum limits to advance standing and transfers to exchange or study abroad programmes based on a case by case analysis.

4.2.3.2.2. Information flow

Multilateral credit transfer systems are *per se* tools to share information and they present a number of common features like describing the roles and responsibilities of HEIs using the systems; i.e. when institutions cooperate as *home* and *host* institutions (in temporary exchanges) or as entities *sending* or *receiving* students (in permanent moves).

Multilateral credit systems analyzed encourage the use of agreed channels and procedures to facilitate understanding of practices and processes based on the assumption that by being *multilateral* they provide more legitimacy to both information and channels. In the sample this is clear in the cases of ECTS, UMAP's UCTS, AUN's ACTS, Campus Asia, AE-ECTS Asia Exchange, Credit Accumulation and Transfer System for East Africa, the Association of African

Universities, the Latin American Credit of Reference (CLAR), the Go8 and the EU-ASEAN credit transfer system for mobility in Engineering Education as they explicitly refer to the setting and functioning of agreed communication channels and procedures.

When considering how HEIs communicate with each other in the context of these systems, they all mention the use of *information packages* that with different levels of exactitude contain standard minimums and application forms. Typically they include forms like learning agreements, records or studies, analysis of previous learning experiences (when applicable), transcripts of study programmes, official certificates of completed programmes, etc.

All systems analyzed are based on the assumption that fluid circulation of information among HEIs promote autonomy at the institutional level as better informed decisions can be made. Likewise, they all seek to build and fortify channels to foster communication between HEIs and students. This can be observed in the fact that students are considered in the systems as *sources of information and evidence* to assist professors and academic committees on decisions about recognition; this is evident in that in all cases, students are encouraged to keep records of the study programmes where they have been involved, with details of curricula, workloads and achievements, and other materials.

DISCREPANCIES observed on how information flows within different systems refer to:

Differences about *who* produces *what* documentation, as well as *who* is in charge of revising documents and making final decisions. The main difference here can be seen in that some systems account with centralized mechanism to produce certifications for students participating in exchange programmes; like in UMPA's UCTS, AUN'ACTS, the Go8, and AE-ECTS Asia Exchange. While the rest of the systems in the sample leave it at the hands of HEIs to produce and circulate information with partner HEIs and to the students.

A few systems offer access to academic information provided to students viewing them as *freemovers* (making the students more responsible for their careers) as it happens in AE-ECTS Asia Exchange, Open University and the Go8; as opposed to more *traditional* views regarding role of HEIs and instructors in *guiding* the learners. Examples of this include UMAP's UCTS or AUN's ACTS where students are requested to agree with their teachers on the subjects they are expected to take while they go on exchange programmes.

4.2.3.2.3. Deciding courses in different HEIs

The analysis of data from the systems in the sample suggest a move towards promoting more student-centred approaches to learning, as compared to more traditional teacher centred approaches. As multilateral credit systems seek to democratize decisions on what students should study they propose the use of learning agreements or study plans jointly decided by HEIs and students as practical way ensure quality and consistency in their careers matching their interests and goals.

In exchange programmes, decisions on study plans are made based on the information packages provided by host universities that offer records on curricula, syllabus, workload, academic calendar, etc, upon which students and advisers at home HEIs discuss and decide.

In the systems that explicitly include operational clauses on this, agreement is reached *before* the students' depart from the home institutions; however these are not stone-carved agreements hence allowing future changes depending, for instance, on availability of courses or level of previous knowledge or skills required. In the sample systems that explicitly mention this include ECTS, UMAP's UCTS, AUN's ACTS, AE-ECTS Asia Exchange, the Latin American

Reference Credit (CLAR), and the EU-ASEAN credit transfer system for Student Mobility in Engineering Education.

Learning agreements are meant to find matches among courses in different HEIs with learners' expectations, which further promote the importance of accounting with ample information packages on courses and programmes, and how they relate to the descriptors of competencies and profiles of the graduates, also to curricula and learning outcomes.

Another trend observed is the growing involvement of national quality assurance agencies serving as *centres for advice prior and post* exchange programmes toward better decisions on recognition of qualifications. Examples of this include the ENIC centres in the context of ECTS, the Australian Qualification Framework in relation to Go8, the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and the Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales.

4.2.3.2.4. Measurement of the students' workload

Measurement and comparison of workload and recognition of grades are sensitive aspects of setting a multilateral credit transfer system. They represent the *core* of the systems that actually allow transfer and recognition among HEIs and that materialize in the students' careers the principles and implications of the credit transfer systems.

The comparison of systems reveals that they all share **SIMILARITIES** regarding:

1. Time factor
2. Level of learning and education cycles
3. Growing use of qualitative descriptors

1. Time factor

All systems analyzed allocate credits based on the length of courses; making the *time-factor* a crucial element to determine value or amount of credits attached to courses.

Because *learning time* is defined differently by individual HEIs, all multilateral credit systems analyzed address the problem by creating ways that ease the measurement of notional hours needed by a learner to achieve certain learning outcome. In all cases the measurement of workload includes elements like lectures and classes, practices and laboratory work, tutorials, self study time, fieldwork and the assessment from instructors.

All systems admit that *taught hours* or *contact hours* vary according to method of delivery in each HEI so they promote the agreement among HEIs in that *learning time* fall within an agreed range so as to make them more comparable. In all cases analyzed *learning time* includes structured learning, practical work, informal learning, and retrieving information for example by doing library research and the like.

Likewise, in all systems analyzed the amount of credits are allocated to courses in relation to their length, hence using academic periods like years, semesters, trimesters or quarters. In some systems even shorter periods are eligible for accreditation as in Campus Asia that allows for accreditation of courses including "short exchanges and visits".

While in the case of HEIs that do not use credits to measure students' workload they still *transfer workloads* by using fractions of total amount of time of full time workload in an academic year, as it happens in UMAP's UCTS and Latin American Credit Reference (CLAR).

2. Level of learning and education cycles

All systems in the sample recognize that the more effort a student is requested to put into a course the larger the amount of credits s/he or he should obtain. And the same logic is applied to more complex courses that bring larger number of credits due to their difficulty, however the concrete management of these differences belongs to the on the HEIs rather than to the credit transfers systems.

All systems analyzed share the principle that credits can be allocated to different levels and cycle programmes (bachelor, master and doctorate –even if more debated-) although not all systems actually do it or gauge them in the same way.

The use of levels to attach weight to credits is common among all systems, however more clearly seen among those that focus on measurement based on learning outcomes rather than time; hence credits for courses at bachelor, master and doctorate levels may weigh differently (meaning that they are also treated differently when being transferred within the same level or to different ones). This does not mean that the credits for an undergraduate course are less than those attached for the same course at the postgraduate level, but that those credits belong to different categories. Examples of this in the sample include ECTS, the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and the Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales.

3. Growing use of qualitative descriptors

It is worth mentioning that the comparison of how systems gauge workloads and amounts of credits attached to them suggest growing levels of awareness and interest among HEIs and government about the implications of measuring workload in credits including both quantitative and qualitatively indicators as a way to facilitate and deepen mutual understanding.

Credit transfer systems analyzed show **DIFFERENCES** on how workload is measured in the following aspects:

1. How and where versus what students learn
2. Workload and timing parameters
3. ECTS as the leading paradigm
4. Workloads and levels

1. How and where versus what students learn

Regardless of the general agreement on the relevance of the time factor, an important difference noted among the different credit transfer systems is that for a first group of systems the *how or where* the learning process took place are relevant; while for a second group of systems those factors are less central since systems focus more on *what* has been learnt and *how that relates to the students' careers*.

The agglutinating factor for each group relates to: 1) the level of mutual trust HEIs have among themselves in the first group; as compared to 2) the value a HEI gives to the learning experience a student has elsewhere in the second group.

HEIs using ECTS in Europe, or universities within the context of AUN's ACTS, Campus Asia or the Go8 represent examples of the first group; while the cases of Latin American Credit Reference or the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales function on logics closer to the second one.

2. Workload and timing parameters

Although in the previous section (similarities) we mentioned that all systems agree in using time to measure workloads we also pointed at the fact that they make different use of time to determine the value of credits per course.

The comparison shows that in ECTS: 60 credits are granted for a full-time academic year, where workload is based on a range of 1500 to 1800 learning hours, including all academic activities of a course, distributed in a range of 36 to 40 weeks in an academic year, or 14 to 16 weeks in a semester, or 12 to 14 weeks in a trimester. This implies that 1 credit in ECTS equals to the learning outcome obtained from the work done by the student in a range of 25 to 30 study hours.

In the cases of Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales, HEIs define learning time in relation to the hours students need to achieve a given learning outcome, including all academic activities. In both cases 1 credit equals to 10 learning hours.

UMAP's UCTS relies on ECTS and uses the convention of the 60 credits for full-time in an academic year as a reference. Workload in the system is based on a range of hours distributed per semester, where extra amount of credits can be granted based on extra volume of academic activities.

At the time of writing this report changes are being introduced to UCTS, considering the idea of *Asian Common Credit (ACC)* that proposes 1 ACC equals to 38-48 hours of student workload to facilitate comparison of credits among HEIs in Asia on a *one-to-one* base.

Similarly but leaning closer to ECTS as reference, AeU/ACTS, ASEM Asia Europe Dialogue and AE – ECTS Asia Exchange, systems use the convention of 60 credits per full-time students in an academic year, where hours of workload are distributed in ranges of 25-30 weeks in a year; 14-16 in a semester and 12-14 in a trimester; whereby a course in one semester yields 20-30 credits, implying that 1 credit is granted for 25 to 30 hours of total workload.

In the Latin American Credit Reference (CLAR), credits are granted based on workload required to achieve a given volume of learning in a given period of time. The length of courses is crucial to the allocation of credits; however there is an average agreed interval of 32 to 40 weeks per academic year; in general HEIs in the system agree with the ECTS convention of 60 credits per academic year for full-time students. In the system 1 credit hour equals to a range of 15 to 16 weeks in a semester, where 1 hour of class requires 2 hours of self-study time. An important feature of the system is the use of qualitative indicators to describe workload and the relative weight of credits (and learning outcomes) from a course relative to the total amount required for graduation in a programme and the relevance of the course to that programme. Hence, the same subject may yield different number of credits depending on the programme where it is studied.

In the Carnegie System HEIs grant a typical semester course 3 credits based on a range of 15-16 weeks as the length of the semester. The 3 credits are granted for a range of 45-46 hours of workload normally required by a course where one contact hour on average includes 2 hours of self-study. Academic periods can be shorter in the amount of weeks but the number of learning hours in the workload needs to be compensated with bigger number of contact and study hours to accomplish the learning outcomes. This allows HEIs to independently determine kind and amount of hours of workloads, allowing for example research activities in lieu of formal classes.

3. ECTS as the leading paradigm

An interesting finding from the comparison of systems is the fact that many of them take the principles set by ECTS in the context of Bologna Process as a raw model both in the ways other systems work themselves and when they seek to bridge contacts with European HEIs.

Among the clearest aspects observed is that a number of multilateral credit systems include among their own principles ECTS' notion of 60 credits for a full-time academic year, whereby a semester equals to 30 credits and a trimester to 20 credits.

Besides ECTS itself, other systems using it as a reference include UMAP's UCTS, AeU/ACTS, ASEM Asia Europe Meeting, EA-ECTS Asia Exchange, the Arab Space of Higher Education, the Latin American Credit Reference (CLAR), the EACTS EU-ASEAN credit transfer System for mobility of students in Engineering Education.

The credit systems in the context of Open University, the Quality Assurance Framework in the UK and the Credit Qualifications Framework for Wales make direct mention in their procedures about how they interact with ECTS when transfers are done with HEIs in Europe.

The Latin American Credit of Reference presents an interesting example of *alignment* of the whole region with integration of HE in Europe, as opposed to creating a newly integrated system of its own, countries in the region have opted to work among themselves and with European partners through a more direct-dialogue based strategy aiming to set a common space with Europe based on the tuning approach (Yavaprabhas, 2009).

The systems analyzed in Africa reveal that even if they are all still in the process of deciding how each system will be implemented, they are all considering procedures used in Europe and this applies to Credit Accumulation and Transfer System for East Africa, the credit system in the Association of African Universities, the EAUI East Asia University Institute and the credit system in the South African Development community.

4. Workloads and levels

Although previously in this section (Similarities: 2. Level of learning and education cycles) we mentioned that all systems consider levels of education and complexity of courses in relation to the level where those courses take place; systems actually work differently when considering the relation between credits and educational cycles.

There are cases where credit transfer systems allocate larger number of credits to courses taken at higher cycles, meaning that the complexity of the course is valued in the number of credits a course yields, hence for example a course offered at a bachelor level yields 4 credits, while the same course offered at a masters level yields 6 credits based on the assumption that the demands in the higher cycle will be higher and that learning outcomes will be more complex. In the sample the case of the Latin American Credit Reference (CLAR) serves as an example of this method for a few countries that use credit system; however and in general this is more of an exception.

In other cases systems create *categories* or *levels of credits* for qualifications granted at different cycles (bachelor, master and doctorate) sometimes even depending on the kinds of programmes (full or part-time, mandatory class attendance or distance or virtual learning, etc.). For example in the case of the Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales, credits are attached to level or cycle of education distributed into nine levels; where the level works as an indicator the relative demand, complexity, depth of learning and of learner autonomy required from a student in a course. The assessment of the level of a credit attached to course is based on learning attainments expected from the course and to the descriptors for each

level. The system is graphically explained in a fun graph available in the Appendix 1. (Hutt, 2009)

In line with this logic, in ECTS national qualification frameworks agree on the use of level descriptors related to learning outcomes from courses, where credits are granted according to those levels, which in turn are defined according to agreed cycle descriptors with learning outcomes and credit ranges (known as ‘Dublin Descriptors’). Here first cycle qualifications contain 180-240 credits and second cycle qualifications 90-120 ECTS credits, with a minimum of 60 ECTS credits at the level of the 2nd cycle. Credits are described based on levels and they can only be accumulated towards a qualification when they are granted at the appropriate level (European Communities, 2009). Other similar examples from the sample include the Go8, the Credit Transfer System at Melbourne University, and the Credit transfer system at Open University and the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK.

4.2.3.2.5. Scale matching

Once again, this represents a sensitive issue in academic credit transfers. The problem relates to whether HEIs that will eventually grant the degrees to the students will accept not only the credits from their workload and achievements obtained in other HEIs but how they will treat the grades obtained by students elsewhere. Evaluating students’ performance and grading their achievements is logically the instructor’s responsibility and the problem here arises as a consequence of students moving to HEIs that use different grading systems.

The issue is present both in the case of temporary move of students in exchange programmes and also students transfer permanently from a HEI to another.

As multilateral credit systems seek to address the issue they propose different strategies to tackle the problem, and even if all systems analyzed recommend the acceptance of grades by HEIs (as logically following the acceptance of credits), in practical terms the general rule continues to be a final right of the HEIs, meaning that transfer of grades is based on voluntary acceptance of the rules set in each systems by HEIs that use them (a principle known as the *veto power of the accepting HEIs*).

All systems analyzed are **SIMILAR** in that:

1. Assessment and interpretation
2. Use of pass-fail marks

1. Assessment and interpretation

Multilateral credit transfer systems aim to facilitate understanding and transfer of assessments of the performance of the students by “translating” grades when dealing with different systems utilized by different HEIs.

When systems are used in the context temporary exchanges the assessment of students is done by host HEIs and *interpreted* by the home HEIs upon completion and return but within the context of their own criteria.

2. Use of pass-fail marks

A generally agreed rule is the fact that transfer of credits (and possibly grades) is done based on the “successful completion of study courses”, meaning that for students to actually transfer credits they need at least a *pass mark* from the evaluator.

Although all systems agree in this principle what renders the issue thorny is the definition of what *pass and fail* mean. Different HEIs set the dividing line at different percentages, for instance while usually HEIs set it at 60%, others set it at higher or lower ranges, meaning that even if contents of a subject may be similar among HEIs, students may -or may not- have their credits recognized depending on their having reached the base/passing line of the HEI accepting those grades.

Among the **DIFFERENCES** found the following are mentioned as the most characteristic:

1. Use of reference norm tables for conversion
2. Alternative forms of conversion
3. Bilateral agreements even within multilateral arrangements

1. Use of reference norm tables for conversions

In the cases of credit transfer systems that connect HEIs using different grade systems tend to set agreed scales to facilitate interpretation and possible conversion of grades. Scales are typically described in tables that work as norm referenced grading schemes whereby for example a pre-determined percentile is used to compare different grades in different systems; in other cases like where normal distribution of grades is used a percentage or range of percentages of candidates in each cohort receive a pass or better mark is used to allow assessment and conversion.

Systems in the sample that account with reference tables typically assert that the usage of scales helps respect the autonomy of HEIs as they “interpret” but do not necessarily “impose” grades. Among the systems analyzed using standard comparative tables for assessment or interpretation of grades we found: ECTS, UMAP’s UCTS, AeU/ACTS, AUN’s ACTS and the Credit Accumulation and Transfer System in East African countries

2. Alternative forms of conversion

Important variations among systems can be seen in the management of the transfer of *raw marks* that may (or may not) be accepted and included into final transcripts and their implications towards setting figures in the students’ GPAs.

Interpretation of grades may be done based on statistical distribution of grades, where students marks are distributed including all students being evaluated for a course and placed into groups based on percentage of students with a given mark in each cohort, as it happens in the cases of ECTS, UMAP’s UCTS, AUN’s ACTS.

Other systems propose the use the percentile as a reference to compare grades; in the sample the case of AeU/ACTS serves as example.

Others use quality descriptors attached to the grades as in the cases of Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and Latin American Credit Reference (CLAR); yet others use assessments based on subjective marks grading students work with adjectives like excellent, good or sufficient as proposed by UMAP’s UCTS, AeU/ACTS, and AUN’s ACTS.

Some systems propose automatic recognition but do not determine how HEIs are to treat those grades, in these cases receiving HEIs are expected to accept the grades from other HEIs and grant them to the students upon graduation in the way they were presented by the host/sending institutions. This is typically seen in national kind of frameworks like in the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales.

Some systems provide mathematic mechanisms for conversion of grades to incorporate the mark into the grade-point average (GPA), like in the case of Carnegie system, which uses a mathematical devise according to which to figure a GPA, grades received in each course are weighed by multiplying it by the number of credit hours, where for instance a 3B (grade points) in a 4-credit class yields 12 quality points. These are added together and then divided by the total number of credits a student has taken to get the GPA. On the other side of the same coin systems like the AeU/ACTS do not consider transfer of grades in to GPA calculation from different HEIs all together.

Lastly it should be noted that in a number of systems, HEIs may offer credits by examinations (not considering class participation); these types of qualifications tend to be shown in the transcripts as a mark that may (or may not) count as workload in terms of hours and they are likely to show in the transcripts with special marks typically not considered for GPA. This kind of grading was observed in the cases of the Carnegie and the Credit Qualification Framework for Wales.

3. Bilateral agreements within multilateral arrangements

Grading systems may be agreed bilaterally among HEIs even if they participate in multilateral credit arrangements, for instance prior to exchange of students as a form of “translation” between HEIs concerned; as it happens in the case of Go8.

4.2.3.2.6. Quality Assurance

The overall analysis of multilateral systems suggests agreement in that they promote improvements in quality assurance of HE by increasing amount and kind of interactions among HEIs, both domestic and internationally. This seems to be based on the assumption that the more open the management and access to information on courses, programmes and institutions, the more positive the impact on quality assurance mechanisms tend to have as a consequence of increasing exposure and comparison.

It must remain clear that credit transfer systems and quality assurance are related yet different schemes; even if both help toward mutual recognition of qualifications among HEIs they are by definition different and function on different principles and rules. Quality assurance mechanisms seek to build trust in the quality of education, while credit systems aim to facilitate understanding of workloads and qualifications, which materializes that trust in the form of recognition. The overlapping point of the two systems is *comparability*.

SIMILARITIES in the sample relate to **QA and CTS overlaps on trust building and mobility**.

All systems share the notion that the primary responsibility in the provision of quality of education lays first on every HEI as accountable entities before their students, governments and societies.

The analysis of credits systems also reveals agreement in that the relation between the two (QA and CTS) represent an integral strategy toward building inter-institutional trust and to promote mobility of students. This is because the two schemes share a common interest in understanding what learning outcomes students achieve when participating in different educational experiences. And also because harmonized quality systems help bringing into line curricula design and complementary academic developments, which are as well among the goals credit transfer systems seek to boost.

A mutually feeding loop boosts comparative quality assurance among countries and HEIs as a horizon to academic progress where credit transfer systems potentiate that process by stimulating mutual exposure. While the developments taking place in the area of quality assurance promote the establishment and improvement of multilateral credit systems as they encourage more exchanges among HEIs whose study programmes can be trusted. Lastly the comparison also makes clear that most countries and HEIs recognize that QA is a central element in the notion of accumulation of credits, therefore their promotion should in turn encourage the notion of lifelong learning as a long term goal.

Among the **DIFFERENCES** spotted it should be noticed that some credit systems have actually been set to function in close collaboration with quality assurance agencies. The cases of ECTS in connection to the role give to national ENIC centres at the international level, and the Quality Assurance Agency in the UK and the Credit and Qualification Framework for Wales at the national levels demonstrate this.

While at the HEI level some systems promote automatic recognition of quality of education of the HEIs in the same network as in the Go8 in Australia and the AUN's ACTS.

There are evident different levels of implementation in regards to mechanisms for quality assurance, this happens at the country and institutional levels and this works against the development of credit transfer systems at the multilateral stage.

4.2.3.2.7. Diploma supplements (DS)

The comparison of systems included a section on diploma supplement to test awareness on the issue and the level of applicability it may have had to simplify recognition of credits.

Information gathered from the systems in the sample shows that the use of academic transcripts has been the rule on how HEIs communicate with each other on students' learning achievements. However in a context of increasing connectivity and growing fluidity of labour markets are boosting the need to account with more complex tools to help HEIs and employers better understand the content and nature of degrees and qualifications.

To respond to this demand, countries in the European zone created a *Diploma Supplement* to help provide more details on contents of degrees, study programmes as well as learning outcomes and grades. Acceptance and actual use of the tool remains limited, however promising in order to facilitate academic and professional recognition of qualifications.

The diploma supplement in Europe is meant to facilitate share of information; yet lack of awareness and unwillingness still hinder its wider implementation, especially at the HEI level as it implies an extra burden of work (gathering and organizing information on personal bases of each student; plus the language problem as it must be issued in more than the national language, when HEIs work in languages other than major European languages.

From the analysis of data in the credit transfer systems in the sample it was found that the idea of diploma supplement is typically used as a reference linked only to ECTS and rather unknown in other regions; rendering the spread use of it difficult unless there is an important promotion of awareness on this tool. While, among those who do know about it outside Europe there seems to be lack of agreement on how it should be issued, by whom, enclosing what content, based on what periodicity and what language should be used.

4.3. Conclusions

The comparison of multilateral credit transfer systems demonstrates that intense amount of work and efforts have been put into creating and consolidating them and yet a long way remains ahead. Previous pages shed light on central aspects of multilateral credit systems; they spot some lessons learnt (and to be learnt) and portray the current scenario on transfer of academic credits. The following paragraphs synthesise what those experiences offer us in order to rethink upcoming efforts towards harmonization in HE.

An aspect to be emphasised about the functioning rules of multilateral credit systems is that without exception they all work on *voluntary bases* that allow HEIs using them a level of autonomy that is perceived not only as healthy but also as necessary if those setting the systems expect HEIs to feel attracted to use them in their daily interactions with other HEIs in the exchange of information toward successful transfer and recognition of credits.

The use of multilateral credit systems as communication tools provide HEIs means that are not invasive and help them better interpret what partner HEIs do (what they teach and research and how they do it), which in turn allows for more interaction in the form of student mobility and the transfer and recognition of skills and knowledge among them, countries and regions, while these systems create frameworks that allow alternative study pathways and chances for progression to learners.

Multilateral credit systems stimulate the mobility of students both at the domestic and international realms which increasingly stimulate reflection and serve as catalysis for curricula development, transparency and updating of study programmes. At more individual/student level they stimulate the transfer of learning experiences among students that can come in touch with wider audiences and learners who share common interests in completely different contexts.

Multilateral credit systems facilitate comparability of national and local legal systems and educational structures, features, goals and strategies based on increased exposure. They help comparison and mutual learning from everyday practices.

Throughout different strategies all systems analysed create devices that are fair, rational, easily understandable and student centred. They seek helping improve networking skills and contacts among HEIs, governments and also among credit systems structurally. They allow for rapid evaluation of students and their workloads (especially when it is based on standard procedures), monitoring, and maintenance of up-to-date information available for students, professors, academics and international relations officers on programmes and syllabi.

Multilateral credit systems analyzed in the context of Asia work on rules that do not require modifications of existing credit regulations and grading rules within each national system or at the HEIs using them. In practice this implies great flexibility based on the fact that even if decisions on transfer and recognition of credits from different HEIs are done following agreed procedures, actual decisions are actually made based on attitudes and acceptance toward otherness (as opposed to rules and procedures only).

Multilateral credit systems are promoting multidisciplinary cooperation among HEIs in terms of subjects and study areas they can offer to students. This is because bilateralism is being progressively overcome by multilateral schemes that eliminate duplication of work and promote complementation rather than competition among HEIs.

The analysis of the data on multilateral credit transfer systems suggests that they are creating a culture of “online shopping” for study courses and programmes expanding the supply of

learning opportunities that increasingly adjust to the needs and expectations of students of all types; making national boundaries increasingly blurry.

These systems facilitate comparison of educational attainment even if they take place in different contexts and programmes, which allows students and HEIs better understand alternative setting and destinations, programmes and institutions, and along that making better matched and more informed decisions.

Multilateral credit transfer systems allow institutions to provide programmes that go far beyond their traditional scopes, giving students the chance to obtain an academic formation that opens doors to new job opportunities and to new markets where they can apply their skills and further explore and expand their potentials.

As these systems put students at the centre of the learning processes they promote ownership and responsibility of the student in the acquisition of knowledge and skills and in the direction they give to their careers; at the same time systems promote more systematic reflection on teaching and learning methodologies and the roles of students and instructors.

Multilateral credit transfer systems promote multidimensional agreements that make societies come closer not only in academic terms but also economically, politically and culturally. They contribute to the process of regional integration and construction of common spaces and identities; they put different peoples in contact and context, which fosters friendship and helps eliminating prejudgements towards otherness.

Among the **CHALLENGES** ahead some issues present call for attention and further efforts, like the need to achieve more consistency and permeability among HEIs and educational systems that demand for reforms at both levels, E.g. in harmonizing academic calendars and generating agreement on the measurement of academic achievements. And the same can be said about accepting and developing ways to deal with different approaches to learning in informal and non-formal settings, as well as giving academic value to prior learning and working experience and finding ways to continue enhancing flexibility at all levels so as to respond and adjust to changes.

Challenges remain on how to treat double or joint degrees and programmes gradually shifting from teaching-centred to learning-centred; how to foster pragmatic approaches, based on step by step ways to focus on contents, and the use of learning outcomes rather than just content oriented, or simply time-based measurement of students' workload.

Other challenges relate to the use of descriptors of academic levels (bachelor, master and doctorate) that still render systems complex and difficult to understand and use when making transfers, however keeping in mind that *that* complexity relates to increasing levels of fairness in granting and recognizing qualifications and towards progression of studies.

Different weights on academic importance of transfer means that domestic transfer of credits seem to be more *academic related*; while international transfers tends to be more culturally oriented and aiming mostly to develop more cultural sensitiveness and mutual understanding at the human and social realms.

Divergences among systems remain broad and refer for example to the fact that different systems show various levels of tolerance towards otherness and change, some systems are open to new members –as it happens in UCTS, where it is entirely up to the HEIs whether to use the mechanisms proposed by UMAP or not-; while others are fixed in their membership or regional scope –as in the network of AUN-. Some systems work on the principle of informality as a base to facilitate contacts and more directly among institutions -as proposed

by AeU/ACTS-; while others are more structured and less flexible –as in the Carnegie system-. Some foster the idea of students as *freemovers* – as in AE-ECTS Asia Exchange and Open University- to promote students’ ownership in terms of career developments, professional decisions and directions; showing at the system level a more liberal approach to learning. While other systems show more traditional positions and see students as youngsters that need guidance and assistance

Lastly, there is a need to develop ownership of the careers by the students in both students and HEIs’ managers. An interesting finding of this research was the fact that there are still significant differences in the levels of trust HEIs are willing to give to their students.

This concludes the comparative analysis of multilateral credit systems, in the pages to come the focus of the study shifts towards recent developments at the national level in the countries included at this time.

5. Credit systems at the country level

This section puts the credit systems used in use in the countries included in the *Explore* phase of the project in perspective. Different from the previous chapter where the comparison focused *multilateral systems* here the focus goes to what happens regarding credit systems, the transferability of academic achievements and the perception of those about those systems *within* the ten countries analyzed.

What motivates this part of the study is the need to understand the particularities in each country on how they manage academic credits; the analysis focuses on the features and the ways countries and HEIS therein deal with the transfer and recognition of credits.

As explained in the methodology in chapter 3, data for this section was gathered locally by a resource person per country, who carried out a focused literature review on the structure and features of HE systems in their countries; and then carried out interviews with key stakeholders to describe credit systems in use considering the views of the governments, HEIs and students. Each resource person created his/her sample (purposively constructed to describe each case). They were requested to put forward recommendations towards the implementation of a scheme that can be comprehensive and inclusive for the region as a whole. (Recommendations are analysed separately in chapter 8)

The following pages synthesize the data from the country reports and provide an overview of the region regarding credit systems, conditions for transferability at the country level and a “perception base” to justify the views stakeholders have of the mechanisms used, as well as possible ways to facilitate the mobility of students through the validation, comparison and recognition of academic credits. Data for this section was obtained from the country reports prepared by the resource persons. All country reports can be found in Annex 4: CTS country reports.

The information gathered through these reports coincides and confirms most of Hotta’s findings that describe the national HE systems in East and Southeast Asia and their respective credit systems and status (Hotta, 2010a).

Although the two studies overlap by analyzing mostly the same countries (Hotta included Brunei Darussalam, Singapore and The Philippines, which were “*put on hold*” for this study for the time being) findings from the data gathered for SEAMEO RIHED’s report provide rich insights about national motivations and policies, strategic plans, methods and stakeholders views on student mobility and their evaluation on the effectiveness of the credit systems, the transferability in them, and rules used in each country.

This report has sought to include the views and voices of those creating, implementing and actually using those systems. I.e. policy makers in the governments, implementers in the HEIs practicing those rules, and mobile students as the ultimate beneficiaries / victims of the decisions on recognition of their qualifications.

In so doing this report sets a starting point for future actions regarding the implementation of credit systems to promote student mobility and harmonization by understanding the logics supporting each system and expectations about mobility and internationalization.

5.1. Findings from the country cases

Data from the country reports confirm great diversity among the HE systems in the countries and also in the mechanisms used across the region. However and interestingly it is worth

noting that in all the cases the reports give high consideration to the motivations of their governments and most HEIs in promoting internationalization of HE through compatible tools like credit transfer and quality assurance (be them external or internal).

This apparent contradiction between diversity and will to harmonize justifies the need for this project to carry on into its upcoming phases (*Experiment, Experience and Expand*).

Country reports greatly confirm what was observed in the literature review in chapter 2 about the fact that the bulk of the moves of students in the region happen based on bilateral agreements between host and home HEIs rather than through multilateral credit transfer systems.

Likewise, all country reports assert that internationalizing HE is a major strategy to provide students with skills and knowledge to face the challenges of regional integration. Similarly all reports convey the idea of general agreement in that workforces and human resources increasingly need to be better prepared to go beyond national borders and be able to understand wider scenarios of the labour market.

Because of this all countries in the region, although with different paces and willingness, coincide on the need to further develop *bridges* among themselves, where harmonization of HE appears not only as “plausible” but rather as an urgent must.

In all cases quality in the provision of educational services appears as a major concern, especially before the booming in the number of HEIs (public and private), the need to democratize access to wider sectors of the populations and to make education systems more competitive and attractive at the international level.

All country reports suggest growing consensus on the need to change traditional attitudes referring to:

- the direction of the flows of students (from typical European, North American or other developed countries toward destinations within East and Southeast Asia;
- the need to build common trust among countries and HEIs (meaning promote *more open-mindedness* among those deciding what students should learn); and
- the growing impulse to give students more responsibility on their own decisions and the future of their careers.

Lastly and yet very important, country reports suggest growing agreement among HEIs and governments on that the management and measurement of students’ workload should be done through the use of academic credits and the modularization of study courses. This may seem an obvious matter at this point, however this process and its counterpart the decreasing attachment of academic courses to time (academic years, semesters and the like) is creating both a more homogeneous and yet fragmented landscape.

The aspects above represent both potentials and challenges in that while HE systems are expanding to offer more accessibility to students, there are also concerns such as the mechanisms to ensure quality and tools to facilitate mutual understanding and trust.

5.2. National education systems in perspective

The following table summarizes the overview presented by the country reports regarding each country in their situation of credit systems from the data on the desk reviews.

Table 10: Country level overview of credit system

Indicators →	National law on credit system	HEIs' autonomy to recognize other HEIs' credits	Decision on transfer of grades	External aid on decisions for QA & recognition	Laws on transferability	
					Decision on domestic credit transfers	Decision on Int'l credit transfer
Countries ↓						
Cambodia	yes	medium	receiving HEI	yes	Yes Receiving HEI	Yes Receiving HEI
China	no	high	receiving HEI	yes	no same tier or group and receiving HEI	no receiving HEI
Indonesia	yes	high	receiving HEI	yes	no receiving HEI	no receiving HEI
Japan	yes	high	receiving HEI	yes	yes receiving HEI	yes receiving HEI
Lao PDR	yes	low	receiving HEI	yes	no receiving HEI	no receiving HEI
Malaysia	yes	high	receiving HEI	yes	no receiving HEI	no receiving HEI
Myanmar	yes	low	compulsory for same kind of HEIs	yes	yes compulsory for same kind of HEIs	not in practice
Thailand	yes	high	receiving HEI	yes	yes receiving HEI	yes receiving HEI
Vietnam	yes	low (with exceptions)	not specified	yes	yes receiving HEI	not in practice
R. Korea	yes	high	receiving HEI	yes	yes receiving HEI	yes receiving HEI

All desk reviews present the structure and a brief history of the HE systems in the countries. Data here allows the reader to understand why HE systems are the way they are and function in the way they do.

This report analyzes issues briefly to avoid repeating Hotta's work and to allow more space for the main goal of this research -looking more at the *procedures* and positions on transfer of credits-. For details on technical matters like legislations, number of HEIs, careers, years per level and degree, credits required per degree, number of students, etc, readers should feel interested in looking at Hotta's work on the regional as well as the country levels.

All countries present points in common as well as differences based on their histories and national visions, the following pages synthesize the most important overlapping areas.

Among the [SIMILARITIES](#) countries share the following features:

1. Evident changes in the role of the HE
2. *Massification* of HE
3. Increasing privatization of HE
4. Impact on quality of education of increasing complexity
5. Diversity as a motto for internationalization
6. Case-by-case treatment of transfers
7. *Asianisation* of student mobility

8. Challenging traditional teaching methods
9. New challenges
10. Length of study programmes
11. Ranking of HEIs
12. Language proficiency issues
13. Need for common communication framework

1. Evident changes in the role of the HE

The comparison of country reports found that in all cases HE was borne out of the need to account with personnel for public administration and so HEIs were initially supported (financial and functionally) by governments; however in all countries there has been a shift towards *privatization* of HE as a response in the change on the perception of HE systems as incubators of ideas, research and innovation, and as producers of qualified human resources to support the productive sectors of the national economies. HEIs are now called to fulfil new roles like training cadres for state and non-state organizations, provide technical help and experience towards the productive systems among different industries, and this is not only as providers of education but also as consultants and entities for external monitoring.

2. Massification of HE

All reports suggest a rapid increase in the amount of HEIs and students in recent decades, implying a greater demand from society for new ways for social mobility and the responses of both governments and for-profit institutions seeking to answer those demands.

3. Increasing privatization of HE

Except for the case of Myanmar, all other country reports mention a tendency toward privatization of HE, where although public education and governmental support continues to be the main development driver in the sector, the relative importance and amount of providers has increasingly shifted toward private and for-profit institutions.

4. Impact on quality of education of increasing complexity

The increasing complexity of the HE landscapes in all countries has consequently raised concerns about quality of education. Reports suggest a contradicting challenge in that while governments seek to allow wider access to HE to more students, yet and regardless of how laudable this aim is, governments are increasingly faced with the challenge of how to ensure quality of educational services and legitimate access

5. Diversity as a motto for internationalization

Educational systems have been shaped by domestic factors and the countries' histories, needs and visions. This factor greatly explains the diversity within the region, however a common trend observed in all countries is the growing will to open their systems toward cross boarder education. Evidence of this is the reforms carried out in recent years seeking more openness and permeability. All reports coincide in that internationalization has increasingly become both, an element of prestige and a goal in itself.

An example of this is promotion of internationalization related to permanent and temporary mobility of students (like in exchange and double degree programmes). In most cases bilateral relations provide the operational framework for that mobility however there is an increasing call and interest from all stakeholders toward *multilateralization* of mobility.

6. Case-by-case treatment of transfers

All reports demonstrate that *by rule*, where mobility of students happens arrangements on validation and recognition of qualifications are done on a case-by-case base analysis by the HEIs involved; a procedural strategy that although seen as *necessary* also greatly alleged as a time-consuming process that still offers no guarantees of recognition.

7. Asianisation of student mobility

Reports confirm Kell and Volg's (2012) idea of *Asianisation of higher education* mentioned in the literature review in chapter 2 of this report, as all resource persons mention a growing interest among parents, students governments and HEIs to consider Asian destinations for international education; which is materializing at the integration discourse and the number of programmes that promote mobility of students and staff *within* the region.

8. Challenging traditional teaching methods

All reports and interviews carried out for the study reflect a change of attitude in the region in that education systems are challenging traditional ways of teaching, seeking a shift from an approach where students were typically spoon-fed by the instructors towards more proactive methods that make students responsible for their careers, active participants of the learning process and creative sources of innovation and progress.

Stakeholders show positive attitudes towards more flexible learning experiences, and this can be seen in the increasing modularization of courses within all kinds of programmes and also by the increasing numbers of programmes that provide long-distance education or on-line programmes. Although these kinds of opportunities are increasing the chances to many of those who wish to study but cannot do it due to financial or distance related reasons; long-distance and on-line learning are also raising increasing concerns about the quality of the services and the increasing blurry nature in the legitimacy of those qualifications.

9. New challenges

All reports coincide in seeing globalization as promoting the potentials to flourish while at the same time bringing new challenges in issues like quality of education, access to employment and human security. They all point at the likelihoods of increasing fluxes of people and knowledge and the implications towards increasing competition in the global labour markets; which coincides with the justification of this project.

10. Length of study programmes

Country reports evidence a generalized yet relative coincidence among countries and HEIs regarding the lengths of study programmes by level. Bachelor degrees typically last three to four years, except for careers like medicine, veterinarian and some areas of engineering usually lasting about six years. While master programmes tend to last on average two years and doctorates three years. Even if variations exist, this information facilitates the cross boarder understanding of programmes and level of the study courses therein.

11. Ranking of HEIs

Another shared trend observed through the country reports is the increasing interest stakeholders show on the level HEIs achieve in different rankings that compare their performance and the quality of the programmes they offer. Accounting with reliable ways to contrast the provision of services in each HEI is promoting changes among HEIs' managers and academicians seeking to raise the quality in their programmes and institutions.

12. Language proficiency issues

All country reports coincide in that proficiency in international languages, typically in English, is a major area of concern. Skills in English language are systematically mentioned and in all cases the issue is portrayed as a basic requirement. This touches on all sides of education; that is the capabilities of instructors to produce materials and teach in a foreign language; the ability of students to follow programmes in foreign languages and to obtain reasonably good outcomes from the learning processes and for the administrative personnel (as they determine the value attached to workload and qualifications) in order to allow for communication among foreign HEIs and students.

13. Need for common communication framework

All reviews alike coincide on that new technologies and communication tools are making international contacts and networking more fluid than ever before, however access to those means and disclosure of information, specially at the worldwide web is still very disperse. The development of proper tools, with democratic access to information and technology appear as a central issue of concern among all stakeholders.

Among the **DIFFERENCES** observed the following are the most outstanding ones:

1. Structural credit systems gaps
2. Treatment of grades (in relation to credit transfer)
3. Autonomy of HEIs
4. Direction of student mobility flows
5. Accreditation of prior learning
6. Accreditation of working experience
7. Quality assurance issues

1. Structural credit systems gaps

All reports show gaps among countries regarding amounts of credits required and value attached to them at the time of measuring students' workloads. Differences are observed at the country level when they set their credit systems, and also among HEIs when countries allow autonomy for the institutions to set their own credit systems. This issue is portrayed in all cases as one of the biggest challenges to facilitate mobility of students.

Similarly, countries show variations in how instructors asses the performance of students as well as how grades are used for final evaluation of the qualifications of the students.

2. Treatment of grades (in relation to credit transfer)

Reports showed relevant differences in terms of countries accounting with regulated qualification frameworks implemented nationally like in the cases or Myanmar, Lao PDR and Cambodia that set homogenous systems countrywide; while in other cases some legislation exist providing guidance to HEIs on credit system policies, as in the cases of Japan, Korea, Thailand or Malaysia; while in others the issue is practically unregulated like in the cases of China and Indonesia, allowing full autonomy to the HEIs to decide.

This gap in legal treatment of grades complicates the scenery in that it makes comparability of systems more difficult particularly for the cases where frameworks do not exist.

3. Autonomy of HEIs

Another area where reports show discrepancies is the level of autonomy granted to HEIs by the governments, special interest was put to the level of independence institutions have regarding recognition and acceptance of qualifications coming from other HEIs.

4. Direction of student mobility flows

Reports greatly confirm what was mentioned in the literature review in chapter 2 about traditional flows of students, where in all cases students have typically moved first toward more developed regions and countries although with a recent growing interest on new and alternative destinations mostly within East and Southeast Asia.

Within the differences seen among the countries here there is a clear distinction between those countries who are typically *sending students* (like Indonesia, Lao PDR, Cambodia, Myanmar and Vietnam) or those more likely to be *receiving* (like Japan or Korea); while others show more balanced situations in terms of incoming and outgoing students (like China, Thailand, Indonesia and Malaysia).

5. Accreditation of prior learning

Reports reveal contrasting approaches towards accreditation of prior, informal and non-formal learning. While some countries have already carried out reforms in their systems to implement mechanisms that facilitate vertical mobility, for example by using credit systems to ease the entrance process to higher levels of education like master or doctorate programmes like it happens in Malaysia and Indonesia. While other countries heavily rely on entrance exams like in China, Japan or Vietnam, that tend to restrict and control entrance to those programmes. For the time being this does not seem to impose major problems for the vertical international mobility of students given that in the all cases acceptance into higher level programmes is normally based on *recognition of degrees rather than validation of credits* and prior learning. However in the longer run this will require engaged dialogue.

6. Accreditation of working experience

In a similar way, country reports show divergent attitudes towards academic accreditation of non-formal and informal learning as well as work experiences outside an academic framework. In some of the countries it was found that practical experiences like internships and participation in voluntary programmes as well as fieldwork are considered for the acquisition of credits to be counted towards the degrees like in the cases of China, Korea, Japan, Indonesia or Malaysia, where HEIs account with higher levels of autonomy.

7. Quality assurance issues

Existence or not of systems of quality assurance (both internal and external) in the frame of national HE systems is another major factor of concern. The region as a whole is still diverse in how quality of education is guaranteed among HEIs in each and among countries. All reports coincide in that regardless of how effective and fair a credit transfer system may be, if educational quality cannot be assured and reach at least some mutually recognized basic standards among HEIs, mobility is likely to remain only a theoretical goal.

5.3. Credit systems at the national level

The following pages present findings from the comparison in regards to how each country deals with accreditation of students' workload and grading systems.

Data collected for this section greatly overlaps with Hotta's (2010) comparison. As explained in the literature review in chapter 2, in his research Hotta presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of the national situations on credit systems in the region. The reader should feel encouraged to examine this piece if s/he looks for particularities about each

country as that author provides meticulously detailed information showing developments and status in 13 countries in East and Southeast Asia in this regard.

Data collected by resource persons for this research carried out by SEAMEO RIHED at the *Explore* phase of the project largely confirms Hotta's recent findings. To avoid repetition a descriptive comparison chart as the one presented by that author has not been included however, and as mentioned the reader should feel encouraged to read Hotta's work.

It must remain clear however, that the contribution of *SEAMEO RIHED's* report to Hotta's analysis comes from portraying the political implications, as well as the perceptions of the main stakeholders on the effectiveness of existing credit transfer systems and their views and recommendations towards creating a scheme to allow for further harmonization. Including the voice of those involved and affected by credit transfer systems serve as a legitimizing base for future steps of the project as a whole.

To obtain data on how the credit systems work, their potentials and challenges and ideals on what the views features of credit transferability should be; local resources persons included in their reports three sections containing information on: 1. *CTS in the eyes of the government*; 2. *CTS in the eyes of HEIs*; and 3. *CTS in the eyes of the students*.

The following pages show: commonalities and differences in the use of credit transfer systems in the region and then particularities observed at the country level.

5.4. Transferability of students' workloads in the systems

5.4.1. Commonalities

According to data presented in the country reports and the interviews carried out during the *Explore phase* of this research countries show common patterns in regards to:

1. Rule of time to measure workload due to the central role of professors
2. International mobility as added value
3. Lack of awareness on credit systems as a common challenge

1. Rule of time to measure workload due to the central role of professors

Even though gaps exist in the disaggregation of time assigned to different learning activities, such as lectures, homework and self-study time or laboratories practices; all reports confirm a broad agreement in the use of *time as the main rule to measure students' workload* among HEIs in the region;

Data from interviews and reports shows growing awareness on the need to include the notion of *learning outcomes* as one of the factors to measure students' workloads and to relativise the use of contact hours as the unit of measurement. This is still perceived as a far-reaching goal for the region, given the countries and institutions attachment to traditional teaching methods deeply rooted on the central role of the teachers.

2. International mobility as added value

All reports portray international student mobility as an added-value to the programmes institutions offer and to the quality of education provided by them; which explains the fact that the great majority of interviewees see the implementation of multilateral credit transfer systems with favourable eyes; although with some scepticism based on the differences of the systems and the lack of more practical methods to bridge these gaps.

3. Lack of awareness on credit systems as a common challenge

Related to the above, country reports coincide in seeing common challenges that refer to lack of a generalized knowledge on credit systems and their functions among stakeholders (government officers, HEIs policy makers and international relations officers, teachers and students), as well as a lack of “a culture of credits” where competence is seen and understood as a process of obtaining knowledge and skills through modular structures.

5.4.2. Differences

Reports and interviews reveal differences among countries in the following aspects:

1. Disperse data on mobility
2. National regulations on credit systems and transferability
3. Attitude before change

1. Disperse data on mobility

Although reports suggest a tendency toward improving records of mobility at national and institutional levels, they all show disperse data available on student mobility, which is the result from the lack of a proper mechanism to gather and consolidate data in this regard.

2. National regulations on credit systems and transferability

Reports reveal important contrasts regarding the workability of credit transfer systems, such as the fact that although all countries account with national legal schemes to implement their credit systems, those frameworks vary greatly. For example, while Cambodia, Myanmar, Lao PDR (and to certain extent Vietnam) have unified credit systems, regulated by national laws that delineate measurement of workload and value of credits (typically based on contact hours), workload and even content of subjects. On the other side, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand and the Republic of Korea have set rules for their credit systems and transferability of credits allowing HEIs broader autonomy. China stands as a single exception as the central government has not established specific norms other than requesting HEIs to use academic credits in order to measure workloads.

Even if in all the countries regulations on academic accreditation exist; implementation at the institutional level varies widely. In some cases HEIs in a country are requested to adjust curricula into a modular and credit based system; however implementation and actual application may lag behind as it happens in Cambodia, Myanmar and most HEIs in Vietnam. On the other extreme there are cases where regulations are flexible, allowing HEIs to implement the credit systems according to their own criteria, as it happens in Japan.

3. Attitude before change

Reports evidence differences on the attitudes among people in HEIs, especially among managers and academicians in terms of carrying out necessary reforms to facilitate the share of information and to make courses come closer to modular structures. Interestingly all resource persons agree in that these positions affect the workability and potentials of credit transfer systems, as more conservative attitudes tend to put unnecessary obstacles that look technical but are easily solved through more open and positive attitudes.

5.5. CTS in the governments' eyes

All reports coincide in portraying the interest o and participation of governments in the region toward regionalization of HE. However an important gap this study found is the fact that most governments have only given partial support to international legal instruments with that goal.

As explained in the literature review central for this project are the Regional Convention on the Recognition of Studies, Diplomas, and Degrees in Higher Education in Asia and the Pacific, signed in Bangkok (1983) and its revised version the Asia-Pacific Regional Convention on the Recognition of Qualifications in Higher Education 2011, signed in Tokyo (2011).

Ratification of these agreements by governments serves as a *barometer* to “see the commitment countries are willing/ready to take to harmonize HE. Information in the country reports confirms what was observed in UNESCO’s website, where support to these Conventions can be deemed poor as only a few countries have signed and even less have ratified these international treaties.

In the case of the *Regional Convention on the Recognition of Studies, Diplomas, and Degrees in Higher Education in Asia and the Pacific* (UNESCO, 1983), only China signed and approved the agreement in 1984, The Republic of Korea accepted it in 1989; Lao PDR ratified the convention in 2003 and Indonesia also ratified it in 2008³.

In the case of the *Revised Asia-Pacific Regional Convention on the Recognition of Qualifications in Higher Education* (UNESCO, 2011), only Cambodia, China, Lao PDR and the Republic of Korea have signed the agreement in the same year⁴.

The information presented here calls for a serious reflection on why, even if most countries support the harmonization of HE, most governments remain hesitant to sign and ratify these instruments.

In this sense the work being carried out by SEAMEO RIHED and ADB through this project and the goals sought here come as a supporting framework to the goals set in those conventions by promoting the implementation of alternative mechanisms for harmonization through multilateral credit transfer.

With this frame in mind and from this point on the analysis presented in upcoming pages focuses on the trends and main features of the credit systems and credit transfer arrangements *within* each of the countries included.

The following chart summarizes main features of the credit systems in each country, their advantages and their challenges.

Table 11: Summary of findings on credit systems in the eyes of governments

Country	Features of credit systems	Advantages	Challenges	Features of Int’l student mobility
Cambodia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Centralized National guideline - Mostly bilateral agreements between HEIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consistent national systems - Autonomy of HEIs on decision of recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detraction of credit systems by HEIs due to competition for students - Quality issues - Language issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bilateralism - Typically outbound with recognition of degrees rather than credits upon return

³ Retrieved in March 2013 from

<http://www.unesco.org/eri/la/convention.asp?KO=13523&language=E&order=chronology>

⁴ Retrieved in March 2013 from [http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-](http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=48975&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html)

[URL_ID=48975&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html](http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=48975&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html)

Country	Features of credit systems	Advantages	Challenges	Features of Int'l student mobility
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accreditation Committee of Cambodia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial and human resources - Credit transfer used only domestic (permanent moves) - No guaranty of recognition 	
China	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralized credit system - Mostly bilateral agreements between HEIs - Recognition done: directly by HEIs, by conversion of subjects or credits by match of workload in hours 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Autonomy of HEIs on decision of recognition - Considering creation of national credit bank - Chinese Service Centre for Scholarly Exchange (CSCSE) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disperse practice in credit transfer - Weak common ground for credit transfer (multilateral) - Gaps in quality issues among HEIs and regions - No guaranty of recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bilateralism is wide spread - Domestic transfers based on alliances of HEIs (regionally or same tier) - Internationally participate in schemes like Campus Asia - Balance in and outbound
Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralized credit system - Mostly bilateral agreements between HEIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Autonomy of HEIs on decision of recognition - Positive and open attitude to credit transfers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disperse practice in credit transfer - No guaranty of recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bilateralism is wide spread - Participates in multilateral schemes in AUN and AIMS exchange programmes - Typically outbound
Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralized system with national guideline on credit system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National guideline allows autonomy of HEIs on decision of recognition - HEIs are requested to clearly explain their own credit systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disperse practice in credit transfer - No guaranty of recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bilateralism is wide spread - Active government promotion of mobility: 300.000 students plan; Global 30; global 30+, Campus Asia - Balance in and outbound
Lao PDR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Credit system → centralized guideline for HEIs to measure workload. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integral approach to credit system that is included in the national strategic plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disperse use of credits due to historic factors and structure of HEIs - Transfers for domestic and permanent moves - Quality issues - No guaranty of recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vertical recognition of degrees rather than credits - Typically outbound
Malaysia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralized credit system - Transfer of credits happens in 2 ways: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. transfer of workload (credits) b. credit exception or reduction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National guideline allows autonomy of HEIs on decision of recognition - Recognition of prior learning and developed advance standing system - flexibility - Malaysian Quality Agency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disperse practice - No guaranty of recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bilateralism is wide spread - Multilateral schemes like AUN and AIMS - Wide use of joint degree, twinning - Balance in and outbound

Country	Features of credit systems	Advantages	Challenges	Features of Int'l student mobility
Myanmar	- Centralized credit system. Homogeneity of curricula and grades	- Central system → consistent through the country - Recognition is guaranteed	- Credit transfer used only domestic (permanent moves) - Lack of flexibility - Decisions on recognition depend on government decision → poor HEIs autonomy	- Not yet participating of outbound mobility. Only inbound exchange (language programmes) - → recognition is up to sending HEI abroad
Thailand	- Decentralized credit system	- National guideline allows autonomy of HEIs on decision of recognition - Flexibility	- Disperse practice - No guaranty of recognition	- Bilateralism is wide spread - Participates in multilateral schemes in AUN and AIMS exchange programmes - Balance in and outbound
Vietnam	- Country wide reforms to promote use of credit systems as strategy for massification of HE	- Promotion of modular system - Recognition of credits for vertical mobility (intra-HEI)	- Disperse practice - Int'l horizontal recognition of credits not yet happening. - Vertical mobility based on recognition of degrees	- Typically outbound - Growing interest in participation of Int'l multilateral programmes (AUN and AIMS)
Republic of Korea	- National credit guideline	- National guideline allows autonomy of HEIs on decision of recognition - Recognition of prior learning	- Disperse practice - No guaranty of recognition	- Bilateralism is wide spread - Promotion of Int'l education in multilateral programmes: Campus Asia and Study Korea 200,000 - 2020 - Balance in and outbound

Cambodia

The country accounts with a national credit system however implementation at the HEIs level is not yet smooth; some HEIs are perceived by the government as manipulating the credit system due to financial reasons (detracting the spirit of the system to recruit more students, a trend that seems particularly visible among institutions in the private sector).

In terms of participation in credit transfer activities, important challenges arise for HEIs in Cambodia regarding ways to convince HEIs in other countries to cooperate through exchange programmes both for temporary and permanent activities (lack of appeal of local HEIs to attract foreign students). A clear feature of the mobility of students in the country is the evident number of students going for post graduate programmes abroad; whereby no credits are transferred but instead degrees are recognized.

At the time of writing the country is in the process of setting the Accreditation Committee of Cambodia (ACC), which delineates working concepts of the national credit system and should support developments toward more permeability of the education system in terms of accreditation.

The government promotes student mobility (domestic and international) by encouraging the use of the national credit system; however obstacles remain regarding application of credit transfer at the international level, especially due to issues of quality and language.

Although the national credit system allows for transferability of credits and qualifications, the system is only (for the time being) being used at the domestic level.

There is evident and strong support from the government for further development of the credit system, especially through policy guidelines for the HEIs. However some challenges remain ahead regarding issues of human and financial resources.

China

Although the overall planning of HE is a state matter in China, the country does not have a centralized credit system, therefore there are important differences in the use of credits and their transferability through HEIs the country.

Domestically transfer of credits happens in three ways: 1) Mutual recognition based on teaching communities established by some HEIs in major cities; 2) Credit transfer alliances among top tier and specialized HEIs; and 3) Cross-region transfer of academic credits.

Internationally the government of China promotes cooperation in education and exchanges focusing on the Asia-Pacific region, through arrangements like Campus Asia. At the individual level HEIs are involved in the transfer of credits through articulations and student exchange programmes with partner institutions bilaterally. This situation is particularly clear among the provinces in the south in relation to partner HEIs in Southeast Asia.

The most usual ways in which students' workloads are recognized are:

- 1) Recognition of courses done through: a) direct recognition; b) recognition by conversion and c) credit recognition. And
- 2) Transfer of credits that refer to: matching of course hours and conversion of grades.

The country report and interviews done for the research suggest that the government of China is considering to create a national framework for the management of academic credits, however it faces a number of important challenges like equity in terms of access and evaluation, lack of resources (human and financial) and the wide differences among HEIs in the country and among its regions.

The government is committed to facilitating student mobility and for that purpose it created the Chinese Service Centre for Scholarly Exchange (CSCSE), which provides information on HEIs, HE systems, qualifications, legitimacy issues and exchanges to students, national HEIs and employers. The agency plays a major role in facilitating recognition and understanding of contents from courses and programmes taken abroad; likewise it eases the access to academic information; however it does not have authority to make decisions on recognition and transferability of credits or other forms of student workloads, which remains a right of the receiving HEIs.

According to interviews carried for this study and to the country report there is growing interest among stakeholders in China toward the creation of a *Credit Bank*, as a mechanism that will help learners keep track of records and qualifications, while it will help HEIs' personnel and employers understand what learners have been doing while studying abroad and what their knowledge and skills should be according to curricula and syllabi the students have been involved with. Although the project is still in its infancy it appears promising in terms of facilitating understanding of academic information.

Indonesia

The country does not have a centralized credit system so each HEI has created its own mechanisms for credit transfer based on bilateral agreements. As a result this has brought about a very permeable attitude among stakeholders towards creating a mechanism to further facilitate mobility through credit transfer.

The legal system allows HEIs an ample level of autonomy to establish their own contacts with foreign institutions in order to create channels for cooperation and partnerships.

The government supports internationalization of HE by providing a number of scholarships for international mobility of students participating in exchange programmes like in the context of AUN using ACTS to mobilize students and have their credits recognized among member universities or the participation of the country in the AIMS programme which uses UCTS for the transfer of credits.

Japan

The country has a decentralized credit system; its national legal frame “Standards for Establishing Universities” works mostly as a guideline for HEIs and among its lines it explains how credit systems *should be* implemented in order for credit to help measurement of students’ workloads. The scheme does not set specific regulations regarding grading systems as long as they are transparent and coherent; hence HEIs are free to choose how to grade students.

The framework defines credits as *a measurement for workloads*; however HEIs in Japan are free to decide the credits they assign to the work students are expected to carry to successfully complete a course.

As the system is decentralized in terms of how HEIs set and apply their credits to subjects, the government mostly focuses on how each institution handles its own system at the macro level in order to ensure quality of the programmes.

Among the good practices spotted it was found that HEIs are requested to present clear outlines of the methods they use to organize courses, the contents they provide, schedules grading systems and the like so as to make the systems easily understandable.

The government of Japan seems to be very active in seeking to promote mobility of students at the international level with increasing interest in the Southeast and East Asia regions. HEIs in the country are participating in a number of exchange programmes like *300,000 international Student Plan, Global 30, Global 30 Plus* or *Campus Asia*, all of which promote the use of decentralized credit transfer agreements set directly by the HEIs.

Lao PDR

The country accounts with a national framework that sets its credit system which is included in the country’s *Education Strategic Vision up to 2020*. The notion of academic credits is embodied in the systems and standards of quality control, administration, professional education management and curricular development under the direction of the Ministry of Education and Sports.

Implementation of the credit system in Lao PDR faces some challenges related to the historical factors in the educational system that was traditionally attached to the notion of academic courses based on semesters, inherited from the French tradition, which seems to remain as an obstacle to the modularization of study courses.

The legal framework in the country sets guidelines for HEIs in terms of how students' workload should be measured in terms of time and learning outcomes, however actual implementation at the HEIs still lags behind. The system also establishes a grading system based on letters (A-D) and can easily be translated into numerical values (4-0). The grading process is based on two methods: 1) groups' study results or 2) ranks of scores (A≥93%, B+=86-93%, B=78-86%, C+=71-78%, C=64-71%, D+=57-64%, D=50-57%, F<5).

Myanmar

The country accounts with a centralized credit system established by a national law that is compulsory to all HEIs in the country. The scheme delineates aspects like duration of semesters, length of academic courses and content and amount of credits to be granted. The system is implemented throughout the country to facilitate mobility of students, which is achieved by a homogeneous curriculum for careers and HEIs of the same kind.

The scheme determines a grading system that is compulsory to all HEIs. Although it is said that the programme is meant to preserve institutions autonomy, in fact HEIs receiving transfer students are in principle compelled to accept and recognize the credits of mobile students regardless of issues of quality in education among different institutions. Final decisions on recognition and accreditation, especially for those related to international mobility are still handled at the public ministry level.

The credit system is described by the report as working smoothly for the mobility of students *within* the country, however it is still uncertain what will happen once the HE system opens and faces more international standards. The government seems keen into implementing reforms that will lead to more autonomy for the HEIs and to promote internationalization. According to the country report and interviews held for this study, it is widely believed that the implementation of its national credit system will facilitate the international flow of students in the near future.

Malaysia

There are two structures to handle the transfer of credits in Malaysia, one is transferability of students' workload in the form of credits and the other is credit exception and reduction of credits. (In the first case credits are transferred among HEIs and included in the students' transcripts with same, similar or different grades; in the second model, reduction of credits means that earned credits from other HEIs qualify the students to be *exempted* from taking similar subjects at the home institutions, here no grades are counted in the student's GPA).

The credit system in the country promotes continuity of studies and accreditation of prior learning, like in the case of *Advance Standing*.

Credit transferability in Malaysia is decentralized and it is based on the implementation of memorandums of understanding and memorandums of agreement between HEIs directly. General guidelines have been set by the Malaysian Quality Agency in saying for example that for credits to be transferable, the title of courses and their contents must be same or very similar, which in practice may set major hindrances to mobility if the principle was effectively applied. Most student mobility activities are treated by HEIs case-to-case.

Thailand

HEIs in the country are entitled the right to organize and structure their programmes with a great level of autonomy. There is not centralized system for the use and transfer of credits and the same applies to grading systems. Although there are some common or usual practices there is not one central set of rules for transferability of credits either at the domestic or cross boarder realms. This has greatly facilitated the signing of direct bilateral agreements between HEIs themselves.

The Thai government through its Office ho Higher Education Commission (OHEC), has participated actively in the development of mechanisms seeking to expand student mobility; OHEC is known to actively encourage HEIs in Thailand to proactively cooperate with counterparts at bilateral and multilateral levels, for example through its participation in UMAP and its support to programmes such as the exchanges organized under the schemes of AUN and AIMS.

Vietnam

The government has sought to bring reforms to its HE system to make it more accessible and open to wider areas of its population; in so doing it has actively promoted the implementation of the credit system among its HEIs as a strategy towards *massification* of the HE. It promotes the use of credits for the mobility of students at graduate and post graduate levels and more recently by looking to expand the traditional domestic mobility of students towards more internationalized arenas.

According to interviews carried out for this research and to the country report, so far, and in most cases of students participating of mobility programmes recognition of qualifications is based on *recognition of degrees rather than credits*, however there seems to be a movement towards opening the attitudes of those in charge of making these decisions toward wider acceptance of courses based on modular structures rather than time based courses and programmes. This coincides with the interest of the government in supporting and spreading the use of credits for the measurement of students' workloads.

There are differences in the way students' workloads are treated by HEIs when dealing with domestic and international qualifications in the case of vertical mobility for international qualifications the rule is the recognition of degrees; however domestic vertical mobility presents a particular case because mobility typically takes place within traditional areas of mono-disciplinary movements; whereby students typically go for higher degrees in the same HEIs where they obtained their lower degrees. In these cases recognition of credits, by rule is done in full. However when students change the HEIs as they move up, recognition practices are more varied as qualifications may be linked to total and partial recognitions and in some cases non-recognition at all. Final decisions on whether recognition is granted or not belong to the administrators and academicians of the receiving institutions.

Regarding international recognition Vietnam shows a clear tendency towards recognizing *degrees* for courses completely finished abroad, while temporary mobility and the use of credits for short-term exchanges have, normally, not been recognized.

The Republic of Korea

The country has a well centralized educational system that is controlled by the government through its Ministry of Education, Science and Technology, the HE system has established regulations that unify academic procedures and HEIs are required to conform to national

laws. A common credit system is set therein and is applied throughout the country as HEIs are requested to adjust to it; however they are in charge of the actual management and transfer of academic credits.

The use of credits to measure students' workloads is widely spread and regularly used by mobile students to avoid repetition and for progression. Although there is a clear definition of what credits are and how they measure student's workload, as set in the national framework there is not a legal scheme to regulate *transfers* among HEIs.

Thus HEIs have the authority to determine their own transfer systems as long as they respect the legal framework, which provides specifications for example in defining the "credit hours" based on amounts of weeks and hours per semesters or quarters.

Mobility of students happens typically within the context of bilateral agreements between HEIs, and in some cases under multilateral arrangements. The government promotes mobility both domestic and internationally and has an active policy towards making Korean HE more visible and attractive especially due to the country's demographic trends. Examples of this can be found in programmes like Campus Asia and the Study Korea 200,000 - 2020.

The country is developing its National Information Centre aiming to facilitate the flow and share of information for all HE students in the country and abroad.

5.6. CTS the HEIs' eyes

Different from the views presented by the governments regarding credit systems and the transferability therein who see from a national strategic point of view, HEIs see and *live* credit systems as everyday issues in their interaction with other HEIs and with the students. They are the actual implementers of the systems.

The following table summarizes findings on credit systems at the country level according to the views presented by the HEIs.

Table 12: Summary of findings on credit systems in the eyes of HEIs

Country	Advantages of credit systems in use	Challenges to credit system in use	Technical features of credit transfer in use	Student mobility issues
Cambodia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open attitude of HEIs to recognize Int'l credits - Consistent use of national credit system among HEIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High competition among HEIs for students detracts spirit of credit system - Quality issues (domestic and int'l) - Decentralized academic information → difficult access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bilateral transfer is widespread (domestically) - Transfers analyzed case-by-case 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Imbalanced acceptance of inward and outward credit transfer
China	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High autonomy at HEIs to set credit systems and decide on recognition - Use of credit system to promote international contact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disperse practice - Credit systems typically imbedded in academic year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralized procedure - Bilateral transfer is widespread (domestic and Int'l) - Multilateral transfer as consortia among HEIs → direct negotiation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Few HEIs participate in Campus Asia programme - Most mobility of students is bilateral (HEI to HEI)

Country	Advantages of credit systems in use	Challenges to credit system in use	Technical features of credit transfer in use	Student mobility issues
			- Transfers analyzed case-by-case	
Indonesia	- HEIs are autonomous to decide on recognition of credits	- Disperse practice	- Decentralized procedure - Bilateral transfer is widespread (domestic and internationally) - transfers analyzed case-by-case	- Most mobility of students is bilateral (HEI to HEI) Few HEIs participate in AUN and AIMS exchange programmes
Japan	- Credit system regulated by law that allows autonomy to HEIs in their implementation	- Disperse practice - Lack of systematization and spread use of personal decision on credit recognition - slow process of setting consortia	- Bilateral treatment of transfer is widespread (domestically) - Transfers analyzed case-by-case	- Growing interest among HEIs due to support from government - Most mobility of students is bilateral (HEI to HEI) - Few HEIs participate in Campus Asia programme
Lao PDR	- National guideline	- Disperse practice - Poor accountability in implementation of credit system at HEIS - Difficult curricular transparency - Problem of total or partial recognition related to school fee issues	- Hybrid credit-semester system for accreditation - Transfers analyzed case-by-case - Wide spread recognition subject-by-subject	- Attachment of fees to course/semester hinders mobility (and transfer) - Mobility happens almost entirely outbound
Malaysia	- Personnel at HEIs are well aware of credit systems and their use - Decentralized system allows HEIs autonomy to recognize or not	- Disperse practice - Formal strictness for equivalence toward recognition	- Various forms of transfer exist for domestic and Int'l moves (based on credits, courses, etc) - Transfers analyzed case-by-case	- Few HEIs participate in AIMS and AUN exchange programmes - Most mobility of students is bilateral (HEI to HEI) - Wide use of double degrees or twinning
Myanmar	- Uniform nationwide credit system - credit transfer practice domestically based on same modular structure among same kind HEIs	- HEIs do not have autonomy to decide on recognition - Compatibility of national system with Int'l ones yet not proven	- Centralized system by the government	- Most mobility of students is bilateral (HEI to HEI) Few HEIs participate in AUN and AIMS exchange programmes
Thailand	- Decentralized system allows HEIs autonomy to recognize or not	- Disperse practice	- Transfers analyzed case-by-case	- Few HEIs participate in AIMS and AUN exchange programmes

Country	Advantages of credit systems in use	Challenges to credit system in use	Technical features of credit transfer in use	Student mobility issues
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Most mobility of students is bilateral (HEI to HEI) - Growing interest in double degrees or twinning
Vietnam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Personnel at HEIs are aware of advantages of credit system but implementation is disperse - Decentralized system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only a few HEIs account with autonomy to decide on recognition of foreign qualifications - Credit transfer used domestically only - Different procedures for domestic and Int'l recognition (vertical) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Horizontal transfer allowed among HEIs (dealt bilaterally) - Int'l recognition of degrees but not credits - Transfers analyzed case-by-case 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Few HEIs participate in AUN's programmes and the country is joining AIMS program at the time of writing - Growing interest in double degrees or twinning
Republic of Korea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralized system allows HEIs autonomy to set their own credit systems and to recognize or not - Personnel at HEIs are aware of advantages of credit system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disperse practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transfers analyzed case-by-case 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Few HEIs participate in Campus Asia programme - Most mobility of students is bilateral (HEI to HEI)

Cambodia

HEIs in Cambodia are encouraged by its government to sign MoUs with other institutions at the international level so as to increase networking and exposure to international standards and procedures, although many institutions in the country are still constrained due to especially quality and financial issues.

Interviewees during the data collection agree in that there is fierce competence among HEIs in the country as, especially private institutions, seek to attract more students into their programmes by using and even manipulating the national credit system, which, as explained, raises the question of quality in the provision of those programmes.

Transfer of credits among HEIs domestically seems to be closely relates to strategies set typically by private universities on how to attract and retain the students (holding students hostage) and avoiding transfers to other institutions. Internationally the transfer of credits seems to work more smoothly when done inwards (from a foreign institution to a local one), as recognition seems to work better and faster benefiting incoming students; however the reverse situation appears taunting as foreign HEIs tend to distrust the quality of the services provided by Cambodian institutions.

Although the country participates in multilateral agreements for transitory student mobility using different schemes for transfer of credits such as AUN using ACTS, there is still a clear imbalanced situation between outgoing and incoming number of students.

Cambodia still lacks an information centre that centralizes and provides information for HEIs and students in general and for mobile students in particular on programmes and support schemes. Both institutions and students alike seem expectant on the setting of such a

mechanism to help them better understand options for mobility and tools for transfer and recognition of qualifications. Interviews with HEIs suggest that they look at the government in the hope to find guidelines that are both clear and respectful of their autonomy.

China

Most HEIs have accreditation systems that are typically embedded in the academic year. Because there is not a unified set of national rules on accreditation, HEIs have the right to determine the number of credits attached to a study course and their own total credit requirements for graduation.

The country report and interviews carried out for the research suggest a tendency among HEIs to use credits to promote students autonomy and innovation and in parallel with that, more institutions in China seek to create bridges with HEIs outside the country through transfer of credits set in MoUs at bilateral and multilateral levels.

As mentioned, the main strategies HEIs use for the transfer of credits at the domestic level is by setting consortia and cooperative partnerships with other institutions that promote mutual recognition based on teaching communities in major cities, alliances of top tier universities that mutually accept to transfer their credits among themselves, more clearly among specialized HEIs, and cross-region transfer of credits among HEIs with certain common features.

Internationally HEIs in China are involved in schemes for credit transfer typically managed bilaterally and in exchange programmes that articulate multilateral parties like Campus Asia. Exchange students returning to home HEIs in China go through evaluation of qualifications and the decisions on recognition of credits and grades taken by the home institution.

As there is not a centralized procedure to transfer credits, HEIs interviewed perceive this as a positive aspect of the HE system in China, for this allows autonomy to decide what and how much to recognize from the credits mobile students wish to transfer.

Indonesia

Because there is not one single standard credit system in the country, according to the report transfers of credits happen with sporadic frequency and are partial in nature as students may be requested to make up for gaps; HEIs are free to transfer academic credits, which in most cases happens on a case-by-case base and on bilateral agreements that take the form of memorandums of understanding among domestic and overseas HEIs. The guiding principle in the transfer of credits for institutions seem to be a “responsible freedom”, meaning that every HEI has the right to build its own comparative advantages according to its field and competence.

Some HEIs in the country participate in international networks and programmes that apply credit transfer, such as AUN and AIMS exchange programmes at the multilateral level, while there are also bilateral agreements that allow for the transfer of credits in the format of “sandwich” students exchanges, twinning and double degree programmes.

According to the country report executives in HEIs in the country seem to agree in that credit systems foster proactive attitudes among the students and tend to boost their curiosity and more out looking perceptions of their careers and interests.

Japan

The country accounts with a legal framework that provides HEIs general guidelines on how the credit system should work. However there are not specifications regarding transfer of credits, nor on grading policies, which give HEIs a great level of autonomy in deciding matters related to recognition and accreditation of foreign qualifications.

Previous research done in the country by re resource person demonstrates a broad set of different practices in the way HEIs handle credit transfers, for example about half of them do not have any policy for transfer of courses for subjects taken in foreign partner institutions, while another important group of HEIs reveal having internal regulations that delineate how credits and subjects from other HEIs are treated, and yet a smaller group of institutions handles the transfer of credits on a case-by-case base.

The report suggests wide discrepancies and levels of willingness among HEIs and personnel working as international relations officers and those in charge of recognition towards accepting or not foreign credits. The same is observed about transfer of grades.

A number of issues have been put forward among HEIs regarding the implementation of credit transfers and these relate to: a) the speediness of processes at the institutional level to actually transfer credits; b) the differences of grading policies among HEIs; c) the issue of recognition of subjects that do not exist in the receiving HEIs; d) the fact that not many students show interest in participating of credit transfer activities; and e) the slow process of establishing arrangements for exchange in the form of consortia.

Attitudes in HEIs towards internationalization and transferability of credits is rapidly changing as a consequence of the strong financial support the government is giving to the HEIs for them to *open their campuses*. More flexible views in the management of transfers can be seen for example in the way HEIs issue transcripts of students by accepting large amount of credits into one special subject or by accepting foreign subjects exactly as they are presented by the host HEIs with their original titles in English into the students' transcripts.

Lao PDR

According to the country report although the country accounts with a national framework setting a credit system, awareness among personnel in HEIs and students on its logic, benefits, and procedures is limited; in fact a hybrid mixture of credit and semester-based systems seems to be the rule in use among HEIs in the country at the time of granting credits to courses students take.

This reflect the fact that HEIs have pending issues regarding transparency and accountability on the implementation of the system, especially given the differences between public and private HEIs, quality of education and provision of what is in the curricula may not really be implemented in the courses provided. Curricular transparency appears as a major challenge given that syllabi may not be well structured, with unclear learning objectives and evaluation methods. A major hindrance in this sense is the fact that curricula are typically kept confidential by HEIs.

The transfer of credits is typically managed at the individual level, on a case-by-case fashion, where students and teachers decide whether credits can be transferred, almost by rule by "replacing" by equivalences based on the titles and contents of the courses. HEIs seem to agree in that transfer of credits is a difficult decision as it includes long and complicated procedures and also because there is no enabling instrument that can be used as official reference for decision making on the transferability of the credits of a course.

Although implementation of credit system is perceived as advantageous issues remain for example in the management of fees (based on semesters rather than modules or courses). Another issue is how to deal with total or partial recognition and its linkage to school fees.

Malaysia

According to the country report HEIs in Malaysia are well acquainted with the use of credits to measure students' workload and their transferability. Credit transfer in Malaysia happens at the national level *within* HEIs; at the *inter-public universities* level; and at the *inter-public-private universities* level; and at the cross-border level as *intra-local-foreign universities*.

Different credit systems are used among HEIs specially related to student mobility programmes both domestic and internationally. Using credits for double degree and twinning programmes appears as a wide spread practice. Likewise, the use of credits for advance standing (lifelong learning) and progression of learning to higher levels of education are well accepted among most HEIs in the country.

As universities are given wide autonomy to decide on the way they manage the credit system and on the recognition of credits from other HEIs, mobility schemes are typically managed at the university and bilateral level through collaborative schemes set in MoUs, a few institutions participate in multilateral programmes as well, for example through AUN's and AIMS' exchange programmes.

Applicability of credit system for the transfer of students' workload faces an important challenge in that the Malaysian Quality Agency set as criteria for transferability the condition that the "content of courses must be exactly the same". As mentioned, this constrains chances for transfer as courses taken in other HEIs may be similar but very rarely will they have exactly the same contents or even titles. In most cases of credit transfer, the working criteria is a case-by-case approach analyzing each student's situation that may be fairer but is also time consuming.

Myanmar

The country report and the interviews carried locally reveal that as the credit system is centralized by a national law, all HEIs conform to it and apply it into their curricula, creating a homogeneous landscape in the country, at least, in terms of structure of programmes where mobility and recognition of credits are guaranteed to the students even if this raises important concerns among HEIs in terms of quality of the education provided by other HEIs.

As the educational system is centralized under the Ministry of Education, curricular matters and syllabi, content of modules for all respective subjects are the same as they are the result of the decisions and directions led by the Board of Studies for each subject in arts and science universities. This also simplifies the transfer of grades, as all HEIs use the same scheme to evaluate the performance of students.

In the cases of domestic mobility, transfer of credits presents a consistent landscape, however there are concerns about the lack of autonomy of HEIs in order to evaluate and recognize credits of new incoming students. The transfer system seems to function smoothly at the procedural phase as there is one common criterion for decision making.

At the international level, mobility of students and the transfer of workload are only being practiced vertically, where typically recognition of qualification happens based on degrees rather than on credits. Temporary exchanges of outgoing students at the undergraduate level

are practically not existent, and when they do happen generally HEIs cannot recognize the credits students bring as the subjects the students take abroad are different from those offered in the country. For the case of temporary incoming foreign students (typically in language programmes) credits issued by Myanmar HEIs are usually recognized in the students home institutions upon return.

Thailand

According to the country report the Office of Higher Education Commission (OHEC) provides HEIs in the country guidelines for their organization and function. Through the Thai Qualifications Framework the government gives a common direction to the education system in terms of policies, standards on quality and some procedures such as the implementation of credits, degrees and qualifications.

However decisions on management of credit systems and the transferability of students' workload belong to the authorities of the HEIs. As such they account with autonomy on decisions related to recognition of credits from other institutions. Likewise, HEIs are free to decide grading systems.

HEIs in Thailand are engaged in various programmes related to credit transfer, which happens at all levels (under and post-graduate). Most of the activities take place based on bilateral agreements signed by the institutions themselves. Multilateral arrangements are also used as some HEIs participate in programmes like AUN's transfers based on ACTS or the AIMS programme. Thus the use of memorandums of understanding and agreements is widely spread.

Some HEIs participate in multilateral exchange programmes like AIMS and AUN where students' workloads are shared and transferred by using the procedure set in UCTS and ACTS (ASEAN credit transfer system) respectively. Credit transfer and exchange of students among Thai and foreign HEIs include activities like internships and tailor-made programmes and training sessions designed by the institutions themselves.

Vietnam

The report and interviews reveal that the idea of credit transfer systems is well known among HEIs in Vietnam however implementation at the university level varies considerably; bilateral (university-to-university) arrangements appear among the most usual ways to share information. There is growing interest among HEIs in developing more bilateral and multilateral transfer systems however there is still high concern about the autonomy that institutions are given to make their own decisions regarding recognition of foreign credits.

In terms of vertical mobility and credit transfer Vietnam shows some differences between domestic and international moves as Vietnamese students tend to commit with one institution where they complete their undergraduate and graduate studies; hence degrees and credits are normally recognized within the same HEIs. However when students move up to a different institution, the Ministry of Education regulates that the rector of the new HEIs will decide, case by case, on whether to recognize in full or partly the degrees and credits of the new students.

Although international mobility attracts more interest among students, HEIs still find it difficult to recognize foreign credits from temporary exchanges. By rule institutions only

recognize credits from “partner universities” in the cases where they account with double degree or joint programmes.

Except for specific universities, most HEIs are limited in their autonomy to decide on recognition issues. At the time of writing two national universities were members of AUN and participate of some of UMAP’s activities and networks where foreign credits are recognized in full.

A few HEIs participate in bilateral programmes with foreign HEIs in neighbouring countries e.g. China, Lao PDR and Cambodia; where under the supervision of Ministry of Education, they agree to get “one-side credit recognition”, thus credits accumulated by international students in Vietnam are recognized at their home HEIs but not the other way around.

According to the country report and the interviews, although there are high expectations among HEIs to be able to participate in international student mobility activities with other HEIs in the region, usually transfer of credits is associated with vertical progression rather than for horizontal and temporary movements.

In this sense Vietnam’s recent joining the AIMS programme brings in new opportunities for credit transfer for short exchanges for undergraduate students in the near future.

The Republic of Korea

Although HE system is monitored controlled by the government HEIs have wide autonomy in regards to the implementation of transfer initiatives. They are free to participate of activities with partner universities both at the domestic and international realms through signing of memorandums of understanding and other instruments of cooperation.

HEIs are participating in bilateral and multilateral agreements that include the transfer of credits; one example of this is the involvement of some of them in programmes like Campus Asia.

Transfer of credits is a well known practice as in general HEIs account with similar regulations and procedures that are based on a unified set of national laws that serve as guidelines that set no restriction on transferability itself.

Credit transfer typically happens as the result of following some steps that include: 1) students filling up an online application form that provide the necessary information for the audit at the receiving institution; 2) a “Department Head Review” takes place in the receiving institution to check on similarities and relevance of courses to be transferred -the review of credits may include an interview with the students if necessary-; and 3) a “Review by the Office of International Affairs” that seeks to give systematic consistency with previous decisions on recognition of credits at the HEIs.

The autonomy provided to HEIs in these decisions is perceived as a facilitator towards increasing mobility of students because it makes the HEIs the owners of their programmes and responsible agents for the quality (and attractiveness) of programmes offered.

5.7. CTS the students’ eyes

The last part of this chapter seeks to give students a space to make their views known. Although much deeper research is highly recommended in this sense, the following pages show how policies and decisions that are delineated by previous stakeholders (governments and HEIs) affect the course of the careers of the students and more broadly their lives.

Because most students that participate in activities of mobility are affected by the rules of transfer and recognition of workload they usually understand how systems work and they may offer creative ideas to make credit transfer more effective.

The following table summarizes findings from the interviews resource persons held with students regarding credit systems at the national level.

Table 13: Advantages and challenges students perceive about credit systems in use

Country	Advantages perceived by students	Challenges and difficulties perceived by students
Cambodia	- Positive views of credit system to facilitate mobility	- Most students are still not deeply aware of functions of systems
China	- Positive views of credit system to facilitate mobility	- Most students are still not deeply aware of functions of systems
Indonesia	- Positive views and growing awareness of credit system to facilitate mobility	- Students fear systems may not be effective for recognition of workload abroad → hinders mobility
Japan	- Positive views of credit system to facilitate mobility	- Disperse practice is confusing for students - Students perceive “too much strictness” in procedures and content requirement for recognition - Students have problems with recognition of core and selective courses - Disperse management of grades and use of pass or fail marks - Inconsistencies in some twinning programmes
Lao PDR	- Positive views of credit system to facilitate mobility (specially Int’l)	- Poor understanding of credit systems and their functions
Malaysia	- Positive views and understanding of credit system to facilitate mobility	- Lack of interest among most students to participate in mobility programmes - General association of the idea of credit transfer with the recognition of minors and selective courses only
Myanmar	- Students understand well the system for domestic transfer only	- Lack of recognition of int’l credits hinders that kind of mobility
Thailand	- Positive views and understanding of credit system to facilitate mobility - Growing interest in mobility programmes in SEA	- Mobility is highly associated to destination HEIs and their prestige (determining factor for mobility) - Lack of certainty on recognition by credit systems upon return from exchange programmes hinders mobility
Vietnam	- Positive views and growing awareness of how credit systems work	- Students do not yet see the connection between credit transfer and temporary Int’l mobility

		- Int'l mobility is perceived as a risk factor as there is no guaranty of recognition of credits from abroad
Republic of Korea	- Positive views and understanding of credit system to facilitate mobility	- Lack of centralized information systems hinders used of credit transfer mechanisms - Credit transfer systems are associated to transfer of selective and optional courses only

Cambodia

According to the interviews carried out with Cambodian students, most of them agree in their wish to see the HE system to further develop in terms of quality of the educational provision, in the quality of teachers and in having more access to international exposure. Due to the history of the country, in general students do not seem have a deep understanding of what credit systems are for, how they work or the possibilities they may bring to their careers. Although students would like to have international experiences they still do not seem to know how to make use of the channels that credit transfer may offer them specially in terms of saving time and money for courses they may take abroad or in other HEIs. According to the country report this may be changing rapidly.

Like other countries students are turning to the World Wide Web for information, however there seems to be agreement in that information available from HEIs and from the government on credit systems and the transferability of credits is still scarce and disperse.

China

Interviews carried out in China suggest that the concept of academic credits and their transferability is not widely understood by students, and typically only those participating in exchange programmes seem to be aware of what the systems are meant to do.

The country report asserts that there seems to be agreement among students in thinking that credit transfer is meant to avoid repetitive learning experiences and to have their workload recognized after the completion of exchange programmes by their home HEIs. And also in that whatever subjects students take they should be seen in a conductive and continuous pathway of coherent learning.

Some students seem to agree more on the idea that credit transfer should take place as an “inter-university” matter (institutional approach), while others see it more as “inter-subject” matter (modular approach).

Indonesia

According to the country report students seem to agree in that credit transfer systems provide flexibility for them to follow more personalized programmes and wider access to courses that are not offered in their home HEIs. However it looks as if they *fear* the risk of having to face situations in which personnel in charge of recognizing their workload at their home HEIs may eventually require them for too much detailed information on the courses they took while on exchange and also for very high levels of percentages of equivalences among the subjects rather than focusing on facilitating their progress into graduation.

Japan

Research carried out on students' perceptions by the resource person on credit transfer shows important differences regarding inbound and outbound students. Differences relate to the amount of students who were able to transfer their credits back to their home HEIs after an exchange programme, and how much of that credit was recognized (in full or partially). Practice shows that in the majority of cases students returning to home HEIs in Japan were able to have their credits recognized after completion of a number of procedures and by presenting certain documentation to support their claims.

Major obstacles mentioned at the time of recognizing foreign credits relate to the fact that many credits did or did not relate to core subjects as opposed to optional courses. Another issue is the level of similarities among subjects and related to this a major obstacle is what to do with subjects that do not exist in home HEIs.

Management of foreign grades is of major concern. Research done by Hotta on this shows that only 2/3 of the respondents who participated in exchange programmes were able to transfer grades, out of which over 50% could only transfer with a "passing" mark, rather than with a mark describing the performance of the student in the courses they had taken.

An apparent contradiction that Hotta's research found was that students participating in twinning programmes reported that in many cases they were only able to transfer credits allocated for elective subjects, while core subjects were more difficult to have recognized by their home HEIs, even if exchanges had taken place within the framework of previously agreed arrangements by the host and home HEIs.

Most students participating in transfer credit activities seem to have received orientations and institutional support both before and after departure for exchange programmes, while only a few were actually requested by the home institutions to fill a study plan or sign a learning agreement before departure, which may have been the cause of difficulties for accreditation upon return to home HEIs.

A number of special obstacles for the implementation of credit transfer were identified by the report in areas like: a) definition of academic hours (which basically consists of 45 minutes); b) differences in the levels of the credits and the distribution of time per learning activities contained in a credit; c) account of teaching hours; d) differences in the complexity and difficulty of graduate exchange programmes; e) extreme exactness required for comparison of curricula and syllabi; f) treatment of core and selective subjects; g) and treatment of "Japanese Seminar Classes", which have special requirements that make them particularly difficult for comparison in terms of workload.

Lao PDR

According to the country report Laotian students seem to be more interested in obtaining a diploma than acquiring knowledge and skills, and this attitude greatly hinders interest in the students' part towards learning and understanding the use of the credit system. However in recent years students seem to have become more aware on the need to access better education, not only quantitative but also qualitatively.

A major problem among students wishing to participate in international credit transfer activities in the country is their proficiency in foreign languages so as to access study programmes at the international level.

Malaysia

Students in Malaysia seem to be aware on the practicality of credit systems and that schemes to transfer academic credits help them acquire more flexible ways through their careers. In general they associate the idea of credit transfer to minors and elective courses rather than to basic and compulsory core courses within specialized fields.

Credit transfer is perceived as a peripheral aspect of their education, typically related to the “international office” and some “internationally committed academicians” of their HEIs trying to promote mobility and internationalization of education. However in general not many students seem to show interest in participating in mobility activities.

Myanmar

Myanmar students seem to be aware on the functions of the credit system as they are actually using it to transfer from HEIs to HEIs within the country. As curricula are set by the Ministry of Education with the cooperation of the Boards of Studies, there is not much understanding among students on the use and practicality of elective and optional subjects. In line with this although students may be interested in participating of temporary exchanges and international mobility programmes the idea is still new to the students in the country, at the same time as credits from HEIs abroad cannot be transferred into Myanmar HEIs students’ participation in these kinds of activities is hindered because if they do –go on short-term exchanges-, they will need to stay longer in the institution to graduate.

Thailand

As HEIs in the country typically provide information on credit transfer activities students seem to be well informed on how credit systems work and what their goals are.

When deciding to embark on credit transfer activities there is a “palpable concern” among students and parents regarding the name and reputation of the HEIs where students will go, which also relates to the destination countries. According to the country report in many cases these are the most central aspects at the time of deciding where to have their international learning experiences.

Because of this, the position in international rankings of host HEIs is an important element either fostering or hindering mobility and transfer of workload. Another factor determining these decisions are the certainty of having their credits recognized upon return to the home HEIs, most students and parents do not wish to delay graduations longer than necessary for the sake of a cultural experience.

According to the report, there seems to be a change of attitudes among students in Thailand towards wishing to participate in exchange programmes in new and alternative destinations in Southeast Asia.

Vietnam

According to the country report although students seem to understand the logic and purposes of the credit system as implementation is disperse among HEIs students do not seem to see mobility as a goal in itself. Also as recognition of foreign credits is typically not recognized students tend to see credit transfer activities more as a “risk factor” that may in fact cause

them to delay their graduations as workloads and achievements obtained in foreign HEIs will not be recognized when based on temporary exchanges.

The Republic of Korea

According to the country report students have a comprehensive understanding of the credit system and the transferability factor related to it as they face problems with decisions on courses they should take when they go on exchange. There seems to be agreement among students in that the procedures for credit transfer are not simple or standard, and that in many cases they need to learn from their peers how to carry the process rather than by having a centralized unit of information. Apparently students need to go through the regulations of their own schools to understand how to do it and in that sense access to HEIs' information online appears the only way to do it.

Some students manifested feeling constrained as the credits they were able to transfer are taken only as optional courses while core courses are more difficult to have recognized. According to the report students seem to agree in that the credit transfer systems should be simple, fair and managed electronically. While most of them also agree in that automatic recognition of the credits is the easiest way to go through their careers without unnecessary delays for going on exchange.

5.8. Conclusion

This chapter has *explored* the situation of credit systems in the region and the mechanisms used for the transferability of credits among HEIs and countries with focus on the perception of how they work.

Previous pages evidence a colourful landscape on credit systems in the region that create both a fertile soil for harmonization but also a thorny path for those in charge of negotiating and implementing necessary changes to further facilitate the understanding, comparison and recognition of students' workloads, achievements and qualifications.

All reports suggest that diversity in HE systems among countries and HEIs is perceived as a source of potentials rather than a point of divergence. In the past gaps and differences among HE systems were typically dealt with inaction, basically by focusing in strategies that were inward looking and at the HEIs level. However regional integration and globalization are rapidly changing that, which can be seen especially in a change of attitude towards otherness by all main stakeholders. Credit transfer systems set rules (typically agreed) however what makes those rules actually work is the attitude of those applying the rules.

An important aspect to emphasise from the comparison of the country reports is that most stakeholders hold positive views towards the use of credit systems, and they agree on the practicality of credit systems in rendering HEIs more transparent and open.

By contrasting the country reports one can perceive that in most cases stakeholders agree in that the more autonomy is given to HEIs at the time of evaluating and deciding on recognition of foreign qualifications and grades the more feasible, the more effective and fairer the task appears to be.

The analysis of the country reports show crucial interlocking issues that are calling for action when looking at the goals credit transfer systems set and how they are implemented at the institutional level -in whatever form of mobility- to facilitate recognition and transfer of students' academic efforts and qualifications. These refer to:

1. The need to develop communication channels and standardized practices to facilitate the understanding and interpretation of subjects to be transferred (contents and outcomes, effort required, quality, depth, relevance relative to majors, etc.). There is a need for a common platform that allows HEIs to *dialogue and interact* in a straightforward and frank manner based on agreed understanding of what is being done.

2. The call for an agreed framework to boost accountability and facilitate mechanisms for quality assurance among HEIs, programmes and courses; and related to this improving quality in the interpretation of qualifications as well as teaching/learning processes and standards both in home and host institutions; which in turn links to the need to promote mutual trust at the country and HEIs levels.

3. The desire to promote acceptance of grades coming from different HEIs. In the context of credit transfer, grades are typically valued based on norm references that help “translate” those grades. There seems to be a generalized need to equate referenced grades, however the ways in which HEIs handle the issue and their will to accept them and set hindrances for the wider use of credit transfer schemes at the regional level. To increase consistency and reliability there is a need to further analyze on common criteria referenced grade schemes that are more reliable, consistent and systematic, however they coincide in that this will remain a right of the HEIs accepting the credits and issuing the degrees.

4. The reports agree in that there is preoccupation towards achieving quality in the delivery of instruction (seen from both sides of teaching and learning). Pedagogic methods are constantly evolving and some common didactical practices need to give base for more harmonized learning experiences. Living in an era where technology and communication tools are of such a level of development offers opportunities of magnitudes human kind has never seen before. And this is an opportunity that should not be disregarded.

5. Likewise country reports suggest common concern among governments and HEIs on the need to seriously consider a common trend in HE towards “*tailor made*” or “*a la cart*” kinds of HE programmes, as even if this seeks to be a student-centred approach, it also means more complexity in terms of ensuring quality in education.

Both governments and HEIs seek to achieve balance between what students wish to learn and what they believe programmes should provide as a core. In general this trend is perceived as a positive change seeking to democratize contents of education, all of which however brings in important challenges in terms of consistency and quality.

6. All reports coincide in showing goodwill among stakeholders towards internationalization of HE, the setting of more bilateral and multilateral systems for credit transfer confirms this trend. Although there are still important challenges ahead it is worth noting that new and creative strategies are being designed and put into practice through the region.

A number of examples demonstrate this, as most countries accept schemes for temporary mobility of students at the bilateral and multilateral levels as it happens among countries participating in the programmes set in the contexts of AIMS, AUN or Campus Asia. Or in the establishment of double degree or twinning and joint degree programmes established under modalities like “2+2” or “3+1” where students spend different periods of time and obtain credits in the partner HEIs.

Information gathered through the reports demonstrate that these agreements usually work at the bilateral level with the mutual acceptance of recognition of participating HEIs; while there is in parallel a growing trend toward multilateralism.

Credit transfer systems -in whatever their form- provide rich experiences and lessons to be learnt in the search for harmonization of HE. These systems contribute in this through their direct outcomes (internationalization of education and degrees and enhanced exposure of students) and they help producing changes in the attitudes of academics, executives and international relations officers in different HEIs.

Programmes based on multilateral credit transfer systems promote mutual trust as they create scenarios for practice and learning on exchange procedures and the valuation and recognition of credits, as well as other forms of accreditation and information share.

Although the region shows gaps in the way to further integrate education systems, there is a generalized change of attitude towards openness observed in the new goals and allocation of resources governments and HEIs are doing. Examples of this are the efforts done in the implementation of multilateral credit exchange programmes like AIMS and Campus Asia.

Among the challenges that emerge from contrasting country situations it should be noted that at the regional level some important gaps remain for example in that while some countries still need to improve and guaranty the provision of elementary education others have already achieved high levels of quality in that area and are able to allocate more resources and efforts to improve their HE systems instead.

Specifically in the area of HE another obstacle to integration observed from the reports is that while some countries are focusing more on hard sciences and development of new technologies, others attach more importance to social sciences and humanities instead in the future this may imply more complementation but also more fragmentation.

Gaps of this sort affect the level of readiness countries account with to face regional schemes for integration at all levels; which in turn may also explain the fact that some countries are more active in the search for internationalization than others.

Lastly and specifically in regards to setting and using multilateral credit schemes, data gathered through the country reports for the *Explore* phase of the project points at a number of challenges ahead that call for consideration and action. These are:

- The need to boost Institutional capacity in the development and management of skills related to understanding and implementing credit systems among international relations officers, academicians, students and parents.
- The need to create flexible strategies that allow stakeholders to function in a world of increasing fragmentation of systems and modularization of programmes. As explained this brings about a number of potentials specially in terms of creating more flexible pathways to HE and more democratic decisions, while it also poses challenges especially in terms of quality of education.
- The need to facilitate and improve bureaucratic procedures and formalities such as visas and permission to work for foreign students, to facilitate access to financial support for mobile students and to improve skills of students, instructors and HEIs personnel in the use of international languages, particularly of English.

The next chapter presents a final conclusion on the situation of the credit transfer systems in the region and then a set of recommendations aiming to create a more harmonized credit transfer scheme for the for the region.

6. Integration of findings toward a common regional CTS

Chapters 4 and 5 provided a general overview of how credit transfer systems work globally and how countries in the region deal with the accreditation and recognition of students' workloads and achievements in different HEIs in a context of increasing regionalization.

This chapter integrates those findings to serve as the foundation from where to propose and develop a credit transfer scheme that is valid for HEIs in the region based on lessons learnt, previous experiences and HEIs' own expectations and practices.

As explained, most of the student mobility taking place in the region happens on bilateral agreements among HEIs directly dealing with the transfer and recognition of students' workloads and achievements; however there is a growing tendency in the interests of governments and HEIs toward setting more multilateral schemes. This chapter presents the common ground among existing mechanisms to serve as the base for further harmonization and toward practical ways to facilitate international mobility of students in the region.

6.1. Basic thinking and what to expect from a CTS

The analysis of the multilateral credit systems and the rules set by countries and HEIs in the region demonstrate that in spite of evident differences they all function on a number of common features that are set to achieve, at least, the following goals:

General goals

- Promote flexible and democratic rules in the pathways of HE
- Use rational and practical means for progression (and transfer) in HE
- Be applicable to:
 - o all cycles of HE (bachelor, master and doctorate)
 - o temporary & permanent mobility programmes
 - o horizontal and vertical mobility
- Work hand-in-hand with QA systems (at the national and HEI levels) to promote transparency, allow for more informed decisions and promote cooperation among QA agencies at the regional level
- Promote more student-centred approaches to learning
- Serve as catalyst for curricular development and updating toward acquisition of competences by students
- Boost academic supplementation of programmes and HEIs
- Promote development of human resources as internationally sensitive graduates
- Develop a common language to facilitate communication
- Better colligate qualifications with cycles, E.g. from diploma to bachelor to master, etc.
- Promote the understanding of workload as the sum of efforts by students including: lectures; practicum; tutorials; self-study time; group study; field trips; assessment, etc.

For students

- Boost student mobility as they reduce uncertainty on recognition
- Help students develop international careers and access to broader labour markets
- Develop students social, professional and language skills
- Reduce barriers to progression toward graduation and further learning
- Promote ownership and responsibility about their careers

For HEIs

- Promote voluntary association and acceptance of the rules by HEIs (autonomy)
- Set systemic and agreed rules for interaction in terms of exchange of students
- Help promoting QA and institutional trust building
- Allow flexible adjustment over time in the ways HEIs interact
- Boost dialogue and networking
- Promote harmony in education programmes and systems with respect for variety
- Develop and update curricula and programmes
- Boost employability of HEIs' graduates and their visibility
- Help HEIs be better positioned in HEIs rankings
- Promote attractiveness and visibility
- Promote innovation and research

For Countries

- Create more inclusive and tolerant societies
- Contribute to the development and diversification of economic systems
- Promote more open attitudes among students and teachers in HE communities
- Contribute toward more motivated populations and internationally sensitive
- Create a pool of more international human resources and boost innovation
- Develop more internationalized know-how based on glocal needs and potentials
- Redirect flows of student mobility (double effect: mobility of resources within the region and brain train with innovation)

For the region and the world

- Promote peace and development
- Support the regionalization of HE toward new regional identities
- Encourage cultural understanding to bridge economic, social and political cooperation
- Develop friendship among nations
- Contribute toward the harmonization and cooperation in HE and beyond

6.2. Context

Although with different levels, all countries analyzed in the region show interest in the need to have their HE systems more internationally integrated. Findings from *Explore* put forward a generalized will to continue to deepen the process of regionalization of HE.

In supporting this process, all country reports agree in that there have been deep changes in the social and economic role of HE as it has increasingly become a central partner in the strategic development of the countries and economic systems.

While phenomena like *massification* and *privatization* of HE are creating a more complex and fluid landscape that, however requires of means that integrate education systems in a consistent and coherent fashion and with more transparent ways to ensure the quality of the programmes and courses.

Findings from research at the national level in this study put forward two common features that call for attention and the need for a common framework for credit transfer:

1. The increasing interest in intraregional mobility of students (*Assianization* of HE)
2. A growing trend in the region to challenge traditional methods of teaching toward more student-centred learning approaches.

Important challenges to a freer student mobility for the region remain in terms of improving mechanisms to ensure quality of education (internal and externally) and to find new and creative ways to financially support that mobility.

Other major challenges remain in terms of creating better conditions and more compatible academic programmes (in terms of goals, contents and academic periods). While there is also a need to further develop a common academic language and agreed communicational channels that are democratic, transparent and open to all major stakeholders.

In technical terms, the main challenges relate to:

1. Structural technical differences among the credit systems utilized in the countries and by the different HEIs, and how to make them compatible to allow for mutual trust.
2. An agreed approach toward the acceptance of grades granted by different HEIs in a way that is fair to the students' efforts and performances yet respectful of the needs of the HEIs and their internal systems.
3. A shared ground to consider accreditation of prior learning, formal and informal learning and work experience as academically creditable.

All country reports coincide in showing growing agreement among stakeholders over the need to progressively open channels for more international cooperation among HEIs and governments; which is evident in the growing number of multilateral student mobility programmes being set in the region and the growing number of students being mobilized by already existing multilateral schemes.

6.2.1. Student mobility and credit transfer

The increasing interest in internationalization of HE closely connects to the need to develop ways to systematically make those moves possible. The following table demonstrates this growing interest of governments and HEIs in promoting internationalization as it shows participation of countries and HEIs in regional mobility programmes that directly relate to the need of accounting with agreed ground for credit transfer and recognition.

Table 14: list of countries participating in multilateral mobility programmes

O: participating X: not participating

Country / mobility programme	AUN	UMAP	AIMS	Campus Asia
Cambodia	O	O	X	X
China	X	X	X	O
Indonesia	O	O	O	X
Japan	X	O	O* ¹	O
Lao PDR	O	O	X	X
Malaysia	O	O	O	X
Myanmar	O	X	X	X
Thailand	O	O	O	X
Vietnam	O	O	O* ²	X
The Republic of Korea	X	X	X	O
Credit arrangements according to grouping				
	Nominal transfer of credits 1-to-1	UCTS reference conversion	UCTS reference conversion	At discretion of the Home HEIs
* ¹ At the time of writing (May 2013) Japan is carrying out dialogues with the grouping to become a member				
* ² Vietnam joined the grouping in April 2013 and is expected to start exchanging students shortly				

The chart above shows not only which countries are participating in each mobility scheme but it also shows that different countries and HEIs are simultaneously using different credit transfer mechanisms. This piece of information is important for it shows that different credit transfer systems respond to different needs yet similar goals.

It also demonstrates common principles upon which credit transfers function:

- Exchange is done on previous agreement and mutual recognition of the HEIs
- Home HEIs have the final say to accept or not credits from host HEIs toward graduation
- All HEIs participating in mobility programmes are officially accredited before the respective national agency and offer quality assured programmes and courses.

However the table also evidences a key difference in terms of how credits are transferred:

- AUN's ACTS: 1-to-1
- UMAP's UCTS: conversion rate or reference range
- Campus Asia: free conversion at discretion of HEIs

Yet, it should remain clear that most HEIs in the region are exchanging students on bilateral agreements, many of which do it with HEIs in Europe. In these cases local HEIs may be applying ECTS as a reference when transferring credits; however in order to accept credits coming from European partners, they need to adjust those credits and convert them into their own systems. Country reports show that because this kind of exchange is done at the bilateral level (HEI-to-HEI) practice is particularly disperse and there is not a generalized approach that may help systematize interaction at the inter-regional level.

6.2.2. HEIs autonomy and credit recognition

In parallel with the interest from governments and HEIs in participating in multilateral student mobility programmes, the comparative analysis of the credit situation in the countries and HEIs of the region demonstrates a positive attitude toward providing more space for academic decisions and autonomy to the HEIs in their respective territories.

Although governments are the last authority in regards to the quality of education provided in each country, through progressive reforms they are all (even if with different depths and speeds) carrying out reforms to allow more authority to HEIs about what they consider proper quality and what they can or cannot accept as *transferable* workloads and achievements toward the degrees they eventually grant.

The position of the governments regarding autonomy they allow to HEIs on decisions about recognition of credits from other HEIs can be classified as centralized, moderated and decentralized. This has important implications over the applicability of whichever multilateral credit transfer system HEIs may use.

According the rules set in each country HE systems may be:

- **Centralized.** Governments set strict norms regarding HEIs accreditation system to the students' workloads and achievements. They may also set a national grading system that is compulsory for all HEIs and specific rules for the transfer of credits coming from both other HEIs within the country or overseas.
- **Moderated.** Similar to the systems above, here governments too set rules that are compulsory for HEIs, however rules and applicability allow for more autonomy in terms of what HEIs consider acceptable to transfer and recognize as students' workloads or achievements coming from other HEIs. Rules set by the governments generally represent

guidelines that give a direction to the activities of the HEIs but allowing them a more freedom in their decisions.

- **Decentralized.** Here governments set basic and general guidelines of accreditation for the HEIs, hence HEIs account with broad autonomy to decide on accepting or not students' workloads and achievements coming from other HEIs.

The following table summarizes the distribution of systems according to this classification.

Table 15: Centralized, moderated and decentralized HE systems per country

Country	Specific features
Centralized	
Laos PDR	Credit system, grading system and rules for transfer of credits are set centrally by the government and uniformly applied by all HEIs. International transfer of credits may happen based on bilateral agreement by the HEIs.
Myanmar	Uniform credit and grading system for all HEIs in the country. Rules for transfer of credits set centrally by the government and uniformly applied by all HEIs. Inward transfer of credits from foreign HEIs is not yet permitted.
Vietnam	The government promotes the use of credit systems among HEIs but implementation is disperse. Rules for transfer of credits are set centrally by the government and uniformly applied by HEIs <i>in</i> the country, except a few national universities that account with more autonomy. Inward transfer of credits from foreign HEIs is not yet permitted but this is expected to change with Vietnam's entry to the AIMS programme.
Moderate	
Cambodia	Governments have set national rules for accreditation that serves as guideline for HEIs. HEIs account with autonomy to decide on what they accept and recognize from other HEIs. Transfer of credits from foreign HEIs is permitted and promoted.
Japan	
Malaysia	
Thailand	
S. Korea	
Decentralized	
China	Governments give full autonomy to HEIs on decisions of accreditation of students' workload and recognition of foreign credits.
Indonesia	

Observation from the situation of credit systems in the countries:

1. More centralized countries participate less in student mobility programmes; a situation that is likely to happen due to:

a. Rules set by systems: like in the cases of Myanmar or Vietnam, where HEIs do not (yet) have the right to decide on recognition of credits granted to students by HEIs overseas.

In Vietnam (for the time being, May 2013) the National Universities of Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh account with autonomy to recognize credits from foreign HEIs as they participate in AUN network; the same can be expected for HEIs that will participate the AIMS programme.

b. QA appears among the major obstacles for inward mobility of international students.

- c. Limited financial resources hinder participation in mobility programmes of the HEIs.
2. Moderate and decentralized countries tend to participate more in student mobility programmes both at the bilateral and multilateral level.
- a. Students (may) show more interest in participating of these programmes when they perceive that there are more guaranties of recognition of their workload and achievements as countries and HEIs commit through formal mobility schemes.
 - b. QA issues (internal and external) among countries and HEIs appear as important factors hindering more mobility.
 - c. International mobility of students presents unbalances in the direction of flows; for example as Japan and Malaysia account with larger number of inward mobility, while Cambodia and Indonesia have more outgoing students than incoming ones.

6.3. Common grounds for accreditation and recognition

As shown in chapters 4 and 5, different credit systems deal differently with how they measure and value students' workloads and achievements. They however share common elements and requirements that serve as a base upon which to compare number of credits normally assigned to courses and granted to students upon successful completion. These common elements are:

1. Credits units are attached to courses to quantitatively describe workloads
2. Wide use of time to measure students' workloads
3. Modular structure of study programmes
4. Mechanisms to promote curricular transparency and assured quality
5. Tendency to move from bilateral to multilateral arrangements
6. Accreditation of alternative forms of learning

1. Credits units are attached to courses to quantitatively describe workloads

All credit systems frame the accreditation of courses as a rational strategy to measure and compare courses. Academic credit units are assigned depending on nature, length and level of effort expected from the student and the level of complexity and difficulty of the course.

For further harmonization to happen there is a need make definitions of academic terms and study periods come closer and in this regard the use of *ranges of time* has brought an alternative solution, for example by applying similar ranges of credits to similar amounts of study hours required per courses.

2. Wide use of *time* to measure students' workloads

All systems analyzed in this study make extensive use of time to determine students' workloads. Time is understood in two ways: 1) the number of academic hours needed for a student to successfully accomplish the learning goals of a course; and 2) the distribution of those hours in academic periods –years, semesters, trimesters, etc- leading to the accumulation of total hours needed per course in relation to the total needed for a programme.

Country reports reveal a growing level of awareness among HEIs in the region in regards to the benefits of using credit systems to rationalize the distribution of workload and time necessary for the students to successfully complete a study programme toward a degree. Although both countries and HEIs account with different methods of measuring workload and

their value in terms of number of credits, they are all based on the same logic of accumulation of knowledge and skills as interrelated blocks.

Although time to describe workload is the most wide spread form of measurement, country reports denote growing interest and awareness among HEIs on the need to consider learning outcomes and competences obtained through the learning process as one more variable in the assignation of credits to courses.

Although bringing study periods into closer definitions in a region with such a diversity of education systems may require institutional reforms, the use of *ranges of time* has already proven to bring flexibility and to bridge differences among systems.

The same applies for desirable changes toward making both national and HEIs academic periods come to closer terms in their lengths and starting and finishing periods.

An interesting observation from the data gathered for the research was the fact HE systems with more decentralized credit systems tend to give more attention to learning outcomes as relative to time; while countries with more centralized systems tend to attach more value to time as the determining factor in the number of credits attached to a course.

3. Modular structure of study programmes

As a consequence of the increase in the use of credit systems there is a growing number of HEIs that structure the curricula of their programmes through a modular design, where each course is organized as a complete unit in itself, typically independent from the rest of the courses, however interconnected in terms of relevance and coherence toward the degree expected from a programme.

Modularization of study programmes has proven to bring a rational distribution of required learning that adds up as *blocks of learning* (courses) towards and integrated and coherent whole resulting in a degree or qualification; where successfully passed modules accumulate knowledge and skills as blocks and allow articulation of different learning experiences.

In modular systems courses are described based on: 1. goals of the course; 2. methods of instruction and evaluation; 3. workload; 4. expected learning outcomes; 5. material used; 6. outcomes from assessment; 7. Etc.

4. Mechanisms to promote curricular transparency and assured quality

Harmonization efforts and mobility programmes require that study programmes are constructed upon standard descriptors and indicators, for example, goals and expected outcomes from courses, teaching methods, materials, etc.

For HEIs to be able to share information and build networks that allow for the mobility of students among them, they require quality assurance mechanisms (both internal and external). In all cases analyzed, accounting with at least some minimum standards in the provision of the courses appears as a non negotiable pre-requisite for HEIs to recognize each other institutionally and to acknowledge the work and achievements students have obtained from courses taken elsewhere.

5. Tendency to move from bilateral to multilateral arrangements

An important overlapping area that was observed from the comparisons carried out in chapters 4 and 5 is the increasing interest in *multilateralizacion* (as opposed to traditional bilateralism) of the interactions among HEIs.

Findings from *Explore* demonstrate an increasing number of HEIs are utilizing multilateral credit transfer systems, while at the same time there is a growing appreciation given by governments to international mobility as an added value of HE.

6. Accreditation of alternative forms of learning

Lastly, findings from *Explore* show growing agreement among stakeholders in HE about the need to consider academic accreditation of non formal and informal learning as well as working experience that can be described in terms of learning outcomes.

The region shows a fertile predisposition towards accreditation of alternative forms of learning in the fact that some multilateral credit transfer systems already include the issue among their procedures as it happens in the cases of UMAP's UCTS and AeU's ACTS; while at the national level some countries and HEIs are promoting reforms in this regard as it could be observed among HEIs in Cambodia, China, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand and the Republic of Korea.

6.4. Credit transfer systems at the core

The comparative analysis of multilateral credit transfer systems and the situation of national credit systems reveal important areas of coincidence that greatly support the significance of this project as a whole.

These refer to the principles that typically apply to the credit systems, for example these mechanisms allow students to get extra amounts of credits for extra amounts of workload, hence making the passage of the students through formal learning a more rational and better planned process; while at the same time giving HEIs an important say in what they believe should be accredited from the students work and outcomes.

A core question for all credit transfer systems is how can workloads required by different courses that take place in different HEIs be contrasted and recognized. Findings from this study show that there are at least four common practices:

- The use of time as a parameter to measure workload distributed into credits
- The recognition of courses to be transferred as course-by-course or as equivalences of similar subjects
- The use of quotas as maximum and minimum transferrable credits and contents
- The use of mechanisms to share information among HEIs (E.g. exchange of information packages and transcripts, and when available centralized websites that permit access to all courses available as in UMAP's *Student Connection* or AUN's *Courses and Programmes website*).

At the same time important differences were also spotted out in terms of how credits are measured and transferred from a HEI to another. For instance:

- In all cases analyzed credits are transferred based on either *conventions* or *conversions*. Among systems in the sample in chapter 4 and national systems in chapter 5; ECTS and AUN's ACTS, and the national credit systems in Myanmar and Lao PDR are systems that use a conventionally agreed value to all credits granted by HEIs in the network. While systems proposed by UMAP's UCTS, ASEM Asia and Campus Asia with all the rest of the national credit systems propose the use of a mechanism to convert the credits obtained in a HEI toward the acceptance in another by adapting the value given by the HEI granting the credit to the value used at the HEI that will grant the degree.

- A different way in which HEIs interactions can be portrayed is as in the currency exchange markets. Where some systems behave as if interacting in a floating exchange market, for example as in Campus Asia at the multilateral level, and at the national level in the credit systems in use in China, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Korea, Thailand and Vietnam; where negotiation of the value of the credit is direct and bilateral.

There are systems that function as a pure currency union, where credits are transferred and accepted by the HEIs “as they are”, as it happens in the cases of AUN’s ACTS and in the national systems of Cambodia, Lao PDR and Myanmar.

Lastly other systems like UMAP’s UCTS work based on the use of an agreed rate that facilitates the comparison of attained credits by using a reference point for conversion of foreign/host credits into the home HEIs.

As explained the great majority of exchanges happening among HEIs happens at the bilateral level and are framed free floating interactions as HEIs directly negotiate the terms and conditions and are free to decide what better suits their needs; the second mechanism (a credit union) requires a high level of mutual trust among HEIs and highly developed QA mechanisms in place for HEIs to exchange students and accept credits without questioning their content and the quality of the knowledge acquired by the student.

The third mechanism (use of an agreed rate) instead offers a solid ground for the region as a whole to interact more systematically; this kind of scheme allows freedom to HEIs to decide how much of the credits incoming students bring can be recognized.

An important difference noted from the comparison of multilateral credit systems as opposed to systems set nationally or at the HEI level is that the first ones are typically designed toward temporary mobility programmes (exchange programmes); as it happens with the cases of UMAP, AUN, AIMS and Campus Asia programmes. It is in this point where credit transfer systems show their biggest potentials; however it should also remain clear that multilateral credit transfer systems are compatible with permanent moves within the same HEIs or among HEIs in the same country, as it can be observed in ECTS, which although was born as a strategy to boost international mobility in the Socrates and then Erasmus programmes, yet it is widely used among HEIs for internal mobility and progression due to its practicality.

The same logic is considered here for the model proposed by SEAMEO RIHED as there is no reason to exclude the applicability of a common framework for transfer of credits among HEIs within a country or among different programmes within the same HEI.

This is particularly the case of mobility of students happening in countries with a variety of credit systems being used among HEIs as it happens in China, Japan, Malaysia or Thailand.

6.4.1. Common regional ground for a future agreement

1. Lengths and number of courses to graduation

The amount and kind of courses required per study programme varies as this is determined by either the HEIs themselves or by the governments in some cases; yet and interestingly, country reports show that the region is gradually becoming more harmonic in the kinds and lengths of programmes offered by the different HEIs.

Although amount of credits allocated per course and the number of credits required for graduation greatly varies the region shows important coincidences in the fact that most bachelor degrees in all countries typically last 4 years, with some exceptions depending on

the careers that may last five or six years for example in medicine, pharmacy, veterinarian sciences and some engineering fields.

In the case of masters degrees they tend to last one or two years, while PhD programmes typically last between three and five years in all countries analyzed.

The above provides an important common ground toward the setting of a regional credit system as there is already agreement in terms of what students' workloads should (to some extent) contain in terms of length of programmes required to obtain and consolidate the necessary skills before graduation.

2. Relative and absolute value of academic credits

In all cases analyzed credits must cover the entire qualification and workload required; while credits are only awarded to students that successfully complete requirements of the course upon evaluation from the instructor.

Because credit systems are built upon the logic of modularization, it is clear that the underlying logic is that each individual course contributes toward the total amount of credits required for graduation. As such credits any course yields can be interpreted both in absolute and relative terms.

In the first case considering a course as a complete unit that produces a given number of credits, while in relative terms it means that each course contributes as a percentage of the total amount of credits needed for graduation.

Although the relative value of credits per course to the total of a programme appears as a practical solution to compare the value of a course when being transferred to another programme, in reality no system (multilateral, national or HEI) seems to use this criterion to transfer and recognize credits. Instead, the use of absolute value of the credits that are then converted through a scale appears as the rule for most transfers where systems do not work as a currency union where, as seen, credits are taken "as they are"; e.g. ECTS or AUN's ACTS. Credit systems that allow transfer of credits work more effectively when based on the notion that credits earned by a student should be taken as absolute figures (regardless of the total number of credits required by a programme) because this enables the transfer of credits from *any* course (within the modular structure of a programme).

This also has the advantage that it frees the student from traditional academic years or semesters based systems, where the students move together as groups.

If due to any reason a student cannot take a given course in a given moment of time dealing with the credits in absolute terms allows him/her to *catch up* either by taking a different course or by taking the same course in a different academic term.

3. Accumulation of courses towards vertical progression

An important point of intersection that deserves consideration among the credit systems analyzed is that there are some cases that promote vertical mobility to higher levels of education based on the accumulation of credits rather than on entrance exams. As it was observed in the cases of The Credit and Qualifications Framework of Wales and in the Quality Assurance Framework of Malaysia that actively promote the recognition of credits from lower levels of education as requisites for advance standing into higher levels.

Country reports show that practice in this regard is very disperse in the region, with countries like China and Vietnam firmly attached to the traditional concept of entrance exams that function as filters to limit the number of candidates. This gives stronger hold to the idea of a

credit transfer model that should at first promote horizontal mobility (within the same level) and progressively open the field for further interactions at the vertical level.

6.4.2. Credit transfer systems as a complex composite

The comparative analysis of multilateral transfer systems and the credit systems at the national level reveal that all systems share at least four basic elements, that even if distinct, they are interconnected and the way in which they function and interact is what makes each system *seem* different from the others. These four elements are:

1. Mutual recognition
2. Transferability of credits
3. Grade transfer and recognition
4. Support mechanisms and system context

1. Mutual recognition

The first crucial element is that HEIs utilizing a credit transfer system will normally recognize other HEIs as properly accredited (formally done according to public laws and regulations and functioning as a quality assured institution).

For HEIs to accept qualifications awarded by another HEI they must first “accept” the quality of the educational products the other HEIs offer. In this case, *recognition* is understood in the *institutional* sense of the term. Universities acknowledge the status of partner HEIs before they can accept credits those HEIs grant to students.

Recognition is considered at least in three levels: at the HEI level (institutional), at the programme and at the course levels, meaning that the programmes are properly accredited and that the courses therein are relevant and quality assured. Typically this means that the national agencies in charge of guarantying the quality of an accredited institution will also run quality evaluations at the programme and course levels.

2. Transferability of credits

For credits to be transferable general and specific competencies are weighed toward the profile sought by the programme. This criterion is considered at the time of attaching value to the courses in terms of credits to be transferred in relation to the number of credits required for that programme.

As a rule, credits are transferred horizontally among programmes of the same cycle under graduate to undergraduate and post graduate to post graduate, unless HEIs agree otherwise.

As mentioned, the analysis of the multilateral credit systems and the way credit systems work at the national levels suggest that HEIs interact in at least three possible ways in regards to the transfer of credits (as a free floating exchange; as a currency union or by using a common factor as convertor). The analysis carried out in chapters four and five of this study demonstrates that HEIs in the region are actually using all three transfer channels.

At the HEIs bilateral level and for those HEIs participating in Campus Asia the transfer of credits is done based on a direct transaction as in a **free floating market** where each HEI decides whether to accept or not credits from other HEIs (veto power). Although this strategy allows for a wide autonomy to HEIs, it also has the disadvantage that transfer practices are disperse; implying duplication of work at negotiating the terms and scattered procedures.

Students too tend to be confused with these arrangements as rules may be different depending on the HEIs participating in the transaction.

In the case where HEIs exchange students as in a **common union**, the only case found for the region at the multilateral level is AUN's ACTS and at the national level in Myanmar. This scheme offers the advantage of simplicity and practicality because credits earned as a consequence of participating in a mobility programme are transferred and accepted automatically and taken "as they are", no conversion is needed. However this kind of system presents important challenges as well:

1. The acceptance of the credits is done only among HEIs participating in AUN's network (leaving the vast majority of HEIs in the region and beyond without chances to participate) or in the case of Myanmar, the system is applicable only among universities in the country and universities of the same kind and for similar programmes. And
2. Given that the number of credits transferred from a HEI to another is done "as they are", this kind of transferability presents difficulties in ensuring fairness of those credits in relation to the workload required to obtain them, the effort done by the students and the quality of the courses.

Lastly, credit systems that work on an "**agreed rate**", and the use a "**parameter to convert credits when transferred**" as proposed in UMAP's UCTS and used by both UMAP's mobility programme and by the AIMS programme.

The comparison of credit transfer systems and of the student mobility programmes in the region strongly suggest this is the most sustainable mechanism to facilitate the transfer and recognition of credits among HEIs. This model offers important advantages that are worth considering, such as:

1. The system allows enough flexibility for HEIs to decide how much of the credits requested for recognition by the students are applicable and relevant to their own programmes.
2. As a transfer strategy, it ensures fairness in regards to the efforts made by the student in relation to the number of credits s/he will obtain from the course taken while on exchange toward graduation.
3. The use of standard procedures and conversion methods facilitates the understanding of the system as a whole, and it reduces disperse practice and duplication of work.

3. Grade transfer and recognition

The comparison of how different systems deal with the transfer and recognition of grades presents one of the thorniest elements of the interactions among HEIs in terms of mobility of students. Rules set in this regard by different systems are diffuse and work on different understandings of fairness toward students and HEIs.

Because of this, the most wide spread solution has been granting the HEIs that award the degrees the right to decide whether they will recognize the grades students wish to bring along, as well as the inclusion or not of those grades toward the final GPA of the students.

In many cases the use of reference tables for comparison and conversion of grades has been proposed, however the veto power of the HEIs remains the rule in this regard.

In some cases HEIs opt to use simpler rules accepting the grades granted to the student by other HEIs using indicators of performance that only refer to that performance as having achieved the minimum requirements or not, hence using descriptors such as "Pass or Fail", "Satisfactory or No-Satisfactory", Etc.

Although this mechanism of accepting grades from another HEI appears simple, it poses two important questions:

1. The fairness of the grades given that they only consider the performance of the student according to the base line upon which the passing mark is set. And

2. The fact that different HEIs and education systems may set different levels for that passing mark, for example in some HEIs the passing mark is set at 70% while in others it is set at 50%.

There is wide disagreement among stakeholders in regards to which system represents the most efficient way to deal with the transfer and recognition of students' performances.

4. Support mechanisms and system context

An important element that both multilateral credit systems and credit systems used at the national level share is how to provide guaranties for recognition of qualifications to students upon return to home HEIs after an exchange period, or when they wish to transfer permanently from a HEI to another.

A series of elements were found to facilitate the flow of information among HEIs when doing credit transfers and typically include:

1. The signing of **learning agreements** between HEIs and students to ensure consistency of the programmes when students go on exchange, while giving more guaranties to the students about the recognition of their attainments. These agreements help both HEIs and students agree, at least, on the terms and conditions upon which the exchange will take place and how the transfer of credits will be done. Typically this includes the subjects the students are expected to take while in the host HEI and the agreement of how credits and grades will be treated by the home HEI upon return.

Some innovative cases propose that agreements are signed by the three parties (home and host HEIs and student) so as to provide more legitimacy to it.

Learning agreements are typically set before students' departure but can be amended upon consultation and approval of parties.

2. The **exchange of information packages** among HEIs to make their curricula more transparent; at the bilateral level HEIs are already exchanging information when they agree to allow bilateral exchanges of students and at the multilateral level two positive examples of information share have been found to bring centralized and systematic answers to this in the websites of UMAP's *Student Connection* and the section on *Courses and Programmes* at AUN's website. These two systems set the leading examples of what should be expected in terms of how HEIs share information on their syllabi and curricula as well as on accreditation of courses and transferability of credits.

As centralized information systems they allow for:

- dissemination of information
- direct communication between stakeholders
- HEIs can upload and update their own information, E.g. programmes and courses
- Students can access information provided by the HEIs to choose their pathways, and
- QA agencies can assist HEIs in the validation of the information available.

3. The use of **official transcripts** to exchange information on workloads and performances.

Academic transcripts are normally issued by HEIs yearly, upon completion of exchange programmes, and up on completion of study programmes to allow for use of credits earned

outside the programme where credits have been granted and to allow for temporary and permanent mobility.

An interesting finding from the research is the growing interest in the production of extended transcript of records containing more detailed information at least on:

- The student
- The qualification
- The level and function of the programme
- Contents and outcomes from courses
- Evaluation methods
- Validation of certifications
- Details on the HEIs
- Other relevant information

6.4.3. Rules governing the transfer of credits

The comparison of multilateral credit systems and the situation of credit systems at the national level show diverse practices in regards to the rules governing transfer and acceptance of credits coming from different HEIs, be them in the same country or from overseas; however a number of common points serve for the setting of a regional framework.

These points refer to:

1. The wide use of selective/optional courses and subjects
2. The recognition of courses based on comparison of content as course-by-course (for subjects with similar contents and workloads).
3. The agreement that for compulsory courses a minimum percentage of equivalence between courses should exist, for example at 60% of matching contents.
4. The *veto power of the HEI* receiving the credits when it will award the degree stands as a generalized rule. Although both multilateral credit systems and country reports suggest a tendency toward attenuating this principle by seeking to include both home and host HEIs in the learning agreements with the students.
5. Recognition of credits by the HEI accepting them can be done in full or partially. HEIs accepting credits coming from other HEIs normally keep the right to request the students to fulfil for gaps that may exist in terms of knowledge or skills students are expected to have upon completion of a course.
6. For credits from different courses to be recognized by the HEIs receiving them, courses need to be related to the overall goal of the programme. The HEIs accepting the credits normally determine the relevance and pertinence of the courses students may request for recognition.
7. Courses might be considered for accreditation by HEIs accepting them when those courses do not exist in their curricula, and will normally be understood as an opportunity for the student to broaden his/her learning experiences.

6.4.4. Principles guiding recognition of credits

Both multilateral credit systems and credit systems in use at the national level coincide in that recognition of credits happens upon the agreement that:

- Credits can be recognized as *1 to 1* when the courses that are being compared are similar or that serve a similar goal (which not necessarily relates to the content of the course but the academic formation it is meant to provide), here the primary focus is the contribution of the student's workload toward the final goal of the graduation. Or
- Credits can be recognized based on a *course-to-course* logic, when HEIs use very different systems to accredit courses. This means, for example, that when a course "A" is given 3 credits in "HEI 1", these credits will be transferred to "HEI 2" where the same (or similar) courses are worth 4 credits; the course will be registered at the HEI accepting the credits as 4 credits in the transcript of the student toward graduation. This is the model proposed by Campus Asia as it allows HEIs to "detach" themselves from the need to convert credits while recognizing courses and yet being able to give the credits students need for their graduation.

This kind of mechanism typically allows HEIs to request students for makeup activities if they deem that what the student has achieved in the other HEI does not suffice minimum requirements to grant the full amount of credits the course could normally yield in the home HEI.

6.4.5. Credits per course and ranges of comparison

Because measurement of workload is not a precise science, procedures in this regard need to be supported by information (quantitative and qualitative) and dialogue of the parties.

The overall situation of credit systems in the countries and HEIs shows that in spite of the great diversity there, there are common points.

One of the most interesting findings from the research was that when multilateral credit transfer systems deal with national and HEIs' credit systems that are too diverse, they typically set rules that allow HEIs to *accommodate* when they wish their students to participate in temporary mobility programmes.

All multilateral credit transfer systems dealing with diverse national systems propose the use of *ranges of agreements* rather than fix points. This means that they set rules that help compare workload to a common ruler, yet the common ruler does not mean a unique point but rather a series of points with relative similarities.

For instance, in the case of ECTS, HEIs applying this system agree to recognize that a fulltime student will normally obtain 60 credits from the courses s/he will take distributed in an academic year, whereby students are expected to have completed a total range of 1500 to 1800 notional hours in a year, which implies that 1 credit equals to 25 to 30 hours of work.

In the case of UMAP, its members are analysing the implementation of Dr. Hotta's proposal: the use of the Asian Common Credit or ACC, which outlines the plan of recognizing credits from HEIs in Asia granted for courses in a range of 1 credit for every 38 to 48 hours of workload that are normally distributed in 13 to 16 weeks of formal instruction, where one academic hour is normally considered in the range of 45 to 55 minutes.

Previous research carried out by Hotta (2010a) and confirmed by this study on the distribution of the number of credits per course in most of the HEIs in Southeast and East Asia in relation to hours of workload found that credits are typically allocated in a rate of 1 credit as equivalent to 40 to 50 hours of student academic work including lectures and other formal activities as well as self-study, which in general are based on a range of 13 to 17 contact hours.

According to the system proposed here most HEIs in the region would be able to convert their own credits to the Asian Common Credit and vice versa allowing for transfers to happen basically on a one-to-one rate.

6.4.6. Maximum allowable transfer credits

Both multilateral credit transfer systems and systems set at the national or HEI levels typically set maximum amounts of transferrable credits. This is particularly clear in the case of temporary mobility programmes, where students spend a given period of time in a host HEI to then return to their home HEI, where they are expected to obtain their final degrees.

Findings from this research suggest that although the home HEI has the final say in what it will accept and recognize from the credits awarded to the students by other HEIs there are some general (not necessarily written) rules that tend to limit the total number of transferrable credits. This can happen in two ways:

1) by setting absolute limits to the number of credits it may accept, for example in saying *“the maximum transferrable credits is 12 credits per courses taken in a semester”* (typically based on the total amount of credits required for graduation); or

2) they can also do it using relative limitations by setting percentages of transferable credits, for example by saying *“under graduate courses can be transferred at a maximum of 30% of the total amount of credits needed for graduation, while for the case of post-graduate programmes, transferrable credits can reach up to 50% of the total required for graduation”*.

In the cases where research has a larger share of the workload other principles may apply in order to offer more flexibility to the research process.

Limitations of this sort are typically based on:

- The need to ensure coherence to study programmes regarding the content students take in the courses toward a given qualification or degree.
- Relevance of the courses toward the skills, knowledge and competences expected by the graduates.
- The need to ensure financial sustainability of the HEIs awarding the degrees (this is particularly clear in the case where HEIs are privately financed)

6.5. Issues to consider in the near future

Findings from the Explore phase of the project suggest a good will and shared interest among main stakeholders on the importance of promoting international student mobility and the need to account with a common framework to facilitate the transfer and recognition of students' workloads and achievements. Although the general landscape appears fertile and promising there remain a number of issues and challenges that require attention and action in the near future, such as:

1. The need to improve communication channels and methods
2. Credit transfer and financial sustainability
3. Modularization, credit transfer and “a la carte education”
4. Challenging traditionally western-centric views of education.
5. Need for systematic records on student mobility and credit systems.

1. The need to improve communication channels and methods. Although HEIs are increasingly providing more detailed information on curricula, syllabi, grading systems and other relevant information the region still shows gaps on academic transparency, which continues to hinder cooperation among HEIs and governments.

More generalized access to academic information is widely desired among stakeholders, for example wishing for more up-to-date information, better structured, more understandable, in more foreign languages and, more recently, accessible via online mechanisms appears as a crucial factor. However not all HEIs or governments keep themselves updated or provide transparent data or even information in languages that are widely understandable out of their own countries.

2. Credit transfer and financial sustainability. Concerns arise in relation to transfer of credits and financial sustainability of HEIs; especially for those private and for profit institutions that see credit transfer as a threat to losing their students to the increasing competitiveness of the sector. However and interestingly this should instead be promoted as a ruler for comparison and improvement.

HEIs have important things to learn from this, if they are unable to retain students they need to revise their management, curricula and teaching methods. This relates to the traditional public connection between provision of HE and access to public positions; a tradition that as explained is challenged now with the growing relevance that the market and the private sector have achieved in the last few decades. Today learners face a landscape of more educational options, and similar to what happens in free market places, there is a tendency to push out those who do not have a proper product to offer or that fail to adapt rapidly enough so as to stay in the market.

3. Modularization, credit transfer and “a la carte education”. Findings from *Explore* suggest a widening gap between educational providers and other decision makers about the setting of programmes that work as “accumulation *a la carte*”; where students are faced with the dilemma of building their careers and choosing their pathways that while facing the risk of creating inconsistent careers, without enough structure or that are incomplete.

4. Challenging traditionally western-centric views of education. Most stakeholders in the region seem to agree on the need to change traditional perceptions of HE related to Eurocentric or western-centric perceptions of education that assume that more developed countries have more to offer in educational terms. Although there is growing awareness among governments and HEIs in the region towards the need to become more attractive, there is still the view from parents and students that continue to look at the education in richer countries as the most desirable destinations; regardless of how accurate or applicable those studies may actually be for the future of students upon return to their home countries. The question here arises in terms of how to change those views, how to better brand HE in Asia, how to further develop comparative advantages in the HEIs in the region to attract and retain more students.

5. Need for systematic records on student mobility and credit systems. An important concern spotted through this study is the need to develop more systematic records and statistical data and on the effectiveness of the credit transfer systems in use in the region. Although slowly changing, there is still a critical lack of empirical figures on mobility and on best practices for mobility and transfer of credits; because of this both more quantitative and

qualitative research in the issue appears urgent for the setting of the region's common educational space for the near future.

This issue closely links to the role governments assign to quality assurance agencies for their countries and HEIs. As previously explained, the initial stage for assuring quality of education is in the hands of HEIs themselves, therefore, keeping records and making them available greatly coincides with the roles they are assigned.

This concludes the final observations that resulted from the overall view of the situation of credit transfer in the region considered for this research.

The next chapter presents a the model for credit transfer that is considered most suitable for the region; Chapter 8 presents a number of recommendations and areas of action that were collected through the research process; lastly a schematic plan of action on how the next phases of the project should be put to work is presented in chapter 9.

Chapter 7

Preliminary Draft

CCCT—TRIPLE CT (tentative title)

Convention on Common Credit Transfer

Proposed Credit Transfer System for Pilot Phase of SEAMEO RIHED-ADB Action Research

This paper is a preliminary draft of concepts and principles to be proposed for consultation with potential participants of the pilot at the 3rd workshop of the SEAMEO RIHED-ADB action research project on development of common credit transfer system in Siem Reap, April 2013.

1. Basic Thinking

1.1. Why transfer credits?

1.1.1. Student mobility benefits

- student
- HEI
- country
- region
- the world

1.1.2. Credit transfer is a system mechanism to promote student mobility.

1.2. Existing Methods

1.2.1. The predominant method used today to assign academic credit is to account for student's inputs, as "workload", and to measure in time unit-- "hours."

1.2.2. Outputs are evaluated as grades, scores, or percentage, whose values vary greatly.

2. CCCT Scope of Application

2.1. Multilateral and bilateral credit transfer management

2.2. Student mobility in the forms of

2.2.1. Student exchange

2.2.2. Joint programmes

3. CCCT Framework

3.1. Focus on an academic programme's building blocks: courses

3.1.1. For the vast majority of higher education programmes, the knowledge and skills required for the degree programmes are delivered in courses, where formal teaching and learning take place.

3.1.2. The nature and the number of courses required depend on the defined knowledge and skills demanded for each degree programme. Hence, while most Bachelor degree programmes take 4 years, some professional programmes take more time. For example, at the undergraduate level: 4 years for most Bachelor degree programmes, 5 years for Pharmacy, and 6 years for Medicine. At the Masters level, there are 1-year and 2-year programmes.

- 3.1.3. The proposed credit transfer system addresses credits earned in a course, regardless of the total number of credits required by a programme.
 - 3.1.4. This focus enables transferability of credits between
 - courses that are offered in module, semester, and quarter;
 - programmes that differ in total number of credits required to complete/ take different number of years to complete;
 - programmes that allow credit accumulation, such as those for continuing education and life-long learning.
- 3.2. Manage a credit transfer system at the level of its system components.
- 3.2.1. CTS is a composite construct which comprises 4 distinct, yet interrelated, components, each of which
 - has a wide range of variations in practice,
 - can be addressed with varying degree of flexibility
 - 3.2.2. These 4 key components are
 - 3.2.2.1. Mutual recognition
 - 3.2.2.2. Credit Transfer
 - 3.2.2.3. Grade Transfer
 - 3.2.2.4. Supporting Mechanisms and System Context

4. CCCT Principles

These principles are proposed for the consideration of potential participants (higher education institutions, HEIs) in the pilot phase of the SEAMEO RIHED-ADB Action Research to develop a common credit transfer system for the region. The principles are grouped according to the 4 key CTS components.

4.1. Mutual recognition

Mutual recognition for the purpose of credit transfer is considered at 3 levels: institution, programme, and course. For HEI A to accept credits of its student's academic work completed at HEI B, HEI A has to recognize HEI B's programmes and courses.

- 4.1.1. Recognition is given to HEIs accredited by the appropriate national authorities—government and quality assurance authority.
- 4.1.2. Recognition is given to (selected) academic programmes approved by appropriate authority, within the HEIs in 4.1.1 above.
- 4.1.3. Courses whose credits can be transferred are those agreed by the home HEI (HEI A) either prior to the student enrolment in the said courses (as in student study plan) or endorsed by student's adviser/programme director after the student enrolment.

4.2. Credit Transfer

- 4.2.1. Course equivalency
 - 4.2.1.1. For a required course, credits can be transferred for a course with at least 60% match between the contents of the course in the home and host HEIs, unless agreed otherwise between the two HEIs.

How percentage of match is determined is entirely within the discretion of the HEI.

- 4.2.1.2. For an elective course, credits can be transferred for courses from 0% to 100% match between the contents of the courses in the home and host HEIs. When course equivalency does not exist, as for example, in courses not offered by the home HEI, considerations can be made for, but not limited to, the following conditions:
- Courses on a subject area relevant to the academic programme the student is undertaking,
 - Courses that broaden the student's experience,
 - Courses that enhance the student's development deemed beneficial to the student and the society.

4.2.2. Number of credits per course

As the number of credits given to the workload in a course vary from HEI to HEI, comparability for the purpose of transfer can be considered in range rather than point. Credits for course work can be considered comparable when the "workload" measurement in terms of hours falls within $X \pm 6$.

[According to Dr. Hotta, the majority of HEIs in Asia value 1 credit as equal to 40-50 hours of workload, 13-17 hours of teaching. He proposes that when 1 credit is inside of range 38-48 hours of student workload or 13-16 hours of teaching, the credits are to be transferred on a one to one basis.]

4.2.3. Transfer principles

Credits from a course are to be transferred by using one of the following options:

4.2.3.1. Option 1: 1 to 1

One credit granted by the host HEI is transferred to the home HEI as one credit.

4.2.3.2. Option 2: course to course

In case the number of credits per course differ between home and host HEIs, the home HEI accepts the transfer of the number of credits equal to an equivalent/similar course at the home HEI. For example, if a course at host HEI is given 4 credits while an equivalent/similar course at the home HEI is given 3 credits, the home HEI shall accept a transfer of 3 credits.

4.2.4. Maximum allowable credits to be transferred

Home HEI may set a limit to the number of credits allowed to be transferred within a programme.

4.3. Grade Transfer

There exist great variations among HEIs and programmes on how student's performance is evaluated. Although the majority employ a grade system, some continue to use scores/percentage. Among those using grades, methods differ in how many grade points are available and how grades are assigned. As a result, grade conversion with accuracy and consistency is hard to achieve.

The proposed system, therefore, allows the home university to determine how grades are to be taken, and whether they are included in the GPA calculation.

Two options are proposed for the purpose of future standardization:

- 4.3.1. Assign a grade given by the host HEI to the closest grade used in the home HEI.
- 4.3.2. Assign 'S' (satisfactory) or 'P' (pass) for any grade equal and above the acceptable level.

For either case, clear rules for the transfer should be set and made public, and there should be no case-by-case deliberation.

4.4. Supporting Mechanisms and System Context

- 4.4.1. Information support system / documentation e.g. Student's study plan, syllabus, diploma supplement
- 4.4.2. Procedures-- major steps, decisions, processing time
- 4.4.3. Roles of government/ministry – HEIs
[To be added later.]

8. Recommendations

The previous chapters have analyzed two main areas of concern, the first one related to multilateral credit transfer systems where the goal of the research basically was to understand how different systems work in order to facilitate the mobility of students through standardized procedures that are agreed and put into practice by different stakeholders, namely governments of HEIs. And in the second part this report examined the current situation of ten countries in the Great Mekong Subregion and beyond in regards to their credit systems and the opportunities they offer for student mobility and for more areas of cooperation at the regional level.

In the upcoming pages the report puts forward a number of recommendations that aim to help guiding the actions of those in charge of making decisions regarding transferability of credits. These recommendations also include and synthesize the views of resource persons as well as the broad and active contribution from participants to the two international workshops organized by SEAMEO RIHED in Bangkok; the first one on 28 September 2012 under the title of *International Workshop on Academic Credit Transfer Systems, The experiences of Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, South Korea and Thailand*; and the second one on 5 and 6 November 2012 under the name of *International Workshop Harmonizing Academic Credit Transfer in the Great Mekong Subregion (GMS) and beyond*.

From the outcomes of the research carried out during the *Explore* phase of the project a number of issues have been put forward and that call for action for further harmonization of HE to happen in the region by means of academic credit transfer.

One of the most outstanding findings from the research carried out by SEAMEO RIHED during the *Explore* phase was the fact that there are high expectations among all stakeholders regarding a credit transfer solution that is suitable for all countries and HEIs, that is inclusive and democratic, that is participatory and transparent.

It was widely agreed that all major stakeholders should be a part of the decision in the way forward. In broad lines this means: 1) the governments in providing the legal frameworks and guidelines that are necessary for reforms to happen and to take root; 2) The HEIs in making themselves more transparent and open, in becoming more global rather than inner looking; and 3) the students in becoming responsible owners of the decisions giving direction to their careers.

The great majority of cases analyzed speak of a growing believe in that study programmes that allow for academic credits to be transferred should be nurtured by the governments by paving the ways to internationalize HE as a whole, while HEIs are called to act by responding constructively to the demands from a rapidly changing socio-economic, technological and cultural environments in order to offer students the knowledge and skills that that make them productive and engaged members of their communities.

Globalized economies with their increasingly intertwined productive systems are calling for a new kind of human capital and neither HEIs nor governments can afford to miss this point.

8.1. Recommendations to all stakeholders

Increasing awareness and usage of credit systems and credit transfer systems require institutional HEIs to scenarios with various rules and procedures and to *critically think on how academic systems work and interact*, how they develop and deliver knowledge and provide

skills to students; therefore the need to develop clear strategic plans.

The same can be said for HEIs executives and academic administrators that need to keep an open mind in looking at the rest of the world as a complementary scenario rather than as a source of competence; hence the need to develop procedures that allow for more flexibility at the institutional level.

There should also be institutional efforts to promote curiosity and willingness among students to take part in credit transfer activities at the regional level; for instance through awareness campaigns and promotion of interest on these activities.

Although the development of a regional credit accumulation and transfer system compatible for the whole region is highly desirable, such an effort will need to include the involvement of all stakeholders to create a framework for credit academic recognition and transfer with the capacity to encompass the richness and diversity of education in Asia; thus high level of commitment and support by main stakeholders should be promoted.

Decision makers in the HE systems of Asian countries and HEIs should put into deep consideration the “Asian Common Credit” (ACC) concept, as proposed by Hotta. That is to say a system where one ACC equals to 38-48 hours of student workload; which would facilitate HEIs to transfer credits on a *one-to-one* base. And where the generalized acceptance of ACC could foster a common trend to transfer credits with European institutions at the rate of 1 ACC equal to 1.5 or 1.6 ECTS, paving the way for increasing transfers of credits at the interregional level.

The research carried out through *Explore* demonstrated a wide lack of awareness among stakeholders on the idea of *Diploma Supplement*. Although the concept is related to student mobility and employability in the European context, as a whole the use of this tool may facilitate the share of information among HEIs, governments, employers and learners, hence efforts should be made at all levels for main stakeholders to get more acquainted with the concept and eventually create a similar tool for the region.

8.2. Recommendations to the governments

The support and commitment from governments to HEIs in their countries is needed to establish at first a range of credit recognition system for the national level from where to progressively move on forwards to the next regional level. Hence it is suggested to the governments to create a set of clear rules or guidelines that may at least help HEIs in giving a more “organized and systematic” approach to credit transfers.

There is agreement in that the role of the governments is to provide policies and guidelines for credit recognition that are however respectful of the HEIs decisions as they are the ones in direct contact with students and academic contents. Therefore those rules need to be set on a framework that allows and promotes autonomy and responsibility among HEIs.

Governments are expected to set and continue implementing regulations and policies that allow for more flexibility at the HEIs level; while, whenever possible, providing support in the areas of technology development and improving the quality of services. Thus governments are called to ease the harmonization of HE as *barometers and promoters of change*.

Governments should feel encouraged to *establish some administration agencies* (although there might be disagreement regarding the level of authority these institutions should have) to help informing students and HEIs on the status and developments of accreditation procedures at country and regional levels. This in turn should foster educational quality

standards and operational rules for standards on accreditation and methods, calculation standard and conversion of credits, teaching quality evaluation, these agencies should be responsible for formulation, validation, coordination and implementation of academic courses.

Governments should *establish agencies to help with the organization and implementation* of a generalized credit system to be set for at national levels but articulated to the region. This should be done upon consensus from the countries and in progressive steps.

As it is the responsibility of educational organisms, like the ministries, to administer, control and coordinate the HEIs of each country, they should carry out and promote research and propose study courses with view to a regional strategic view. For example as it is explicitly set in the goals of the Campus Asia programme.

In some countries these institutions or agencies are also responsible of organizing the credit systems and of deciding the amount of credits that universities grant for courses on an agreed base; as such they should help guiding and constructing the structures of study courses and the measurements of workloads however with important participation from the HEIs. These organisms should find and propose key points that can be used for the recognition of credits especially when dealing with foreign institutions. They should as well formulate national operational standards, in order to promote the formation of clearer and more harmonized credit transfer systems.

Governments should consider opening alternative ways to register and keep records of learners' achievements, e.g. as setting of agencies to keep records of students' attainments that can be used to explain those records to other HEIs or employers. A typical example of this would be creating national credit banks or students personal academic records.

Governments should *promote a sense of responsible freedom* among HEIs and students, allowing for wider areas of autonomy regarding academic freedom as well as authority to make decisions on recognition of foreign qualifications and optional courses for students.

Governments should allow and promote the setting of double degree programmes or joint international programmes between HEIs in their countries to work as partners with HEIs overseas. These programmes are becoming increasingly visible in the region and that is because they usually account with important features like: 1) as HEIs set partnerships they too look for quality in their sister institutions, hence it works as an internal mechanism to promote quality in education among them; 2) these arrangements tend to guarantee that credits of the students are transferred smoothly avoiding conflicts and duplication; 3) these programmes are showing good practices in transferring and recognizing not only optional but also core subjects among HEIs that decide to trust each other; and 4) all this may in turn facilitate the acceptance of grades from foreign institutions.

Regionally recognized mechanisms for quality assurance under government control should be set, this is clearly a major challenge for the region as a whole however if working in a coordinated fashion at the country level important developments may take place as it is happening with the ENIC centres in the countries participating of the Bologna Process in Europe.

Governments of the region should feel encouraged to sign and ratify the Revised Regional Convention on the Recognition of Qualifications in Higher Education (Tokyo Convention).

8.3. Recommendations to HEIs

In order to make credit systems fairer to the students' efforts, HEIs should consider focusing more on evaluating students' learning outcomes rather than focusing only on learning processes. The concept of learning outcomes provides deeper understanding of not only *how* the students have learned but most importantly *what* they have achieved by successfully finishing a course. Using learning outcomes describe aspects of the course that refer to time required for learning and also level of difficulty and complexity of the course, explanation of the content about the knowledge acquired and the skills developed by the students through the course. Hence it is important that HEIs develop conceptually well-grounded curricula that go beyond the setting of syllabi per each course and clearly include descriptions of what can be expected from students to know after participating in any given study programme or course.

HEIs are called to explore and implement credit recognition system by establishing curricula that are open and transparent, at the same time support the development of more computerized management, and explore new implementation models that allow for comparison and permeability.

As HEIs apply and put into motion credit systems, they should, by nature of the systems themselves, start producing changes in their approaches to education shifting from traditional teacher-centric approaches to more student-centric forms of education.

HEIs should further explore and make their comparative advantages more widely known within their own countries and abroad by developing and fostering their own academic competitive advantages. This should eventually materialize in some form of *information base* that should help the academic performance of institutions as well as making the profiles of the professionals they produce more widely known and understood.

HEIs should provide transparent and easy to understand information to other institutions and students alike. Although most HEIs in the region are developing and providing their information packages, contents and formats still remain very diverse, hence an effort to harmonize the ways and substance of information should be made. It is a common practice among HEIs to provide course catalogues or other forms of descriptions of their systems and curricula, where content of syllabi, methods of teaching and measurement of workload in terms of credits should be clearly explained.

Related to the above HEIs should provide clear information on the students' achievements through the use of academic transcripts that offer details on the performance of the students and the grading systems being used to evaluate them. This documentation should all be made available in languages that are widely spoken. In most countries in Asia the use of English appears as a well accepted practice, although clearly the use of other languages should not be disregarded.

HEIs stand at a cross road when looking at their future, as the world is integrating rapidly into blocks and regions become increasingly interconnected, education providers need to build creative schemes that serve as incentives to promote their academic advantages and become more attractive to students through the use of credit transfer schemes. HEIs need to prepare themselves and be ready to offer their audiences a kind of formation that is more international in terms of content and methods, in order to do it they need to foster contacts with other universities and HEIs of different forms where multilateral agreements open multiple networking pathways and doors, provide courses where languages of instruction are international ones and be ready to use and explain credit transfer systems in whatever their forms.

Produce and keep information in the form of academic records and participate in events related to the diffusion and use of credit transfer systems that may be of help and guidance for their staff.

Provide quality information on their curricula and syllabi and through different channels. The effective use of online services are increasingly demonstrating that even if they may be difficult and expensive to be set at first they offer better options for access to the information to all interested parties as well as possibilities for rapid updating and changes on the information provided.

The use of different languages other than national languages for instruction, information share and explanation of procedures should be promoted.

HEIs should create manuals or guidelines that facilitate the understanding of procedures on credit transfer to students and other stakeholders. Institutions should make it easier to other HEIs, governments and students to understand how they manage their credit systems and the procedures of transfer and recognition as clear and straight forward as possible. This includes providing detailed information on how student workload is measured and how that workload becomes how many credits.

HEIs should create clear and systematic rules and procedures on the management of credit transfer situations to give institutional consistency to their credit systems among different departments and faculties in every institution (hence overcoming bilateralism).

Promote the diffusion of information on credit exchange and its use as well as to make the benefits they produce more broadly known among students.

Student mobility happens due to different reasons, some times out of self motivation and on volunteer bases, however sometimes mobility is the result of reasons out of the control of the students. In all cases however HEIs should make an effort in trying to understand the motivations behind that mobility and hence offer flexible alternatives and solutions for students like family or work related reasons.

In the case of students participating of exchange programmes, their decision to go and try alternative venues and forms of education should be taken as valuable learning experiences, where learning processes go far beyond the mere content of the subjects taken. Clearly quality of education should also be kept as a driving goal for those managing and administrating HEIs however a positive and open-minded attitude can greatly facilitate a sense of responsibility and ownership among students if they are given the chance to build their own careers.

While in the case of students that move HEIs due to other reasons should also account with a positive appreciation from those evaluating their prior learning experiences. Although this may seem naïve, it should be noted that the changes in itself is already a source of learning (regardless of quality issues) Hence a more flexible approach to credit transfer should be promoted, this is to say that even though equivalences should consider titles of subjects, contents and workload, at the time of making that appreciation the experiences of the students should be put in the context where they happened.

HEIs should start at least, considering measuring students' workload in alternative ways to traditional contact hours. Including notions like learning time and time for experience or self-study should provide optional units to assess the efforts carried out by students to achieve the learning outcomes proposed by the study courses.

Clearly detach the measurement of workload (quantity and quality of learning effort done by the students to obtain certain knowledge or skills) from measurements of achievements or performance (grades given by instructors that indicate how well the students performed or have learned). This requires the attempt from managers in HEIs to explain in detail how workload is measured in terms of distribution of workload (contact hours, differentiated by type e.g. lectures, lab practices, etc. self-study time, etc) as compared to what descriptors are used to evaluate the students' performance.

HEIs should start at least, considering the use of different forms of learning towards the achievement of learning outcomes by the students. Alternative learning experiences can greatly contribute to the formation of well qualified professionals, hence non-formal and informal learning experiences should be considered as "*accreditable*" that includes practices like participating in internships, voluntary activities, laboratory, etc. To do it, institutions will need to create tools that indicate and describe types of activities, time used as workload and how those activities contribute to the academic development of students. An alternative way to do it would be creating standard formats that learners can use to "match" and explain how their experiences can be considered as academic learning.

HEIs should consider making available wider amount of optional subjects and courses to their students (as opposed to core or compulsory subjects). By so doing they provide more flexible pathways for the students.

Similar to the point above, HEIs should consider the process of modularization of their curricula. When detaching the learning process from the notion of time (hours per week and length of courses), students may have more access to courses and learning experiences that too closely connect to the notion of academic years, semesters or other time frames that may render it more difficult for students with special needs or different expectations, e.g. students who need to work or that can finance their careers on sporadic financial incomes.

HEIs should consider recognizing qualifications of students being transferred "as they are", especially when judging the transferability of grades. The use of "pass" or "not passed/fail" marks for transferred credits appears as an unfair practice to the eyes of the students. This is because this kind of mark says nothing about the performance of the students while on exchange. This also relates to the students' chances to advance to further levels of education as well as their access to the labour market as these marks may affect their GPAs. Because of this institutions should consider and accept grades coming from other HEIs in a way that is fair and demonstrative of the students' achievements. In this sense the use of norm reference tables or percentiles can greatly facilitate the interpretation of grades into multiple grading systems.

HEIs should keep records of all financial, administrative and legal activities related to the mobility of students and of credit transfer operations as this information can help better track changes and trends in the future. Developing a regional standard mechanism and format to keep documented records, process them and make them available would greatly facilitate the share of information and would make credit transfer systems more transparent although clearly this may appear very ambitious.

8.4. Recommendations to the students

Students should be well informed about the conditions and rules for credit transfer, especially

before departing for exchange programmes as well as when moving vertically to other levels of education and or to different institutions. Accounting with good and up-to-date information is a key for successful transfer.

Students should sign learning agreements or make clear study plans with their home institutions *before departing for exchange programmes*. With assistance of an academic adviser they should at least have a clear goal on what subjects or area of subjects they should attend while on exchange. Although these arrangements should be flexible in order to allow for changes as many times it happens that courses offered by host HEIs may differ from one year to the next or may not be available.

Students should feel encouraged to keep good records of all documents related to their workload and achievements while in exchange so as to facilitate the evaluation of credits and the recognition of qualifications.

They should also feel encouraged to participate in credit transfer initiatives that provide them with wider views of the world and alternative ways to approach their careers in ways that go beyond the mere academic learning experiences.

This concludes the Recommendations, which, as explained, integrates ideas and suggestions that were gathered and put forward throughout the research. The ideas put forward in the previous pages condense the views from researchers in SEAMEO RIHED, the resource persons that contributed to this study at the national level, as well as participants in the two workshops organized by SEAMEO RIHED as part of the *Explore* phase of the project.

It should be noted at this point that these recommendations serve as a platform from where the next phases of the project *Harmonization and Networking in Higher Education. Building a Common Credit Transfer System for GMS and beyond* will be developed.

The last chapter of this report presents a strategic plan to carry the project forward as envisioned at the time of writing this report (March 2013).

8.5. Other considerations: Results from group discussions during workshops 1 and 2

Bangkok, September and November 2012

In order to foster ownership of the outcomes of the research, to allow the creation of a wider platform for participation and to make the future steps of the project a participatory process SEAMEO RIHED made an open invitation to main stakeholders in HE in the region to participate of two workshops. In these occasions resource persons from the countries included at this stage were invited to present their findings on the credit systems and transfer opportunities of their respective cases, and on a second stage of both the workshops all participants were invited to provide their views on the ways they foresee harmonization of credit transfer systems should happen in the region.

To gather main stakeholders' views on what are the *ideal features of multilateral credit transfer systems*, discussions were organized around four areas:

1. Recognition: acceptance/agreements/requirements
2. Credit equivalency and transfer: conversion
3. Grading systems and grade transfer
4. Information support system/documentation and system context

With view on the requirements, structural differences and degrees of application, of different credit transfer systems participants were requested to put forward ideas for the future of credit systems and the transferability of credits they believe may be welcomed by governments and HEIs. Participants and resources persons discussed *ideal features of credit transfer systems* focusing on multilateral rather than bilateral approaches; then they proposed options for action and feasible tools for the region.

Discussions moved around specific concepts seeking to deepen findings of *Explore* phase of the project, each of the topics touched upon specific issues and discussions show different levels of agreement between participants regarding ideas proposed on the ideal features needed for transferability of credits to improve in the region.

The level of agreement among participants regarding the ideas proposed by each group resulting from their discussions, topics were classified as *high agreement, medium agreement* and *disagreement among participants*.

The level of agreement was determined based on the amount of questions, rejections or comments against from other participants to ideas presented by the groups on each topic, hence:

High agreement

Means that there was no- existent debate or rejection to ideas presented by the group. There were no comments against and questions were clarifying or explanatory. It was considered as high agreement when the same ideas were presented by other groups.

Medium level of agreement

Means that the ideas proposed by groups were questioned and discussed. There was debate regarding nature and scope of the ideas but no open conflict or rejection.

Disagreement

Means that participants openly rejected and discussed ideas put forward by groups. A final solution or consent could not be reached. This happened in two cases, where debates were lively and vigorous:

- a) Discussion on who has authority to recognize credits (governments or HEIs)
- b) Recognition (or not) of e-learning and long distance learning

The following chart summarizes main areas discussed.

Table 16: Outcomes from the discussions during Workshops 1 and 2

Areas of discussion	<i>High agreement among participants</i>	<i>Medium agreement among participants</i>	<i>Disagreement among participants</i>
---------------------	--	--	--

1. Recognition	<i>Mutual recognition relates to partnership</i> --> possible to create shared standards	<i>Equivalence</i> : content of subjects should be comparable in at least 60%	Who has authority to decide on recognition of qualifications: Governments? Specialized agencies? HEIs? All of them <i>together</i> ? Some of them <i>combined</i> ? Some of them <i>only</i> ?)
	<i>Mutual recognition relates to reputation of HEIs</i> . Easier among similar tier HEIs	Use of <i>elective courses</i> to allow transfer of courses outside the programme	
	<i>Time units</i> should be the main unit of comparison of workload	Recognition of non-core courses relates to the profile sought in the students by HEIs	
	Courses to be transferred must be relevant to programme and of similar complexity		
	<i>Comparability</i> is based on clear description of programmes, course contents, methods and outcomes		
	Level of courses (under & post graduate) should be considered for accreditation		
2. Quality Assurance			
2. Quality Assurance	High agreement among participants	Medium agreement among participants	
	QA crucial for credit transfer for it is the base for trust building	Need to promote use of QA mechanisms (internal and external) to facilitate trust and recognition A practical solution: having <i>fix reference rulers</i> that describe and clarify practices and outcomes	
	Use of university rankings help develop cooperation agreements		
	Information on QA must be reliable and accountable		
	For transfer of credits to happen QA must be ensured at national and HEIs level		
	Bilateral MOUs help build trust on QA		
3. Credit equivalence			
3. Credit equivalence	High agreement among participants	Medium agreement among participants	Disagreement among participants
	Methods of instruction affect decisions on credit transfer (teacher-centred vs. student-centred)	More acceptance of alternative ways to measure workload (learning outcomes combined with time)	Transfer of credits for long-distance and e-learning programmes due to hassles in monitoring substance, relevance and actual learning. Three positions: 1) promoting acceptance based on fairness; 2) discourage transfer due to threats to QA; 3) leaving the issue out of the discussion is unfair and unrealistic
	There should be maximum amount of transferable credits (percentage of total amount of credits in a programme)	Alternative to time (unit for comparison): transfers <i>as course-to-course</i>	
	Clearly defined time frames of courses. (E.g. semesters or quarter system or simply comparing workloads)	A solution to equation of subjects may be using the criteria set by UMAP as <i>practical and workable framework</i>	
	Need of a tool to deal with diversity - Weigh credits and relation to workload - distribution of academic & notional time		
	<i>Cocktail of factors</i> to value credits (lectures, self-study, attendance, participation, level of courses, etc)		
	Support of transfer decisions from recognized bodies (public QA agencies)		
	Accreditation of non-academic learning		
4. Transfer of credits			
4. Transfer of credits	High agreement among participants		
	Transfers are possible <i>only</i> for learning achievements with <i>passing or above grades</i>		

	<p>Upon students' return from exchange programmes, home HEIs may request students to make up for <i>gaps</i> by examinations or other catch-up-activities to ensure core skills and knowledge</p> <p>HEIs issue and review transcripts. When review information issued by other HEIs they should do it with open spirit and consider other institutions as <i>partners</i> providing similar contents and quality</p> <p>There need to be a minimum level of similarity in the instruction/learning methods (e.g. contact hours and lab work). Level of similarity in content of subjects must be agreed by and understood by both HEIs and students (E.g. 60 or 70% and the student makes up for gaps at home institutions)</p> <p>There need to be limits to the amount of transferable credits. (E.g. 75% of the total workload for a degree obtained from the HEI issuing the degree; or only 1/3 of the total amount of credits needed for graduation may be obtained and transferred from other HEIs as a result of exchange programmes)</p> <p>As relevance of time to measure workload decreases, HEIs should consider learning outcomes instead and consider including more qualitative perspectives</p> <p>There is a need to consider <i>relative value</i> and <i>amount of transferable credits</i> according to level of degrees. (E.g. for undergraduates in exchange maximum should be up to 30%; for postgraduates transfers should be allowed up to 50% (difference due to complexity and research)</p> <p>Attention should be given to differences among HE systems in areas like: use or not of "foundation years"; use of "majors & minors": "compulsory/core" as opposed to "optional/selective" subjects</p>
5. Grade Transfer	<p style="text-align: center;">High agreement among participants</p> <p>To make grades transfer possible HEIs need flexible and open minded attitudes, trusting the students and acknowledging evaluations partner HEIs do of students' performances. The logic is: <i>If your university send your student, whom you selected, to study in a partner HEIs you selected. Why should the student perform less effectively in an institution to which you committed to trust?</i></p> <p>Transfer of grades means analysis of syllabi and curricula; hence to value workload and performance, and to transfer credits, HEIs should -in the same way- recognize grades according to efforts and achievements</p> <p>Acceptance of grades should relate to learning outcomes; if information in transcripts is not enough home HEIs may request for details to host HEIs and control accomplishments by the students. If learning outcomes are real and accounted for there is no reason not to grant the grades as they are.</p> <p>Evaluation towards acceptance of grades should include analysis of methods of instruction. Students should be made aware of this, so as to make informed decisions</p>
6. Possible areas of conflict	<p style="text-align: center;">High agreement among participants</p> <p>Due to differences in syllabi; HEIs need to analyse students work case-by-case HEIs should focus on content studied but more importantly on how that content (knowledge and skills) will be used by students in their careers</p> <p>It is recommended that academic committees support decision makers when evaluating credits and grades from other HEIs. HEIs should have operational units to inform and support decisions on recognition. This means redefining roles, competencies and authorities within the institutions.</p> <p>Areas of major challenge include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) gaps and inconsistencies among grading systems among institutions and countries (e.g. number, letters, percentages, etc); 2) gaps in learning and teaching systems; 3) kind of interactions resulting from the systems: student-centred or teacher-centred <p>Many participants express the desire to account with reference tables to convert grades, but a sense of caution is observed when considering that reference tables for grading systems are difficult to implement and unrealistic because they attach fix conversions to figures that evolve over time. In advance experiences of integration what happens is that HEIs develop <i>their own tables</i> As an alternative: <i>mapping grade systems for conversion</i> in countries and HEIs should ease understanding, but this should only serve as reference</p>
	High agreement among participants

<p>7. Course assessment criteria</p>	<p>Assessments of students' workloads and performances should be done at least upon:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assignments by teachers and response from students - management of their own self-study time - learning experiences and participation in academic projects - outcomes from mid-terms and final examinations - homework - class participation - attendance - tutorials - Etc. 	
<p>8. Dealing with different grading systems</p>	<p>High agreement among participants</p>	<p>Medium agreement among participants</p>
	<p>There is a desire to account with <i>a common ground, a standard tool to understand grades</i>. However challenges remain due to constant changes in grading systems issues like: 1) determining who will set that tool; 2) What authority it will have; 3) How changes over time will be treated; etc</p>	<p>Creating a <i>Conversion Protocol</i> (a table of major systems -or a representative sample-) can ease interpretation of grading systems. Sharing this information should include "qualitative room for grading"(E.g. give teachers a space to explain more details on the grades and students' performances)</p>
	<p>HEIs sending and receiving students temporary or permanently should make it clear to students that conversions and transfers of credits and grades <i>may be</i> implemented and special considerations may be necessary after completion of courses. Providing students this information gives them better chances for success as they plan their learning experiences</p>	<p>Governments and HEIs need to consider <i>grading at the regional level</i> and to seek for a tool to see trends among different systems and making them come into closer interpretations. E.g. from letters to percentages, or from scores to percentages. A practical solution is to convert all forms of grades into percentages, but this may be unrealistic. An expectable challenge here is that that HEIs need to agree on minimum passing marks. E.g. 60 or 50%.</p>
	<p>Acceptance by home/receiving HEIs of grades coming from foreign/sending HEIs should remain a right of the home/receiving HEI</p>	<p>A positive step would be that institutions and countries consent and engage on models based on common percentages as a base for harmonization; E.g. setting a <i>pass mark</i> as equal or above to 60 %; a <i>fail mark</i> as less than 60%; an A mark as equal to 80 to 100%, etc</p>
	<p>Agreements among HEIs that contain tables of conversion should facilitate transfer of grading; combining all possible systems may serve as a <i>general reference</i>, but it should not be used as a <i>tabula rasa</i>.</p>	
	<p>Even if tedious and time-consuming, evaluation and conversion of grades should be done case-by-case to ensure fairness</p>	
<p>9. Options for grade transfer</p>	<p>High agreement among participants</p>	
	<p>It is important to offer options and information to students before they go on exchange so they can make better decide on whether to take certain subjects according to the transferability of the credits they produce. Role of supervisors at home HEIs is central</p>	
	<p>Decisions on <i>what</i> and <i>how much to transfer</i> should include the views from experts like academic committees and professors and those of the students as well</p>	
	<p>A positive step toward integration in the region would be that an organization or group of organizations with enough authority develop a guideline that can be widely accepted by HEIs and governments. The drafting of such instrument should be participatory and open.</p>	
<p>10.</p>	<p>High agreement among participants</p>	

Supporting mechanism and system context	<p>There is a need to set a modern and comprehensive information system that does not compromise local perspectives, i.e. a mechanism to share information at the regional level that is inclusive, democratic and designed on a two ways strategy (top down and down top to enhance participation and guaranty decision making power to governments and HEIs)</p> <p>This initiative should not represent a major challenge, at least in its technical aspects</p>
	<p>Government in the region should consider and assess the feasibility of creating an <i>ASEAN/Asian Credit Transfer Unit</i> -as a regional information knot to centralize and keep updated information, and to support decisions on academic credit issues-. This unit should advise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Governments in terms of policies and reforms ○ HEIs in terms of strategies for implementation, good practices and evaluation ○ Students if they decide to participate in academic activities related to credit transfer. <p>A mechanism of this sort should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ be of use in broader scenarios as well (beyond credit transfer) ○ offer multilateral access and rules should be set on voluntary acceptance ○ contain -at a minimum- information on curricula and syllabi (content descriptions, text books, method of delivery and assessment provided by each HEI) ○ be made easily available and understandable for all
	<p>HEIs should continue to explore and develop more online options</p> <p>Information should be provided in the universities' websites and interconnected</p> <p>Information should be available in national languages and English as a minimum</p> <p>HEIs should offer access and guidance to related websites and other sources of information</p>
	<p>As academic committees in every HEI play a central role in the decision of transfer of credits and grades, those decisions, rules and procedures should be kept as records and made accessible. The compilation of these records serves to understand previous decisions and contexts, and help keeping track of good practices for future references</p>
	<p>HEIs should provide detailed information as a minimum on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) location of city/university b) academic calendar c) English (or other languages) proficiency requirements d) information on English-based programmes and other international programmes e) detailed information on courses' titles and descriptions d) Etc.
	<p>Documents and other forms of information share tools should at a minimum include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) paper work requirements and formalities (visas, features of the degrees, applications, fees, important deadlines, etc) b) information on their foreign and own language-based programmes –especially those in English- c) International programmes with details on curriculum-course code/course title and description d) Etc.

The following paragraphs present the analysis of those discussions in more detail.

8.5.1. Recognition

Groups discussing area *Recognition* focused on:

- Mutual recognition/acceptance/agreements/"trust"
- Factors/requirements/criteria to make programmes agree to accept transfer of credits from other HEIs or programmes
- Factors affecting recognition

The debate on the issue of *recognition* produced the following outcomes:

Groups/participants agree on that:

- *Mutual recognition* relates to *partnership, consortia* or other forms of cooperation set in bi or multilateral agreements by HEIs and governments to create standard (or at least compatible) frameworks.
- Recognition relates to institutional reputation and rankings of HEIs → The more similar the perceptions HEIs hold of each other, the easier the mutual recognition. (Similar to *diplomatic relations* among partners of the *same tier*. Problem: how to overcome gaps of this sort).
- Time should be the main unit of comparison (number and definition of academic hours and lengths of courses)
- To be considered for transfer the content of courses must be relevant to the programme and of similar complexity.
- Compatibility / comparability of contents, methods of teaching and outcomes should be described and considered.
- Levels of programme and courses should be described and considered.
- Programme specifications: detailed syllabi, number of academic terms, hours spent on lectures, laboratory and practical practices, outline of courses, etc. should be described and considered.

Most groups/participants agree on that:

- For transfer and recognition of courses to happen on *equivalence of subjects*, those courses should be comparable or have similar contents in at least 60% or more.
- *Courses outside the programme* may or may not be transferable. Key factor: recognition or not of “elective courses” by the programme.
- Recognition of different courses (not core or mainstream) relates to the profile HE systems and programmes want for their graduates.

Groups/participants disagree on:

- Who should have authority to decide on matters of recognition of qualifications (Governments? Specialized authoritative agencies? HEIs? All of them *together*? Some of them *combined*? Some of them *only*?)

8.5.2. Quality assurance

Groups discussing on *quality assurance* focused on:

- Whether or not quality is a requirement for credit transfer to happen. If yes,
 - o Which quality assurance/ranking/accreditation system(s) are acceptable? And to what levels: National? Regional? Others?
 - o At what level — HEIs or programme— should quality assurance be made in order to facilitate credit transfer?

Groups/participants agree on that:

- Quality in education and the mechanisms to ensure it is crucial when considering credit transfer since inter-institutional cooperation is more likely to happen when quality assurance (institutionalized or not) is set and reliable.
- Reliable HE rankings help institutions develop cooperation agreements because they serve to gauge HEIs’ similarities and differences (E.g. prestige, quality of programmes, infrastructure, Etc.).
- Information provided on quality assurance needs to be reliable and accountable.

- For transfer of credits to happen quality assurance must be done in all countries and at all levels: national and HEIs.
- Previous agreements among countries and/or HEIs (E.g. MoUs) are the most recognized base of trust.

Most groups/participants agree on that:

- There is a need to promote the use of quality assurance mechanisms to facilitate recognition, and a practical solution to this should be accounting with documents and other *fix reference rulers* that describe and clarify practices and outcomes.

8.5.3. Credit equivalence

Groups discussing *credit equivalency* focused on:

- Comparability of workload (Number of hours? Kind of hours? etc)
- Lengths of academic hours
- Transferability of credits:
 - One-to-one? (based on number of hours)
 - Course-to-course?
 - Using conversion factors? Which ones?

Groups/participants agree on that:

- Methods of instruction highly affect decisions about credit transfer.
- There should be maximum allowable transferred credits (E.g. a percentage of the total amount of credits in a programme).
- Importance of clearly defined time frames of the courses. (E.g. semesters or quarter system or simply comparing workloads).
- There is a need to create mechanisms that facilitate dealing with diversity; especially regarding weighing credits and their relation to workload and distribution of academic and notional time.
- When appraising credits a “cocktail of factors” must be considered (e.g. combining lecture hours, operating hours and self-study hours, class attendance, participation, together with the number of credits to be assigned depending on syllabus and level of courses).
- Approval and support of transfer decisions from recognized accreditation bodies (most likely public agencies) is highly desired as it relates to the quality assurance.
- There is a need to start considering accreditation of non-academic forms of learning (E.g. internships and working experiences).

Most groups/participants agree on that:

- Although time (i.e. academic years, semesters or quarters) is widely used to calculate workload there is growing acceptance towards the need to use alternative forms (E.g. learning outcomes). However concern remains regarding feasibility.
- An alternative proposition to the use of time should be the acceptance of transfers based on equivalences such as *course-to-course* as a practical solution.
- A feasible solution to equation of subjects may be adjusting to the criteria set by UMAP as *practical and workable framework* to deal with equivalences.

Groups/participants disagree on:

- Transferability of credits for long-distance and e-learning programmes due to hassles in monitoring substance, relevance and actual learning. Three positions were put forward in this regard: one promoting acceptance of the transfer of these credits based on fairness; a second one seeing too many threats to quality assurance, hence discouraging transferability; and a third one arguing that leaving the issue out of the discussion would be unfair and unrealistic, proposing alternative ways to ensure quality and recognition.

8.5.4. Transferability of credits

Groups discussing on *course comparability/equivalency* focused on:

- Transferability for same courses: requisites to set equivalence to accept foreign credits (title, content, etc.)
- Role of elective/optional courses and core courses. For example: Are credits from a course that is not in the programme of the home university acceptable for transfer?

Groups/participants agree on that:

Credits to be transferred typically work on the following premises:

- Transfers are based information provided by students and HEIs; transfers are possible *only* for learning achievements with *passing or above grades*.
- Upon students' return from exchange programmes, home HEIs may request students to make up for *gaps* by examinations or other catch-up-activities to ensure core skills and knowledge, and to cover gaps students may have left from exchange experiences.
- HEIs issue and review transcripts. Homes HEIs review information issued by host HEIs on students' workload; when doing it home HEIs should consider other institutions as *partners* providing (and accepting) same or similar content and quality.
- There must be at least a minimum level of similarity in the instruction/learning methods (e.g. contact hours and lab work). The level or amount of similarity in content of subjects (e.g. 60 or 70% and the student makes up for gaps at home institutions) must be agreed by and understood by institutions and students.
- There should be limitations to the amount of transferable credits. E.g. 75% of the total workload needed for a degree should be obtained from the HEI issuing the degree; or only 1/3 of the total amount of credits necessary for graduation can be obtained and transferred as workload from other institutions as a result of exchange programmes.
- As relevance of time to measure workload decreases (less use of semesters or quarters), HEIs should consider learning outcomes instead and more qualitative perspectives.
- There is a need to consider *relative value* and *amount of transferable credits* according to level of degrees. E.g. in undergraduate programmes, for exchanges the maximum should be up to 30%, for master and doctorate programmes transfers should be allowed up to 50% (the difference is based on complexity and the role of research).
- Attention should be given to differences among HE systems in matters like: the use of not of "foundation years", the use of "majors and minors", "compulsory and core" subjects as opposed to optional or selective ones.

8.5.5. Grade Transfer

Groups discussing on *grade transfer* focused on:

- Factors / requirements / criteria affecting decision on acceptance of grades from other HEIs

- Dealing with different grading systems: scores and grades
- Options for grade transfer

Groups/participants agree on that:

- To make grades transfer possible HEIs should adopt flexible and open minded attitudes, try to understand; and accept what students did while on exchange, based on *trusting the students* and acknowledging evaluations partner institutions do of the performance of the students. The logic is: “if you as a university send your students, who you selected yourself, to participate in an exchange programme, why should the student perform less effectively and learn less because s/he takes classes in a different institution; to which you have previously committed to trust?”
- Transfer of grades implies the analysis of course syllabi and programme curricula; hence to valuation of performance, workload and transfer of credits should -in the same way- be granted a mark according to efforts and achievements.
- Acceptance and transfer of grades should be related to the learning outcomes achieved by the students; if information in transcripts is not enough home institutions should have the right to request for more details to host institutions and to control actual accomplishment of the students. If learning outcomes are real and accounted for there should be no reason not to grant the grades as they are presented by the host institutions.
- Evaluation towards acceptance to transfer grades should include analysis of methods of instruction. Students should be made aware of the implications of this, so that they can make informed decisions.

8.5.6. Sources of possible conflict

When HEIs participate in cooperation programmes with other institutions normally face a number of conflicts. Being aware of them may help them be prepared to address those issues when they arise. These *conflicts* occur due to:

- Differences in syllabi offered by HEIs and selected courses by students; hence institutions need to analyse students work on a case-by-case base to find similarities in syllabi and curricula. This means focusing on what students have studied as content and more importantly how those lessons, knowledge and skills will be applied in their careers.
- It is recommended that to address issues of this sort academic committees are set guide and support decision makers when evaluating and deciding on recognition or not of credits and grades from other institutions. Institutions should find and account with persons or operational units to help inform and support decisions on recognition. This relates to the need to redefine roles, competencies and authorities within the formal structure of the institutions.
- Among the main challenges there is the issues of 1) gaps and inconsistencies among grading systems among institutions and countries (e.g. number, letters, percentages, etc); 2) different learning and teaching systems; and 3) the kind of interactions that result from those systems: student-centred, teacher-centred or institution-centred.
- Although many participants put forward the desire to account with reference tables that help translate and interpret grades, a sense of caution is also tangible among them as a small but well informed group puts forward the fact that reference tables for grading systems tend in fact to be both difficult to implement and unrealistic as they usually attach fix conversions to figures that by definition change over time and evolve. In more

advance experiences of integration such as the Bologna process what has actually happened is that institutions have instead tended to develop *their own tables* which in many cases may not work or measure grades in the same way a general table does.

Mapping grade systems for conversion in countries and HEIs should ease understanding and facilitate dialogue, but an effort of this kind should only serve as reference.

8.5.7. Course assessment criteria

There is wide agreement in that the assessments of students' workloads and performances should be done upon:

- assignments and response from students
- management of their own self-study time
- learning experiences and academic projects
- outcomes from mid-terms and final examinations
- homework
- class participation
- attendance
- tutorials
- Etc.

8.5.8. Dealing with different grading systems

Groups/participants agree on that:

- Acceptance by home/receiving institutions of grades coming from foreign/sending institutions should remain a right of the home/receiving institution and its system.
- Even if tedious and time-consuming, work related to evaluation and conversion of grades should be flexible and case-by-case to ensure fair treatment.
- There is a need to create *a common ground, a standard mechanism to understand grades*. However challenges remain for the creation of a tool of this sort due to permanent changes grading systems undergo and to difficulties like: 1) determining who will set that *chart*; 2) What authority will it have; 3) How will changes along time be treated; etc.
- Written agreements among HEIs that contain tables of conversion should facilitate transfer of grading; combining all possible systems may serve as a *general reference*, however it should not be used as a *tabula rasa*. A tool of this sort should be helpful for bilateral and multilateral schemes.
- Parties to cooperation agreements sending and receiving students on temporary exchanges or permanently should make it clear to students that conversions and transfers of credits and grades *may be* implemented, however that special considerations may be necessary even after completion of courses. Providing students updated and comprehensive information gives them better chances for success as they will know how to plan their learning experiences.

Some groups/participants agree on that:

- Creating a *Conversion Protocol* (a table with all major grading systems -or at least with a representative sample-) can facilitate the interpretation of different grading systems. The transfer and share of this information should include some "qualitative room" for grading and information sharing, e.g. give teachers a space to express and explain more details on the grades and students' performances.

- There is a need to consider grading at the regional level and to seek for a strategy to understand trends among different systems and making them come into closer interpretations, e.g. 1) from letter grade to percentages; 2) from scores to percentages; or 3) from workload to percentages.
- A practical strategy to convert grades would be the use of percentages. However an expectable challenge here relates to the need that HEIs agree on minimum passing marks.
- A positive step would be that institutions and countries consent and engage on models based on common percentages as a base for harmonization; E.g. setting a *pass mark* as equal or above to 60 %; a *fail mark* as less than 60%; an A mark as equal to 80 to 100%, etc.

8.5.9. Options for grade transfer

There is wide agreement in that it is important to provide diverse options to students before they go on exchange so that they can make more informed decisions on whether to take or not certain subjects according to the transferability of those credits to both sending and receiving HEIs. Here the role of the supervisors at home institutions becomes central.

The decision on what and how much to transfer should include the opinion from experts like academic committees and professors and should include the views of the students as well.

Participants agree in that it would be a positive step forward towards more integration in the region if there was an organization or group of organizations with enough authority to develop a common guideline that can be widely accepted by HEIs and governments. The drafting of such guideline or instrument should be participatory, open and function as a consortium.

8.5.10. Supporting mechanisms and system context

Groups discussing on *supporting mechanisms and system context* focused on:

- Information support system/documentation (student's study plan, syllabus, diploma supplement, etc)
- Procedures: major steps, decisions, processing time, etc
- Roles of government / ministry – HEIs
- Other important issues — recommendations only

Groups/participants agree on that:

- There is a need to develop and set a modern and comprehensive information system towards the regionalization of HE; however this should not compromise local perspectives, i.e. a regional information system should be inclusive, democratic and designed on a two ways strategy (top down and down top to enhance participation and giving decision making power to both governmental agencies and HEIs).
- In a world of advanced communications, this initiative should not represent a major challenge, at least in its technical sphere.
- An issue that should be considered and researched is the setting of an ASEAN/Asian Credit Transfer Unit, as a regional information knot that to keep updated information, provide guidance and support on credit transfer issues to all stakeholders:
 - o for governments in terms of policies and necessary reforms
 - o for HEIs in terms of implementation strategies and good practices

- for students to give them a clear view of the options they have if they decide to embark on credit exchange activities.
- Information sharing systems of this sort would be applicable in broader scenarios (beyond credit transfer system).
- These systems should offer multilateral access and rules should be set on voluntary acceptance.
- They should contain -at a minimum- information on curricula and syllabi (content descriptions, text books, method of delivery and assessment)
- They should be made easily available and understandable for all.
- HEIs should continue to explore and develop more online options (making information available and updating it on the Internet); that information should be provided through universities' websites and catalogues and in English as a minimum. Institutions should offer access and guidance to related websites and sources of information.
- As academic committees in HEIs play a role in the decision of transferability of credits and grades their rules and procedures should be kept as records and made accessible to all. The compilation of these records serves to understand previous decisions and contexts, and help keeping track of good practices for future references.
- HEIs should provide detailed information on: a) location of city/university; b) academic calendar; c) English (or other languages) proficiency requirements; d) information on English-based programmes and other international programmes, e) detailed information on courses' titles and descriptions.
- Transcripts and other relevant information should be clear and include: a) paper work requirements (visas, features of the degrees, applications, fees, important deadlines, etc); b) information on their foreign and own language-based programmes –especially for those in English-; c) International programmes with details on curriculum-course code/course title and description, etc.

Recommendations presented here open the door for new questions and new action plans. The findings put forward in previous pages greatly call for further actions that can help continue the process of integration in the region and specifically in making the landscape of HE more harmonic. The next chapter presents a brief description of the activities proposed by SEAMEO RIHED for the upcoming phases of the project.

9. Way forward for the project: Proposed model for phase two: *Experiment*

Harmonization and Networking in Higher Education

Building a Common Credit Transfer System for GMS and beyond

Asian Convention on Academic Credit Recognition for HEIs

Development and implementation of pilot project

The previous chapters this report put forward the design and outcomes from the research process in phase 1 -*Explore*- of the project *Harmonization and Networking in Higher Education. Building a Common Credit Transfer System for Great Mekong Subregion and beyond*; pages to come propose a series of actions towards the implementation of Phases 2, 3 & 4: *Experiment, Experience & Expand*.

9.1. Introduction and background

Regional integration continues deepen in different parts of the world and Asian nations too have shown increasing will to deepen interactions towards advancing economic and social development.

Within this context the upcoming setting up of *ASEAN Community* expected to function as a people-centred and socially responsible association together with the goals set at the *GMS Human Resource Development Strategic Framework and Action Plan* to further harmonize the landscape of HE in the region; Phases 2, 3 & 4 (*Experiment, Experience & Expand*) of the project seek to ease that process through fostering reforms and bringing into line national regulations, standards and procedures to facilitate the cross-border flow of students.

HE has a central role in developing capable human resources to contribute to productive systems and economies. Now more than ever the educational systems face the challenges brought by regional integration and need to be ready to produce professionals capable of responding to more complex demands from labour market. Encouraging cross-border student mobility is an effective strategy to develop a well-trained internationally aware workforce.

Germinating from the focus on Great Mekong Subregion to further expand on to the whole South East Asian Region and beyond, the project aims to create a framework to harmonize credit transfer arrangements in HE and to develop a network of institutions, including both governments, universities and other HEIs to cooperate and foster international student mobility among countries in the region through the use of comprehensive multilateral credit transfer systems.

9.2. Rationale

Phase 1 -*Explore*- showed that even if regional multilateral credit transfer systems exist, the amount of students moving *within* the region remains relatively small and that still most exchanges happen based on bilateral agreements at the country-to-country or university-to-

university levels. At the same time the bulk of exchanges are directed outbound, typically to developed countries usually outside Asia rather than *among* these countries.

Even if multilateral credit transfer systems have been set in the region they provide only partial answers to student mobility as some of them are either *too general and all too inclusive* like in the models set by UCTS -UMAP's credit transfer system or ACTS -as set in the Asia Cooperation Dialogue scheme (Asia e University, n.d.), (Asia Cooperation Dialogue, 2011) , while others are too narrow allowing limited number of HEIs to participate like in the cases of AUN and AIMS programmes. Findings in this regard greatly coincide with previous research in this issue, where for instance political and historical aspects have hinder the participation of countries in multilateral systems, particularly clear in the case of China not becoming a member of UMAP. (Hawkins, 2012)

Findings from Phase 1 confirm a trend towards the rapid expansion and *complexification* of the high education landscape, with growing amount of public, private and mix institutions, growing amount of disciplines and more specialized contents, using different names and languages, following various goals, providing different kinds of degrees, etc. which serve as indicators of the major changes taking place in the region towards broader access to more people (*massification*), growing concern towards quality and democratization of HE.

Likewise, and especially for the scope of this project, *Explore* reflects wide diversity in the nature and procedures used to transfer academic credits within and *among* countries. Findings suggest increasing fluidity and permeability of transfer systems and a progressive shift from traditional bilateral arrangements towards more inclusive and multilateral schemes; findings also imply growing awareness on the need of HEIs to become more attractive, better qualified and financially sustainable. HE is booming due to increasing demands from productive sectors in most modern societies, this brings about a change in the traditional nature of education. Now more than ever before the sector needs to go out of its historical clusters and become attractive, ensure the provision of quality programmes and face more competition.

Explore shows growing awareness among stakeholders in HE on the need to deepen the connections between HEIs themselves with the productive sectors in their countries and beyond national borders. This in turn relates to the need to have internationally sensitive personnel, proficient in different languages and able to understand and appreciate multiculturalism as a source of synergy in the search for new markets and opportunities.

9.3. Justification (Relevance of implementing next phases)

The project as a whole aims at responding to the following demands:

- The need of HE systems and HEIs to adjust to a context of increasing regional integration.
- The call for strategies to promote students' mobility to boost international awareness with view to growing competition and opportunities as national borders become blurrier.
- The responsibility of HEIs to contribute to the further creation, development and consolidation of mechanisms for quality assurance.
- The need to systematically answer to students' demands for standard mechanisms for vertical and horizontal mobility.

- Synthesize lessons learnt about to how credit transfer systems function; how they can be used more effectively and fairly; and how multilateral agreements work more inclusive and extensively.
- Hence Phases 2, 3 & 4 of the project are designed to bring answers through an action plan to address those demands.

9.4. Goals of the project in its next stages

Phase 1 –*Explore*– compared and assessed multilateral credit transfer systems globally with focus on the region and the use of multilateral procedures, to spot more *workable practices*. As such the first stage provides ground-based evidence upon which the next phases are to be implemented.

The project as a whole seeks to create a shared multilateral credit transfer framework; in other words it seeks to produce a *model* that is fit for all countries and HEIs in the region; that allows for cooperation between government agencies and HEIs to be *doers* and the *decision makers*; and that include the views of students.

The project seeks to ease and increase students’ mobility to:

1. Deepen the link between demands of the labour market and the provision of HE.
2. Continue to internationalize and to widen HE regarding continuous and borderless education.
3. Create mechanisms to harmonize processes among HE systems.
4. Build trust among institutions to smoothen the process of mutual recognition and accreditation.
5. Develop standard academic transfer procedures that are easily understandable for all stakeholders and flexible enough to respect diversity and autonomy.
6. Strengthen the sense of ownership and responsibility among all stakeholders.

9.5. Action plan: reaching the goals

Based on the information gathered in phase 1 the next phases are designed to achieve the above goals through specific actions:

Goals	objectives
Short and mid-term	
1. Develop standard transfer procedures	- Develop and promote a conventional agreement on transfer principles and procedures for HEIs “ <i>Asian Convention on Academic Credit Recognition for HEIs</i> ”
2. Internationalize HE systems	- Provide technical support student mobility programmes - Promote multilateral mechanisms for recognition, particularly the “ <i>Asian Convention on Academic Credit Recognition for HEIs</i> ”
3. harmonization of HE	- Promote multilateral dialogue and cooperation among HES - Facilitate share of information
4. Strengthen ownership	- Incorporate stakeholders inputs: 1) Mobile students; 2) HEIs; 3) Governments; and 4) the private sector

Longer run	
5. Build trust among HEIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share curricular developments to spot complementary areas - Foster cooperation with quality assurance agents - Foster cooperation for complementation of programmes
6. Deepen the relation labour market – HES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research on trends, demands and expectations. - Consider channels for communication: private sector - HES.

Proposed activities and implementation units, tentative time required for implementation

Phase 2 –*Experiment*- will take place in three stages:

- 1) Develop and agree on “Asian Convention on Academic Credit Recognition for HEIs”
- 2) Dissemination and revision
- 3) Implementation and Pilot

Stage 1: Develop and agree on “Asian Convention on Academic Credit Recognition for HEIs”

- RIHED to develop the draft of Asian Convention on Academic Credit Recognition for HEIs. (Time required: four weeks).

Stage 2: Dissemination and revision

- First dissemination process of draft: RIHED to seek for acknowledgement, consideration and participatory inputs from HEIs to be involved in the pilot, governments and related agencies. (Campaign for diffusion and engagement. E.g. workshop for representatives from universities in AIMS* and other pioneers**. (Time required 12 weeks)
- Review, dissemination and agreement on final text by RIHED and HEIs. (Time required: 8 weeks)

State 3: Implementation and Pilot.

- Start application of the Convention among pioneer HEIs (AIMS programme) – Pilot (Time required 25 weeks, depending on academic calendars)
- Preliminary evaluation & consolidation of project into the future (*Experience*) (last 8 weeks of phase 2 to start collection of data and preliminary evaluation)

*Note: the selection of the AIMS (Asia International Mobility for Students) programme is based on the fact that this is an ongoing exchange programme and that financial constraints in terms of student mobility are currently covered by existing government financed scholarships.

**Note: Participation and accession to the Convention will be open to other universities and HEIs beyond the AIMS programme.

9.6. Expected outcomes

Through the implementation of phase 2 of the project it is expected that:

1. HEIs in the region progressively embrace and use the terms of the *Asian Convention on Academic Credit Recognition for HEIs* in more standardized and better harmonized procedures for measurement, transfer and recognition of students workloads (typically but not only academic credits).
2. Progressive growing support from governments to internationalization of HE based on systematic procedures of regional scope applied at the HEIs level.
3. Growth in the mass of mobile students *within* the region (re-direction of students flows) due to promotion of alternative destinations and use of agreed procedures.
4. Increasingly attractive HEIs in the region for students as programmes become more visible, accessible and intertwined.
5. Increase in access to exchange programmes to more students due to shorter distances; and in the case of ASEAN due to the relatively similar living standards and costs of living.
6. In the longer run, improvements and more cooperation in quality assurance and curricular development.

9.8. Tentative structure of the *Asian Convention on Academic Credit Recognition for HEIs*

1. Goals:

- Contribute to the regionalization of HE by boosting a sense of identity and “regional brand” based on Asia’s comparative advantages
- Promote an open and responsible spirit among HEIs regarding mechanisms to facilitate student mobility
- Provide technical support on issues of value recognition, transfer and accreditation of academic (and non-academic) students’ workloads.
- Promote efficient management of time and resources for students in HE programmes.
- Promote HE enrolment and boost completion rates
- Promote sense of ownership and responsibility among students regarding their professional futures and careers.
- Reduce duplication of work due to bilateralism by promoting a multilateral agreement
- Promote fairness in the evaluations of students’ workloads
- Systematically address *homogenization* and *fragmentation* of HE

2. Methods

- Voluntary accession by HEIs
- Governments endorsement and support through QA mechanisms (when available)
- SEAMEO RIHED as temporary registrar (at least during phases 2. Experiment, 3. Experience and 4. Expand)

3. Advice to governments

- Promote autonomy of HEIs in decisions on recognition of credits and grades while assuring quality (responsibility and ownership by HEIs)
- Promote the notion of accumulation / life-long learning
- Improve liaison among QA agencies and institutions in charge of recognition of credits
- Encourage ratification of international instruments for harmonization (E.g Tokyo Convention)

4. Guiding clauses for HEIs

4.1. Cultural change

- Promote the use of existing credit systems at HEIs level
- Promote the recognition of foreign credits and grades
- Relativize the use of *veto power* of receiving HEIs towards “better negotiated learning agreements”
- Relativize / reduce the use of “exactness” for equivalences
- Promote “coherent modularization”
- Promote the use of selective / optional courses

4.2. Technical aspects: *Asian academic credits & grades*

4.2.1. Academic Credits

- Description of different measurements and values of credits
- Flexible, standard and easy-to-understand transfer procedures
- Use of learning outcomes (at least relative to contact hours) for accreditation of workload
- Accreditation of non-academic workload (internships, voluntary activities, etc)
- Relative value of credits according to kind of course (core / optional)
- Relative value of credits according to HE cycle (Ba. Ma. PhD)
- Accreditation of research activities (Eg. Japan’s thesis seminar)

4.2.2. Grades

- Collect and display information on evaluation methods
- Share information on values of grades and “conversion options”

4.3. Long-distance and virtual learning

- Accreditation, recognition and transfer of credits
- Access and provision of relevant information

4.4. Post graduates

- Notion of accumulation / life-long learning
- Recognition of credits (as opposed to recognition of degrees)

5. Communication

- Promote transparency of study programmes (contents, outcomes, evaluation)
- Create a communication channel:
 - centralized for dissemination to public
 - decentralized for updating data on programmes
- Use of an common “Asian academic transcript” or “Diploma Supplement”

10. Glossary & Acronyms

10.1. Glossary

The following terminology is presented here as reference and to give the reader a consistent understanding of the terms used throughout the study. Many of these concepts follow the definitions set in the Bologna Convention or other Bologna process instruments however they have been adapted to the context of the present study.

Academic / Academician: a person involved in academic work that teaches and /or does research at HE level, typically that is concerned with arts or sciences. There is a tendency to use the words synonymously and most dictionaries provide single definition, typically opting for *academician* as professor and member of a society or academy.

Accreditation: is understood in at least two ways:

- The first related to the HEIs being awarded official recognition upon having met specific quality standards typically set by public agencies. Hence in this sense HEIs are accredited to provide educational services and to issue degrees. Here accreditation represents a form of quality assurance process under which services and operations of HEIs or study programmes are evaluated by an external body (typically a governmental organization) to determine if necessary standards are met.
- The second related to the credits HEIs grant to students who successfully meet the requirements of a learning process and are evaluated positively by the instructors upon completion of a study course or other form of learning process. These credits build as blocks towards a final degree that entails the student to demonstrate skills and knowledge obtained through the study programme. It is in this second sense that the term is used throughout this study.

Accreditation of prior learning (APL) refers to the process of identifying, assessing and acknowledging of learning achievements or experiences and qualifications students may have had in the past. More usually used in the area of vertical mobility.

Accumulation of credits refers to the process by which students add the credits that they have obtained through different courses of a programme. Workload and achievements pile up leading to the award of a full qualification. Systems that allow for accumulation of credits are usually associated with programmes that allow for progression through study programmes.

Articulation of programmes refers to the process that allows students to move around and progress from one completed qualification to another of higher level. Typically this refers to moves from diplomas to bachelor degrees and from there to masters and to doctorates. This process of articulation may happen as a result of recognition of credits or recognition of previous learning experiences or degrees.

Assessment or evaluation criteria refer to the indicators that demonstrate that a learning outcome has been achieved by a student, it constitutes a set of descriptors used to describe and measure what the learner is expected to know or be able to do.

Assessment or evaluation refers to the total amount of written, oral and practical tests/examinations, projects and portfolios, used to evaluate the students' performances and progress in courses or programmes. Assessments typically take place in formal settings where professors or instructors evaluate the performance and achievement of the student throughout and upon completion of study programmes.

Cohort a group of students that started a particular degree programme in the same year.

Competences are a combination of knowledge, understanding, skills and abilities acquired by the students through the process of learning in whatever its form. They are achieved through various ways or course units and they are usually assessed at different stages by instructors. They may be divided into subject-area related specific fields or generic competences that are common to any degree or course.

Condoning refers to a situation where a board of experts gives the right of being exempted to a student by means of reassessing a failed module or by recognizing an already successfully passed course and hence not requesting the student to take that course again.

Contact hours refer to the time students spend with professors or instructors. This is a period of time usually ranging from 45-60 minutes and refers to the amount of time students spend in classes or lectures.

Continuous assessment is the evaluation that occurs in the normal teaching period and contributes to a final assessment.

Convergence refers to the involvement and voluntary adoption of suitable policies for the achievement of a common goal. For this study this refers to the policies and activities carried out by HEIs stakeholders aiming to facilitate permeability and understanding of structures, goals and strategies. The world indicates “coming closer” therefore “harmonizing”.

Course units refer to self-contained, structured in a formal setting where a learning experience takes place. They typically have a coherent and explicit set of outcomes, described as skills to be obtained, and evaluated through an assessment. Course units can also be called modules and they can be assigned with different amounts of credits depending on complexity and amount of workload.

Coursework defines all the tasks students are expected to do in the framework of a course, subject or module.

Credit level indicates the relative complexity or level of difficulty necessary to achieve a certain learning outcome. This relates to the traditional levels within HE, i.e. degrees for diplomas, bachelor, master or doctorate degrees where typically the higher the level the higher the complexity of the workload, as well as the level of autonomy learners account with. The level of credits may also relate to the year of study and/or on the type of course content e.g. basic, advanced, or specialized courses. Based on this different HEIs may attach different values to the academic credits according to their levels and complexity.

Credit systems refer to the models established at the country, provincial level or by HEIs in order to facilitate the measurement and comparison of learning outcomes achieved through different qualifications, study programmes and learning environments on the basis of student workload measured typically in time or outcome. This set of rules basically indicates the way credits are to be attached to courses and express information on the relation between workload to amount of credits.

Credit transfer refers to the process through which students, with the consent from HEIs, “move” the attained credits among different institutions towards the achievement of a given degree, typically based on comparisons and similarities in content and learning outcomes between matched qualifications.

Credit type describes the status of a course unit or modules in the study programme. It can, for example, be described as *core credits* (major course unit), *related credits* (unit providing instrument/support) or *minor credits* (optional course unit).

Credit value is the amount of credits, at a given level, that is attached or assigned to a body of learning, a course or subject. This concept indicates the amount of learning expected and the relative level of difficulty from a particular course in a programme.

Academic credit (or simply credit) represent a way to quantify and express the volume of learning based on the achievement of learning outcomes throughout the efforts carried out in the form of workload usually expressed in time or outcomes, and that show what an average student at the relevant level might be expected to achieve in terms of learning outcomes. Credits constitute a *value attached to a course* or subject to measure the effort required by a student to obtain and learn a given content and to achieve certain outcomes. Different amounts of credits are usually assigned to different courses to show differences in the types of learning and/or qualifications obtained upon completion. They are a form of “academic currency” -different from modules that are curricular tool to divide the curriculum into logical and different parts-.

Curriculum and Syllabus are related yet different concepts. *Curriculum* refers to the complete set of materials taught in the context of a school system; it is a prescriptive notion, as opposed to the *descriptive* syllabus that constitutes the outline of topics covered. While a curriculum prescribes the goals of an educational system, the syllabus describes the means to achieve those goals). Curriculum calls for an understanding that gives meaning to education that is functional and ethical; it works as guiding document that helps teachers in understanding standards that students need to achieve at the end of a developmental stage. A curriculum indicates “what” to teach, “how” it should be taught and helps monitoring of the teaching process or “whether” the curriculum is taught as per the document. A syllabus gives a more focused outline for particular subjects and content. It cannot be equated with curriculum, because a curriculum is for a course while a syllabus is meant for a subject. The syllabus refers to the content, the topics and concepts to be taught, whereas the curriculum is a consideration of the objectives, the content, methods chosen to achieve those objectives.

Cycles are programmes or study courses that upon completion lead to an academic degree. According to the Bologna Declaration, for example, the European area of HE consists of a system that accounts with two main cycles: undergraduate and graduate (bachelor and master). While doctoral programmes are usually seen as a third cycle but more associated to work and research experience.

Degrees are qualifications granted by HEIs to the students after successful completion of a programme. When HE systems work on credit base, typically as accumulation, students complete the programme at the time they have added up a given amount of credits awarded as the result of achieving certain learning outcomes. *Diplomas* are also qualifications that work in the same way as degrees; however they tend to denote shorter academic programmes.

Diploma supplement is a concept developed in the context of the Bologna Process and it works as an *annex to the official degree/qualification*. This document is designed to provide a detailed description of the nature, level, context, content and status of the studies that were pursued and successfully completed by the holder of the degree/qualification. As an information support tool it is used to offer international transparency and facilitate the academic/professional recognition of qualifications.

Doctorate refers to a high level qualification that is generally accepted in describing the qualifications of the holder. It typically relates to original research skills or other forms of high educational performances. Typically it refers to the degree awarded after completion of third cycle studies.

Formal learning refers to the learning process that takes place through a programme that is structured in its aspects of learning and assessment that leads the student to obtain full or partial attainment of a recognised qualifications or other formally recognised qualification.

Home and Host HEIs, these two concepts refer to HEIs that are engaged in exchange programmes of students, whereby the *home* HEIs represents the university or college where the students is registered permanently and from where s/he is expected to obtain the final qualification. While *host* HEIs denote those universities or colleges receiving students to take a temporary period of stay there. These concepts correlate to sending and receiving institutions, however these last terms usually refer to transfers of students on *regular* and *permanent* bases.

Informal learning refers to learning gained through non formal experiences, or outside typical learning contexts such as learning based on work-experience, through family or social activities, may result from hobbies or other leisure activities that bring along a process of learning. Different from formal and non-formal learning processes, informal learning tends to happen in settings that are neither regular nor organised, the learning process tends to be freer, without set goals, time frames or any particular form of learning support.

Learning outcomes are typically described through a set of statements about what a learner is expected to know, understand and/or be able to demonstrate after completion of a process of learning.

Modules are the parts into which a curriculum can be broken down into discrete units of accessible study (subjects, courses, etc). A study programme may be formally a modular structure, where a student builds his degree by acquiring enough credits from independent modules. It may also be informal when the programme is divided (although not necessarily explicitly) into more or less discrete units or subjects. Most study programmes using credit systems are structured upon a logic that adds blocks of knowledge distributed in modules through a progressive and accumulative sequence.

Non-formal learning refers to learning taking place through study programmes that are structured, however that do not necessarily lead to a formally recognised qualification.

Notional hours of learning refer to the time measured in academic hours that a learner is expected to spend (depending on the level), on average, to achieve a given learning outcome at that level.

Qualification descriptors, grades or mark are statements of the outcomes of study for the main qualification at each level that exemplify the nature and characteristics of that qualification. They describe quantitative or qualitatively the performance of the students in a given study course.

Recognition: similar to the case of *accreditation*, the term *Recognition* also offers at least two senses in which it can be understood.

- The first one, more general, relates to the recognition granted to a HEI due to its having achieved a standard or agreed level of quality. In these sense HEIs recognize and are

recognized (or not) by others as quality assured institutions where the programmes they offer are considered proper and providing minimum quality requirements.

- In the second and narrower sense, the term refers to a HEI *accepting* accreditations awarded by another HEI to a student upon successful completion of a course; whereby the act of recognizing academic credits granted by another HEI may (or may not) lead to the student being exempted from having to take a given course if s/he can demonstrate having successfully obtained the minimum requirements in the other HEI. Thus, here recognition means that a HEI considers as valid the qualifications granted by another HEI to a student toward the degree it will eventually award to him/her.

Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) is a process through which students' activities are assessed towards recognition of previous learning experiences to be understood in the framework of academic work. It involves evaluation of the students' prior learning experiences and achievements so as to determine whether or not academic credits are to be assigned and recognized for the academic outcomes s/he may have obtained in the past.

Transcripts are formal records of student's achievements issued by a HE provider or awarding body. These are documents used to describe the title subjects and the grades obtained out of performance from courses taken in official or formal HEIs.

Unit/module is a self-contained, formally structured learning experience with a coherent and explicit set of learning outcomes and assessment criteria. This closely relates to the idea of *courses or subjects* within structured study programmes.

10.2. Acronyms

ADB Asian Development Bank

ASEAN Association of South East Nations

Ba Bachelor degree

ECTS European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System

HE Higher education

HEI(s) Higher education institutions(s)

HES Higher education system

Ma Master degree

PhD Philosophy doctorate

QA Quality assurance

SEA Southeast Asia

SEAMEO RIHED South East Asian Ministries of Education Organization – Regional Centre for Higher Education and Development

11. Resources

- (ECA) European Consortium for Accreditation in higher Education. (2007). *Advancing mutual recognition of accreditation decisions*.
- Adam, S. (2001). Too much or just right: how can information for recognition be improved? *Seminar on Recognition Issues in the Bologna Process, 11-12. apr 2001* (pp. 11–12).
- African Union. (2007). Harmonization of Higher Education Programmes in Africa: Opportunities and Challenges. *Third Ordinary Sesin of the Conference of Ministers of Education of the African Union (COMEDAF III). AU/EXP/EDUC/2 (III)* (p. 83). Johannesburg, South Africa: African Union.
- Allen, R., & Geoff, L. (1995). *Credit-Based Systems as Vehicles for Change in Universities and Colleges. Managing Innovation and Change in Universities and Colleges*. Stylus Publishing. Retrieved from http://www.eric.ed.gov/ERICWebPortal/search/detailmini.jsp?_nfpb=true&_ERICExtSearch_SearchValue_0=ED410841&ERICExtSearch_SearchType_0=no&accno=ED410841
- Altbach, P. G. (2009). The Giants Awake: The Present and Future of Higher Education Systems in China and India. In Centre for Educational Research and Innovation (Ed.), *Higher Education to 2030. Volume 2 Globalization* (pp. 179–204). OECD.
- Asahara, T., & Hotta, T. (2010). *Study on the ACTS (ASEAN Credit Transfer System) and Credit Transfer Systems in Asian Nations*.
- Asia Cooperation Dialogue. (2011). *Asian Credit Transfer Systems (ACTS)*. Kuala Lumpur.
- Asia e University. (n.d.). *ASIAN Credit Transfer System (ACTS)*. Kuala Lumpur.
- Asian Development Bank. (2009). Strategic Framework and Action Plan for Human Resource Development in the Greater Mekong Subregion (2009–2012). *GMS e. C. Program. Manila, Asian Development Bank, (August 2009)*.
- Banks, M., & Bhandari, R. (2012). Global Student Mobility. In D. K. Deardoff, H. de Wit, J. D. Heyl, & T. Adams (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of international higher educ* (pp. 379–396). Singapore: SAGE.
- Bekhradnia, B. (2004). Credit accumulation and transfer, and the Bologna process: an overview. *Higher Education Policy Institute, (October)*, 1–54. Retrieved from <http://www.bccat.ca/pubs/13CATFullReport.pdf>
- Bergan, S., Divis, J., & Rauhvargers, A. (2000). Bridges over Troubled Waters: Bologna and the Recognition of Qualifications. *Journal of Studies in International Education, 4(2)*, 11–20. doi:10.1177/102831530000400203

- Betts, M., & Smith, R. (1998). *Developing the Credit-based Modular Curriculum in Higher Education* (p. 167). Hong Kong: Falmer Press.
- Bhandari, R., & Blumenthal, P. (2011). Global Student Mobility and the Twenty-first Century Silk Road: National Trends and Directions. In R. Bhandari & P. Blumenthal (Eds.), *International Students and Global Mobility in Higher Education. National Trends and New Directions* (pp. 1–23). New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Chien, C., Kot, F. C., & Mpinganjira, M. (2011). Building regional higher education capacity through academic mobility. *SARUA Leadership Dialogue Series*, 3(1). Retrieved from http://ahero.uwc.ac.za/index.php?module=cshe&action=viewtitle&id=cshe_800
- Council of Europe. (2011). *Convention on the Recognition of Qualifications Concerning Higher Education in the European Region*. Council of Europe.
- Damme, D. Van. (2000). Internationalization and quality assurance: towards worldwide accreditation? *European Journal for Education Law and Policy*, (July), 11–14. Retrieved from <http://www.springerlink.com/index/g32h927071643070.pdf>
- De Prado Yepes, C. (2007). Regionalisation of higher education services in Europe and East Asia and potential for global change. *Asia Europe Journal*, 5(1), 83–92. doi:10.1007/s10308-006-0069-z
- De Prado Yepes, C. (2006). World Regionalization of Higher Education: Policy Proposals for International Organizations. *Higher Education Policy*, 19(1), 111–128. doi:10.1057/palgrave.hep.8300113
- European Commission, Council of Europe, & UNESCO/CEPES. (n.d.). *Outline structure for the diploma supplement*. Theologische Hochschule Friedensau.
- European Communities. (2009). *ECTS users guide 2009*.
- Gaston, P. L. (2010). *The Challenge of Bologna* (p. 225). Virginia: Stylus Publishing.
- Grosjes, T., & Barchiesi, D. (2007). European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System: An Alternative Way to Calculate the ECTS Grades. *Higher Education in Europe*, 32(2-3), 213–227. doi:10.1080/03797720701840807
- Harris, J. (2002). *Brief History of American Academic Credit System: A Recipe for Incoherence in Student Learning*.
- Hawkins, J. N. (2012). Regionalization and harmonization of higher education in Asia: Easier said than done. *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 1(1), 96–108. doi:10.1108/20463161211194496
- Hirosato, Y. (2012). International/Regional Cooperation among Universities in Asia – Current Status and Future Prospects. RCAP Seminar. *RCAP Seminar*.

- Hotta, T. (2010a). Section 1 : Comparative Table of 13 Asian Countries. *ACTS(ASEAN Credit Transfer System) と各国の単位互換に関する調査研究* (pp. 1–14). Hiroshima: Hiroshima University.
- Hotta, T. (2010b). Chapter 4: Summary of Data Analysis1 Section 2: Issues and prospects of student exchanges with quality assurance in Asia. *ACTS(ASEAN Credit Transfer System) と各国の単位互換に関する調査研究* (pp. 1–3).
- Huisman, J., Adelman, C., Hiseh, C., Shams, F., & Wilkins, S. (2012). Europe's Bologna Process and Its Impact on Global Higher Education. In D. K. Deardorff, H. de Wit, J. D. Heyl, & T. Adams (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of international higher educ* (pp. 81–96). Singapore: SAGE.
- Hutt, J. (2009). Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales Delivering the Promise Implementation Plan and Handbook 2009 – 2014. Welsh Assembly Government. Retrieved from www.wales.gov.uk/educationandskills
- Junor, S., & Usher, A. (2008). *Student mobility and credit transfer: A national and global survey*. Educational Policy Institute. Retrieved from <http://higherstrategy.com/wp-content/uploads/2011/07/CreditTransfer.pdf>
- Kamogawa, A. (2012). Student Mobility Programs towards Asian Regional Networks in Higher Education: ses of Regional Organizations and Universities in Thailand, Malaysia, Singapore, and Japan. *Education at the Dawn of the New Decade: When the Quality and Sustainability Movements Converges*. Bangkok: Comparative Education Society of Asia.
- Kargidis, T., Kefalas, P., Stamat, D., & Tsadiras, A. (2003). *Towards a European Credit Transfer System for Networked Learning (ECTS-NL). ... on Networked ...* (pp. 1–9). Greece. Retrieved from <http://www.city.academic.gr/special/research/xcityng/papers/Kar-Kef-Sta-Tsa-03.pdf>
- Kell, P., & Volg, G. (2012). *International Students in the Asia Pacific, mobility, risks and Global Optimism* (p. 197). London, New York: Springer.
- Knight, J. (2008). *Higher Education in Turmoil. The changing World of Internationalization* (p. 241). Rotterdam: Sense Publishers.
- Knight, J. (2012). Concepts, Rationales, and Interpretive Frameworks in the Internationalization of Higher Education. In D. K. Deardoff, H. de Wit, J. D. Heyl, & T. Adams (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of international higher educ* (pp. 27–42). Singapore: SAGE.
- Mongkhonvanit, P., & Emery, L. S. (2003). Asian Perspectives on European Higher Education. *Higher Education in Europe*, 28(1), 51–56. doi:10.1080/0379772032000110107
- Morrison, H., Cowan, P., & Harte, S. (1997). The Impact of Modular Aggregation on the Reliability of Final Degrees and the Transparency of European Credit Transfer.

Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education, 22(4), 405–417.
doi:10.1080/0260293970220405

- Neubauer, D. E. (2012). Introduction: Giving Dimension and Direction to Mobility and Migration in Asian Pacific Higher Education. In D. E. Neubauer & K. Kuroda (Eds.), *Mobility and Migration in Asia Pacific Higher Education* (p. 239). New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Nguyen, A. T. (2009). The role of regional organizations in East Asian regional cooperation and integration in the field of higher education. *Asian Regional Integration Review*, 1, 69–82. Retrieved from http://kms1.isn.ethz.ch/serviceengine/Files/ISN/138243/ichaptersection_singledocument/b1bbf25f-10e6-4f87-b9dc-3a70fadf4127/en/Vol_1_Article_5.pdf
- Omar, R., Jan, J. M., Hamid, H. A., & Akhir, A. M. (2009). The humanities in Asean studies and higher education-Teaching of ASEAN History in Higher Education.
- Oyewole, O. (n.d.). *Harmonisation of Degree structures , and Regional Qualifications frameworks in the African Higher Education Space* (pp. 1–12).
- Polytechnics International New Zealand Ltd. (2011). Implementing the Greater Mekong Sub-region Human Resource Development Strategic Framework and Action Plan. Asian Development Bank.
- Rauhvargers, A. (2004). *Recognition of foreign qualifications* (p. 43).
- Regel, O. (1992). *The Academic Credit System in Higher Education: Effectiveness and Relevance in Developing Countries*.
- Reinalda, B. (2011). Asian and European Backgrounds of international Rankings. *ru.nl*. Retrieved from http://www.ru.nl/publish/pages/614169/helsinki_university_rankings_2011_paper_bob_reinalda.pdf
- Rumley, L. E., Altbach, P. G., & Reisberg, L. (2012). Internationalization Within The Higher Education Context. In D. K. Deardorff, H. de Wit, J. D. Heyl, & T. Adams (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of international higher educ* (pp. 3–26). Singapore: SAGE.
- Sakamoto, R., & Chapman, D. W. (2011). Expanding Across Borders: The Growth of Cross-Border Partnerships in Higher Education. In R. Sakamoto & D. W. Chapman (Eds.), *Cross-border Partnerships in Higher Education. Strategies and Issues* (pp. 3–15). New York: Routledge.
- Salmi, J. (2001). Tertiary Education in the 21st Century: Challenges and Opportunities. *Journal of the Programme on Institutional Management in Higher Education*, 13(2).
- SEAMEO RIHED. (2011a). SEAMEO RIHED 2010/2011 Annual Report. Retrieved March 13, 2013, from http://www.rihed.seameo.org/mambo/publication/annual_rept10_11.pdf

- SEAMEO RIHED. (2011b). Building a Common Credit Transfer System in Southeast Asia Region. Policy Action Research. Bangkok.
- Shedd, J. M. (2003). The History of the Student Credit Hour. *New Directions for Higher Education*, 2003(122), 5–12. doi:10.1002/he.106
- Sirat, M. (2012). “Shared Space” in Global Higher Education: A Southeast Asian Perspective. In D. E. Neubauer & K. Kuroda (Eds.), *Mobility and Migration in Asian Pacific Higher Education* (pp. 53–64). New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Spöttl, G., & Becker, M. (2005). Work Related Zones of Mutual Trust (WRZMT) as a Basis for a Model for Credit Transfer in Vocational Education and Training Discussion paper. Flensburg.
- Steiner, D. (1996). European Higher Education and the issues of Tradition, transfer-credits, and Credibility. *Higher Education in Europe*, 21(4), 65–75. doi:10.1080/0379772960210407
- Sullivan, K. P. H. (2002). Credit and Grade Transfer within the European Union’s SOCRATES Programme: Unity in diversity or head in the sand? *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 27(1), 65–74. doi:10.1080/02602930120105063
- The ASEM education secretariat. (n.d.). Credit Systems and Learning Outcomes in ASEM Member Countries. Bonn: ASEM Education Secretariat.
- The Inter-University Council for East Africa. (n.d.). *The need to establish a regional system of accreditation of higher education institutions and programmes in East Africa* (pp. 1–6).
- The World Bank. (2009). *Putting Higher Education to Work. Skills and Research for Growth in East Asia* (p. 222). Washington DC: The World Bank.
- Tillman, M. (2012). Employer Perspectives on International Education. In D. K. Deardorff, H. de Wit, J. D. Heyl, & T. Adams (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of international higher education* (pp. 191–205). Singapore: SAGE.
- Tomusk, V. (2004). Three Bolognas and a Pizza Pie: notes on institutionalization of the European higher education system. *International Studies in Sociology of Education*, (March 2013), 37–41. Retrieved from <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09620210400200120>
- UMAP. (2011). Features & Timeline: UMAP Student Connection Online [USCO] Implementation: 1-2011.
- Umemiya, N. (2008). Regional Quality Assurance Activity in Higher Education in Southeast Asia: Its Characteristics and Driving Forces. *Quality in Higher Education*, 14(3), 277–290. doi:10.1080/13538320802507679

- UNESCO. (1983). UNESCO - Regional Convention on the Recognition of Studies, Diplomas and Degrees In Higher Education in Asia and the Pacific. UNESCO. Retrieved from http://portal.unesco.org/education/en/ev.php-URL_ID=13959&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html
- UNESCO. (2009). Asia-Pacific Regional Convention on the Recognition of Qualifications in Higher Education (Tokyo Convention). Tokyo: UNESCO.
- UNESCO. (2011). Revised Asia-Pacific Regional Convention on the Recognition of Qualifications in Higher Education. Tokyo: UNESCO. Retrieved from http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=48975&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html
- Vincent-Lancrin, S. (2009). Cross-border Higher Education: trends and perspectives. In Centre for Educational Research and Innovation (Ed.), *Higher Education to 2030. Volume 2 Globalization* (pp. 63–86). OECD.
- Witte, J., Huisman, J., & Purser, L. (2009). European Higher Education Reforms in the Context of the Bologna Process: How did we get here, Where are we and where are we going? In Centre for Educational Research and Innovation (Ed.), *Higher Education to 2030. Volume 2 Globalization* (pp. 205–225). OECD.
- Woldetensae, Y. (2011). Reinforcing the AU Harmonization Strategy towards Establishing the Space of Higher Education in Africa: Some Pragmatic Approaches. *Conference of Rectors, Vice Chancellors and Presidents of African Universities Stellenbosch, South Africa, May 30 – June 3 2011*.
- Woodfield, S. (2012). Key Trends and Emerging Issues in International Student Mobility. In F. Maringe & N. Foskett (Eds.), *Globalization and Internationalization in Higher Education. Theoretical Strategic and Management Perspectives* (pp. 109–122). London, New York: Continuum International Publishing Group.
- Yavaprabhas, S. (2009). Experiences of Asian Higher Education Frameworks and their Implications for the Future. In K. Kuroda, M. Kamikubo, & D. Passarelli (Eds.), *Formulating and International Higher Education Framework for Regional Cooperation and Integration in Asia*. Waseda University Global COE Program, Global Institute for Asian Regional Integration.
- Yavaprabhas, S. (2010). Regional Efforts Toward Harmonization in Higher Education in SEA: Where is it headed? *6th IIEP-SEAMEO RIHED Workshop on Institutional Restructuring in Higher Education*. Retrieved from <http://www.rihed.seameo.org/mambo/uploadfiles/bali/harmoni.pdf>

12. Annexes DATA (in CD attached)

Content	Page
Annex 1: CTS Categories of comparison	2
Annex 2: COMPARISON OF CREDIT TRANSFER SYSTEMS	3
Annex 3: Individual Credit Transfer system charts	59
1. Asia e University / Asian Credit Transfer System	59
2. ASEAN University Network /ASEAN Credit Transfer System	71
3. CAMPUS Asia	81
4. ECTS European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System	86
6. Arab Space for Higher Education	123
7. ASEM Asia Europe Meeting	126
8. Asia Exchange / Europe Credit Transfer System	130
N/A	131
9. Association of African Universities	137
10. Credit Accumulation and Transfer System East African Countries, Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania	140
11. Carnegie Unit and Student Hour	147
12. Crédito Latinoamericano de Referencia (CLAR) Proyecto TUNING LATIN AMERICAN CONTEXT	151
13. EAUI East Asian University Institute (EAUI) for Asian Region	158
14. The Go8 Credit Transfer Agreement (Australia) Group of 8 universities	162
15. CTS SADC South African Development Community	166
16. CQFW Credit and Qualifications Framework for Wales	170
17. Credit Transfer system at The University of Melbourne	181
18. EU-ASEAN Credit Transfer System leading to Implementation of Student Mobility and Joint-Award Degree Programs in Engineering Education	186
19. Credit system at The Open University (UK)	193
20. QAA Quality Assurance Agency UK	198

13. Country reports (in CD attached)

Content	Page
Comparison of Credit transfer systems in the region (compact from country reports)	1
1. Cambodia	8
2. China	25
3. Indonesia	43
4. Japan	52
5. Lao People's Democratic Republic	77
6. Malaysia	98
7. Myanmar	118
8. Republic of Korea	139
9. Thailand	154
10. Vietnam	164